

Utah Lake Limnocorral Study 2024

Progress Report

To
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Title page figure. Path diagram of ecological (physical, chemical, and biological) latent components and their observed constituents. Interactions including direct and indirect effects between constituents within each latent component and between components are numerous but are not shown.

SUMMARY

In just over a century, Utah Lake, a descendent of Lake Bonneville, has undergone an ecosystem shift and hysteresis from a clear water healthy state with high complexity (low entropy) to a degraded turbid, lower complexity state (high entropy) and is now primarily managed as a storage reservoir. The lake is presently dominated by only a few non-analog invasive taxa including Common Carp and other nonnative fishes and pollution tolerant native species. Ecosystem engineering and keystone native species including Bonneville cutthroat trout, macrophytes (aquatic plants) and mollusks (clams, mussels, snails) have all but been completely extirpated.

There is considerable concern by citizens and managers as to the future of Utah Lake and what can be done to improve its condition (i.e., health, integrity), including the reduction of potentially harmful algal blooms and restoration of its native biota. However, there has been little to no effort expended to examine or understand the importance of the lake's food web and how top-down, trophic cascades effect and respond to current conditions or how biomanipulation may help restore its ecosystem health despite decades of research documenting their importance worldwide. Successful Utah Lake restoration cannot proceed without this understanding and holistic based implementation.

To help understand how to restore Utah Lake, we conducted limnocorral- mesocosm experiments from 2021 to 2024 that bridged the gap between highly controlled laboratory experiments that target causality of underlying mechanisms and unfeasible whole level ecosystem experiments. This progress report focuses on results from data collected between June 18 and October 9, 2024.

The overall goal was to understand factors that influence nutrient cycling, algal blooms, food web dynamics, and ecosystem functioning that contribute to the impairment of the ecological health of Utah Lake, particularly the effects of wind driven wave turbulence. Results from our research will help direct managers on how best to initiate restoration, focusing on an integrated and adaptive management strategy essential for improving its health. Specifically, we examined the direct and indirect effects of wave action, bioturbator exclusion, and phosphorus addition on:

1. Chemistry
2. Light attenuation,
3. Phytoplankton assemblages,
4. Zooplankton assemblages,
5. Benthic algae (periphyton) assemblages,
6. Benthic invertebrate assemblages,
7. and their interactions.

We postulated that the application of these treatments would have measurable direct and indirect effects on chemistry and the four assemblages.

We present seven chapters in this report:

Chapter 1: Introduction, Justification, Goals

Chapter 2: Chemistry

Chapter 3: Light Attenuation

Chapter 4: Phytoplankton and Periphyton

Chapter 5: Zooplankton

Chapter 6: Benthic Invertebrates

Chapter 7: Recommendations

Results

Chemistry

Multivariate statistical analyses showed that components of the chemistry assemblage varied by sample date that was unanticipated, and that the chemistry assemblage differed between the water column inside of corrals and the lake water column. There was strong evidence that many water column chemical variables increased throughout the study period including, pH, DO, conductivity, TSS, VSS, TP, dissolved P, ortho P, NH₃, COD, Al, K, and Mg. Water temperature and Ca decreased. Chemical variables that were likely to be greater inside corrals included ChlA, pH, VSS, Ortho P, TP, and dissolved P. DO tended to be lower inside corrals. Wave break/bioturbator reduction and phosphorus additions demonstrated that there were measurable differences in chemistry inside corrals vs. in the lake and that restoration efforts geared towards stabilizing sediments will be beneficial. In addition, corral treatments likely caused direct and indirect interactions between chemical variables and biota.

Light Attenuation

Light attenuation, the rate at which light diminishes as depth increases, required a separate chapter because of its extreme importance to Utah Lake's ecosystem function. Light attenuation varied throughout the duration of the study, among corrals, and within the lake. Differences between PAR (photosynthetically active radiation) inside corrals and in the lake were primarily due to reduction in wave action sediment disturbance. Slopes of regression lines of \ln mean PAR vs depth varied by date and were almost always steeper inside corrals. PAR was higher at shallower depths and less at deeper depths in the lake than inside corrals. The theoretical photosynthesis light limit ($0.01 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) also varied and was predicted to occur at lower depths inside corrals on most dates with strong evidence that on average it was deeper inside corrals. This was likely due to reduction in calcium carbonate, CaCO₃ crystal precipitate inside corrals that can cause light backscatter. Other covariates likely affected light attenuation including phytoplankton densities (as measured by Chl A), conductivity, and ORP (oxygen reduction potential). Wave action disturbance on easily resuspended sediments, including CaCO₃

precipitates, in Utah Lake alters light attenuation and is a major factor affecting ecosystem function, hindering restoration efforts. Ecological and restoration implications of improved light attenuation via reduced disturbance are immense for Utah Lake including improved food web interactions and trophic transfer of energy. Restoration measures necessary to reduce attenuation include, establishment of benthic algae, macrophytes, and native mollusks, and improved lake level management or mechanical sediment stabilization.

Phytoplankton and Periphyton

In a healthy state, Utah Lake's primary production should have substantially greater contribution from benthic sources, including benthic algae and aquatic macrophytes, given its shallow nature. Algal blooms, including potentially toxic cyanobacteria blooms (HABs) now occur regularly during summer months. The most important factor contributing to this non-analog condition is sediment resuspension from wave action and bioturbators e.g., carp and catfish, and loss of sediment stabilizing macrophytes and bivalve mollusks. A total of 179 phytoplankton samples were collected and processed in our 2024 study. Seventy-seven phytoplankton taxa were identified from seven algal divisions. Chlorophytes (54%) were the most abundant division followed by cyanophytes (22%), and bacillariophytes (10%). The other four divisions Chrysophyta, Dinophyta, Euglenophyta, and Xanthophyceae comprised 14% of taxa. Several taxa dominated the phytoplankton assemblage in our study both by biovolume and by frequency of occurrences (number of samples taxon occurred in), primarily *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (cyanophyte), *Ceratium hirundinella* (dinophyte), *Dolichospermum circinalis* (cyanophyte), and *Chlamydomonas* sp. (chlorophyte).

There was strong evidence of seasonal phytoplankton assemblage patterns using Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling and Multiple Response Permutation Procedure. Although phytoplankton assemblages varied by sampling date, there was not as pronounced of a seasonal progression as we have reported elsewhere in Utah Lake or as occurs throughout temperate regions in aquatic ecosystems. Several taxa were more common and abundant inside corrals compared to the lake including, *Chlamydomonas* sp. (chlorophyte), pennate diatoms (bacillariophyte), *Cryptomonas* sp. (cryptophyte), and *Dolichospermum circinalis* (cyanophyte). One taxon was an indicator of outside corrals, *Desmodesmus intermedius* (chlorophyte) but that species was uncommon. Pennate diatoms are primarily associated with stable conditions including benthic substrate or grow as part of the periphyton community (e.g., on sides of corrals). It is well worth noting that improved stable conditions inside corrals allowed pennate diatoms to increase in abundance and become indicator species. Five richness and diversity indices varied by sampling date and there was good evidence ($p < 0.05$ to < 0.10) that all five indices were greater inside corrals than outside signifying improved conditions within the corrals.

Each phytoplankton taxon reacted differently to measured variables demonstrating that it is imperative to taxonomically identify phytoplankton to the lowest practical taxon.

Our best fit Structural Equation Model (SEM) of the six dominant taxa in relation to five chemistry variables provided direct, indirect, and total effects and had an $R^2 = 0.91$. The SEM model provided good to strong evidence of positive and negative interactions between and among phytoplankton taxa and nutrients. For example, *Dolichospermum circinalis* and *Ceratium*

hirundinella either coexisted or facilitated *Aphanizomenon flosaquae*, but facilitation was not reciprocal. *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* seemed to positively affect *Oscillatoria* sp. but not the opposite. *Dolichospermum circinalis* was negatively associated with *Phormidium* sp. *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* facilitated *Oscillatoria* sp. but it was not reciprocal. Indirect effects were numerous, and these influenced the level of total effects.

We also found strong evidence that corrals themselves had the most effect on abundant phytoplankton taxa including *Aphanizomenon flosaquae*, *Dolichospermum circinalis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Cryptomonas* sp., pennate diatoms, *Euglena* sp., and *Aulacoseira granulata* var. *angustissima*. Phosphorus additions also had positive effects. All these taxa tended to be at least more abundant inside some of the treated corrals or control corrals than outside. *Euglena* sp. and *Aulacoseira granulata* var. *angustissima* seemed to have benefitted the most from the first phosphorus addition but were not more abundant in the second treatment corrals or the control corrals than the lake.

Attached algal growth that formed the periphyton community on the bottom of corrals and on the sides of the corrals were abundant and, in some instances luxurious later in the season (August through October). Periphytic algae on the sides of corrals were observed to be denser with longer filaments on southern facing areas of the corrals. Superficially the periphytic filamentous algae appeared to be composed of only one or two taxa however, on microscopic examination, its community was often diverse with many other algal taxa found within their filaments for a total of thirty taxa. Periphyton biomass increased over the study period starting around September 4, and there appeared to be greater biomass in the P treated corrals on August 15 and September 4. However, we did not find statistical evidence for differences.

The positive effects of limnocorrals on the phytoplankton and periphyton assemblage clearly implicates wave induced turbidity, mostly in the form of sediment resuspension and unstable substrates as leading impairments to Utah Lake's health. Bioturbation also continues to be a problem that needs to be rectified. The observed growth of periphyton on the side of corrals should not be underestimated because the establishment of benthic and periphytic algae could have tremendous positive effects on Utah Lake's ecosystem. We suggest that a more diverse, balanced phytoplankton and periphyton rich assemblages in Utah Lake will also help dampen the intensity and occurrences of harmful algal blooms and should be a main goal of restoration.

Zooplankton

Zooplankton are the key intermediary between phytoplankton primary production and fish assemblages. They are the main consumers of phytoplankton, can be omnivorous or carnivorous, and are the primary prey item of small fish including juvenile white bass, and even large adult carp in Utah Lake. Zooplankton are the epicenter of Utah Lake's food web, trophic level energy transfer, nutrient cycling, and ecosystem function. The zooplankton assemblage is not only a function of the effects of recent conditions (bottom-up control), but they also contribute top-down control. Their food web interactions are fully two-way: zooplankton both influence and are influenced directly by primary producers and tertiary consumers. However, there has been almost no research on these invaluable members of the lake's ecosystem.

Our 2024 mesocosm study found additional strong evidence that zooplankton assemblage composition and relative abundances exhibit rapid seasonality and can still respond to ecosystem changes induced by our mesocosms that further highlights the limited resilience and adaptability of zooplankton assemblages in Utah Lake. Mesocosm altered zooplankton-phytoplankton assemblage interactions differed from lake zooplankton-phytoplankton assemblage interactions. For example, inside corrals there was a strong positive relation between zooplankton densities and phytoplankton biovolumes up until about 4.1×10^7 (95% CIs 2.9×10^7 , 5.4×10^7) $\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$. It appears that above these phytoplankton biovolumes, zooplankton were unable to have top-down control on phytoplankton blooms. Contrarily, there was no relation between zooplankton densities and phytoplankton biovolumes outside of corrals at any phytoplankton biovolume.

Only seventeen zooplankton taxa were found during summer months and only five taxa dominated, *Acanthocyclops americanus*, *Daphnia retrocurva*, *Leptodiaptomus sicilis*, *Diaphanosoma cf. heberti*, and *Daphnia mendotae*, the latter of which was an indicator of conditions inside corrals. Richness and diversity indices generally showed that the zooplankton assemblages inside corrals were in better health than in the lake. Because of so few zooplankton taxa and the importance of each taxon to Utah Lake's ecosystem, we focused our zooplankton analyses on the dominant taxa relationships. A best fit SEM showed that most interactions were one-way effects of zooplankton on phytoplankton or on each other. The only interaction where phytoplankton taxa influenced zooplankton was *Phormidium* sp. negatively affecting *Diaphanosoma cf. heberti*.

Results from the 2024 study presented here support our past findings that reducing turbation can have significant effects on the zooplankton assemblage in Utah Lake. These findings are important additions to our accumulating scientific knowledge of the lake's food web and ecosystem function and are invaluable for holistic, science-based restoration of Utah Lake. However, we need to combine all years of our mesocosm studies with other research to get a better understanding of the ecosystem and the beneficial effects of reducing sediment resuspension and increased nutrient utilization. Results from this 2024 study combined with our past limnocorral studies can be combined to populate useful ecosystem function models to guide restoration and lake management.

We suggest that zooplankton assemblage composition and their ecosystem function will likely improve more rapidly than higher trophic levels (e.g. fish assemblages) in the food web after reducing turbation via restoration that includes macrophyte establishment in the littoral zone, mollusk reintroduction, a balanced fishery, and focused mechanical sediment stabilization or removal.

Benthic Invertebrates

The dominant benthic invertebrates in Utah Lake presently consist of just a handful of taxa, predominantly pollution tolerant chironomid (midge) larvae, segmented worms (oligochaetes and lumbricids), and non-segmented (nematode) worms, except for a few isolated locations where macrophytes still exist in the littoral zone housing more diverse invertebrate assemblages. However, much of the lake exists as profundal zone and considered chronically impaired.

Sixteen macroinvertebrate taxa and six zooplankton taxa were collected and identified in our benthic survey 2024. Most were chironomid taxa (N = 10). Multiple response permutation procedure showed that the (benthic) invertebrate assemblages strongly differed between sample dates and between inside vs. outside vs. periphyton habitats. Invertebrate densities were orders of magnitude greater in the periphyton growing on the inside of corrals than in the bottom of corrals or lake sediments. Two species of chironomids were indicators of the benthic substrate community inside corrals, *Cladotanytarsus* sp. and *Glyptotendipes* sp. One species of lumbricid worm, *Eiseniella* sp. was an indicator of the benthic substrate community outside of corrals in the lake. Six taxa were indicators of the periphyton community within the periphyton growing on the insides of corrals, *Glyptotendipes* sp., *Cricotopus sylvestris* grp., *Parachironomus* sp., Oligochaeta, Naididae, and Ostracoda. Limnocorrals had a measurable improvement on invertebrate taxa richness (number of taxa), evenness, two diversity indices (Shannon and Simpson), and the effective number of benthic macroinvertebrate taxa. These metrics did however decrease over the study period reflecting changes in seasonal conditions and increased dominance by a few taxa. We suggest that the low effective number of benthic invertebrate taxa is of concern because it reflects the degraded condition of Utah Lake's benthic environment. Dominance by only three pollution tolerant taxa is a red flag in all biological assessments of water quality throughout the world. However, these remaining three dominant taxa are now the default keystone ecosystem engineers that struggle to maintain the lake's present ecological state and are a crucial component of the lake's food web. Also, the amazing proliferation of invertebrate diversity and abundance within the periphyton community unequivocally shows that by stabilizing sediments, increasing light penetration to the sediments, and reestablishing macrophytes and mollusks, Utah Lake's ecosystem can be put on the road to recovery.

Recommendations

Several recommendations based on this progress report, past reports, and our collective knowledge of Utah Lake's ecosystem include:

- Combine results from all our mesocosm studies and analyze.
- Assign and conduct functional traits analysis on our data.
- Continue funding and conducting limnocorral studies.
- Initiate holistic and adaptive restoration efforts for Utah Lake outlined in each of our progress reports.

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Introduction, Justification, Goals	1
Utah Lake Past and Present	1
Justification	3
Why Mesocosms	4
Limnocorral Study Goals	4
Limnocorral Design 2024	5
Phosphorus Additions	6
Acknowledgements	6
Literature Cited	7
Chapter 2: Chemistry	9
Introduction	9
Methods	10
Statistical Analyses	10
Results	12
Assemblages	13
Chemistry Assemblage Indicators	15
Chemical variability and corral effects	17
Treatment Effects	21
Discussion	25
Literature Cited	25
Chapter 3: Light Attenuation	26
Introduction	27
Methods	27
Light attenuation	27
Statistical methods	28
Results	28
CaCO ₃ Backscatter	34
Other covariates affecting light attenuation	38
Discussion	41
Ecological and Restoration Implications	43

Food web	44
Acknowledgements	45
Recommendations	45
Literature Cited.....	45
Chapter 4: Phytoplankton and Periphyton.....	49
Introduction	49
Methods.....	49
Phytoplankton Sampling and Processing.....	49
Periphyton Sampling and Processing.....	50
Statistical Methods	50
Results.....	52
Phytoplankton Assemblages	60
Phytoplankton taxa in relation to sample date, inside vs. outside corrals, temperature, and blooms.....	67
Phytoplankton Richness and Diversity	67
Temperature and Solar Radiation effects	70
Relationships of cyanobacteria (HABs) with Fe, Mg, Ca, nutrients, and other dominant phytoplankton taxa.....	72
Methods.....	72
Results.....	72
Corral and phosphorus treatment effects on dominant phytoplankton taxa	74
Periphyton	75
Discussion.....	80
Phytoplankton.....	80
Periphyton	82
Literature Cited.....	83
Chapter 5: Zooplankton	87
Introduction	87
Methods.....	88
Field	88
Laboratory	88
Statistical Methods	89
Results.....	91

Taxa	91
Assemblage level	93
Richness and Diversity	96
Individual Taxa	97
Zooplankton and P treatments	104
Phytoplankton- Zooplankton Interactions	105
Discussion	108
Conclusion.....	108
Literature Cited.....	109
Additional Readings	111
Addendum: The importance of zooplankton and bivalve interactions in Utah Lake	113
Chapter 6: Benthic Invertebrates.....	114
Introduction	114
Goal.....	114
Methods.....	114
Benthic Invertebrate Sampling, Processing, and Taxonomic Identification.....	114
Processing and Taxonomy.....	115
Statistical Analyses	116
Results.....	116
Benthic Invertebrate Assemblages	117
Densities.....	122
Indicator Species.....	122
Richness and Diversity Metrics.....	123
Discussion	126
Conclusion.....	127
Literature Cited.....	127
Chapter 7: Recommendations	131
Research.....	131
Restoration.....	131
Literature Cited.....	132
Appendices.....	133

Chapter 1: Introduction, Justification, Goals

Utah Lake Past and Present

Utah Lake, $\approx 380 \text{ km}^2$, is but a small remnant of oligo-mesotrophic paleo Lake Bonneville, once nearly as large as present day Lake Michigan. Utah Lake is now a shallow, turbid, eutrophic, slightly saline-brackish¹ lake managed as a storage reservoir with an unnatural flow regime. Its ecosystem has been severely degraded ever since first settlement by Americans of European descent, almost 150 years ago (Richards 2022a).

Utah Lake has lost its ecological integrity² and by most quantitative, qualitative, and bioassessment based standards remains in poor health³. The major loss of integrity occurred when the lake transitioned from a low entropy⁴, stable, clear water state to a turbid, higher entropy state of unpredictable stability shortly after settler population growth in Utah Valley, circa late 1800s. This transition rapidly depleted the lake's native biota, deteriorated its food web, reduced water quality, and altered ecosystem function (Janetski 1990, Richards et al. 2022 a, b, c, d, Richards and Miller 2024). Utah Lake's resilience to future perturbation and resistance to improvement (restoration) now appears to be conceded (Richards and Miller 2024).

Presently, Utah Lake's ecosystem is dominated by only a handful of non-analog taxa including invasive Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*), other non-native fishes such as White Bass (*Morone chrysops*) and Channel Catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*), and pollution tolerant (native) chironomids (Richards and Miller 2024, Richards 2022a). Primary production is presently co-dominated by water column production and strongly respiring benthic detritus production, mostly apparently derived from detrital 'rain' (Richards and Miller 2024). The lake has low robustness (e.g., resistance), is well below optimal trophic functioning, and despite its long geologic history is now stalled at an 'immature' early succession stage, primarily because of chronic wave action and unnatural water level fluctuations that consistently disturb unconsolidated sediments, reset the food web and prevent maturation and stability of the system (Richards and Miller 2024).

¹ During low water years, Utah Lake **conductivity** often ranges from 1200 to 1700 $\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ indicative of slightly saline or brackish water conditions.

² **Ecological integrity** is the sum of physical, chemical, and biological integrity. Integrity implies an unimpaired condition or the quality or state of being complete or undivided; it implies correspondence with some original condition (Karr 1993, 1996).

³ **Ecological health** implies a flourishing condition, well-being, vitality, or prosperity. An ecosystem is healthy when it performs all its vital functions normally and properly; a healthy ecosystem is resilient, able to recover from many stresses; a healthy ecosystem requires minimal outside care" (Karr 1996).

Chapter 1: Introduction

In just a brief geological timeframe, Utah Lake has undergone an ecosystem shift and hysteresis⁴ from a clear water state with high complexity (low entropy, high ecoexergy⁵) to a turbid, lower complexity state (high entropy, low ecoexergy), a classic example of a large shallow lake rapidly increasing in entropy after deterioration of its native mature food web that for millennia evolved to resist entropy (Scheffer et al. 2001, Berrios et al. 2017, Silow et al. 2011). One of the key components in this transition has been the loss of the lake's robust near shore, littoral zone community (Richards et al. 2023).

Utah Lake once had a littoral zone that extended as far out into the lake as shore bound early explorers could see or from make-shift reed boats (Janetski 1990, Carter 2005). The Timpanogos Tribe, a dominant subgroup of Shoshone that, until extirpated, lived along its shores and were known as the "Reed People" attesting to the bounty of aquatic vegetation (i.e. macrophytes) that thrived along Utah Lake's shoreline and littoral zone wetlands⁶. Historically, the lake was characterized by a more stable substrate than at present due to stabilizing biota including native aquatic macrophytes, benthic algae, and bivalve mollusks (Richards et al. 2023, Richards 2022, Richards and Miller 2019, 2024, Libralato et al. 2006, Williams et al. 2024). Utah Lake's diverse and abundant molluscan assemblage was likely unsurpassed in the western USA (Richards 2017); a true Utah natural heritage that has all but vanished. The synergy between aquatic macrophytes, benthic algae, bivalves, other benthic invertebrates, and a balanced fishery (i.e., its food web) ensured that water clarity in such a shallow lake was able to penetrate to its benthos throughout a large portion of the lake and that nutrients were fully utilized (Richards et al. 2021, 2022, 2023).

Utah Lake's littoral zone began to suffer and rapidly decline soon after settlement by non-indigenous peoples. Reasons for this decline were numerous including water diversions,

⁴ **Ecosystem shift** All ecosystems are exposed to gradual changes in climate, nutrient loading, habitat fragmentation or biotic exploitation. Nature is usually assumed to respond to gradual change in a smooth way. However, studies have shown that smooth change can be interrupted by sudden drastic switches to a contrasting state. Although diverse events can trigger such shifts, studies show that a loss of resilience usually paves the way for a switch to an alternative state. This suggests that strategies for sustainable management of such ecosystems should focus on maintaining resilience (Scheffer et al. 2001). **Hysteresis** "implies that communities and ecosystems might be easily pushed into some configurations from which it may prove much more difficult for them to recover" (Beisner et al. 2003). Hysteresis is "where the observed equilibrium of a system cannot be predicted solely based on environmental variables but also requires knowledge of the system's past history". (Wikipedia accessed November 24, 2019).

⁵ **Entropy** is central to the second law of thermodynamics, which states that the entropy of an isolated system left to spontaneous evolution cannot decrease with time. As a result, isolated systems evolve toward thermodynamic equilibrium, where the entropy is highest. A consequence of the second law of thermodynamics is that certain processes are irreversible." (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Entropy>). Ecosystems can be characterized by the processes of transforming available energy, cycling materials, and replicating information. Ecosystems self-organize into hierarchical networks. An ecosystem is a thermodynamic system, and its dynamics follows the laws of thermodynamics. **Ecoexergy** is used to measure the following aspects of an ecosystem state: 1) the total complexity of ecosystem; 2) structure and functions of ecosystem; and 3) ability of an ecosystem to survive. Structural ecoexergy reflects: 1) efficiency of energy use by organisms; and 2) the ability of ecosystem to regulate interactions between organisms or groups of organisms." (Berrios et al. 2017, Silow et al. 2011).

⁶ Today the Timpanogos People point out that the names Yutahs, Ewuhua or Eutah (Indian words spelled phonetically) also refer to the reeds that grow around Utah Lake that were used to make arrows. "eu" in their language means reed, and "tah" meaning arrow. Bancroft makes the same observation also referenced in his book *The works of Hubert Howe Bancroft; The Native Races 1883 – 1886* (Gottfredson 2022). Technically, the only 'reeds' native to Utah Lake were *Phragmites* sp.

Chapter 1: Introduction

pollution and pollutants⁷, and introduction of bioturbating Common Carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and catfish (Family Ictaluridae), and the loss of native mollusks, among other factors (Janetski 1990, Carter 2005, Richards 2022, Richards and Miller 2017, 2019).

Photosynthetically available light that can reach the substrate is now typically only between 10 to 50 cm depth; any substrate deeper than this receives very little to no light (see our previous mesocosm reports and Chapter 3 in this report). This ensures that almost the entirety of this shallow lake resides outside of the littoral zone especially during low lake levels when surviving emergent aquatic vegetation is exposed outside of the lake wetted areas. Presently, aquatic vegetation coverage is between 1 and 5% of the lake. Unfortunately, aquatic macrophytes, benthic algae, and bivalves are no longer able to provide sediment stabilizing ecosystem services due to strong wave action that easily disturbs sediments and dislodges their benthic habitat making it mostly unstable and uninhabitable (e.g., early successional, low ecoexergy, high entropy).

The open water limnetic (euphotic) zone in Utah Lake also varies from about 10 to 50 cm depending on conditions (but see Chapter 3 this report). This zone is now almost exclusively where primary production occurs in the form of photosynthetic phytoplankton, including potentially harmful cyanophytes and where phytoplanktonic grazers, zooplankton reside. Consequently, most of the secondary production also occurs in the limnetic zone (Richards 2022). Domination by limnetic zone primary and secondary production as opposed to a balance with littoral zone production indicates degradation from past conditions in Utah Lake and is the primary reason the lake is now often classified as eutrophic or hyper-eutrophic (Richards et al. 2021, 2022, 2023).

Almost all lakes have a well-developed profundal zone, the area located below the range of effective light penetration. The amount of area that a lake's profundal zone covers is dependent on many factors including depth, topography, climate, benthic substrate, trophic state, and the health and balance of biota in its food web. Most healthy lakes have a balance between littoral, limnetic, and profundal zones. This is not the case for Utah Lake; it is now dominated by the profundal zone. The lake's profundal zone substrate is comprised of a thick unconsolidated, easily disturbed, nutrient laden sediment that is relatively homogenous throughout most of the lake bottom with very little structural habitat. Its benthic inhabitants are those relegated to survival under very low or no light conditions, often low levels of dissolved oxygen (hypoxia), and unstable fine sediments. The lakes' profundal zone only allows for low ecoexergy- high entropy primary and secondary production derived from heterotrophic decomposition including detrital 'rain' that falls from the limnetic zone primarily in summer months (Richards 2022a, b, c, Richards and Miller 2024).

Justification

There is much concern by citizens and managers as to the future of Utah Lake and what can be done to improve its condition (i.e., health, integrity), including the reduction of algal blooms and restoration of its native biota (Utah Lake Authority <https://utahlake.gov>). However, there has been little to no effort expended to examine or understand the importance of the lake's food web

⁷**Pollutant** is a substance that contaminates the environment, whereas **pollution** is the process or result of pollutants being released

Chapter 1: Introduction

and how top-down, trophic cascades⁸ effect and respond to current conditions or how biomanipulation may help restore its ecosystem health despite decades of research documenting their importance worldwide. Successful Utah Lake restoration cannot proceed without this understanding and holistic based implementation.

Why Mesocosms

Mesocosm (limnocorral)⁹ experiments bridge the gap between highly controlled laboratory experiments that target causality of underlying mechanisms and whole level ecosystem experiments. Even though mesocosm experiments are simplifications of an ecosystem (i.e., limited realism), whole lake experiments (e.g., Utah Lake), although realistic, cannot be easily justified (Stewart et al., 2013).

According to Stewart et al., (2013):

“Because mesocosms can include more biological complexity at larger scales, they are generally regarded as being more amenable for testing community-level and ecosystem-level responses to change in more realistic settings. They can also (ideally) help disentangle direct from indirect effects over intergenerational scales, especially for taxa that cannot be housed in microcosms, parameterized, due to a lack of appropriate empirical and experimental data. Field surveys typically explore correlations between climatic conditions and biological properties but cannot confirm causal relationships and have little or no predictive power. A deeper understanding of the ecological consequences is therefore achieved by combining multiple approaches, with mesocosms playing a central and increasingly important role.”

Very few, if any, aquatic ecologists now conduct mesocosm studies restricted to a few components of an ecosystem, given our accumulated knowledge that lake ecosystems are complex with physical, chemical, and biological components continuously interacting and inseparable, and with the knowledge that properly designed mesocosm studies can provide substantially more information. The contemporary mesocosm experimental paradigm is to measure as many ecological responses as feasible providing scientists and managers invaluable information, which can then be incorporated into an entire ecosystem management framework. Our limnocorral studies substantially add to this knowledge.

Limnocorral Study Goals

The overall goal of our 2024 limnocorral study was to understand factors that influence nutrient cycling, algal blooms, food web dynamics, and ecosystem functioning that contribute to the

⁸ **Trophic cascades** are powerful indirect interactions that can control entire ecosystems, occurring when a trophic level in a food web is suppressed. For example, a **top-down cascade** will occur if predators are effective enough in predation to reduce the abundance, or alter the behavior of their prey, thereby releasing the next lower trophic level from predation (or herbivory if the intermediate trophic level is a herbivore)(Wikipedia accessed February 18, 2025).

⁹ A **mesocosm** is any outdoor experimental system that examines the natural environment under controlled conditions. Macaulay et al. (2025) defined mesocosms as “experimental systems that replicate a representative natural community or ecosystem under controlled but realistic environmental conditions. This definition encompasses three key aspects of mesocosms that provide advantages for ecological research: replication, control and realism (Fraser and Keddy 1997, Stewart et al. 2013)” A **limnocorral** is a specific type of mesocosm designed, as the name implies, to corral desired conditions within an aquatic setting.

Chapter 1: Introduction

impairment of the ecological health of Utah Lake, particularly the effects of wind driven wave turbulence. Results from our research will help direct managers on how best to initiate restoration¹⁰, essential for improving its health, focusing on an integrated and adaptive management strategy (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024, ongoing DWQ Utah Lake Science Panel studies, Richards and Miller 2024, Utah Lake Authority, others). We chose achieving realism over optimal control for these studies because we were mostly concerned with simulating the Utah Lake ecosystem and guiding restoration management (Macaulay et al. 2025).

The goal of the ecological component of the TSSD Utah Lake limnocorral study 2024 was to examine the direct and indirect effects of wave action, bioturbator exclusion, and nutrient addition on:

- Chemistry
- Light attenuation,
- Phytoplankton assemblages,
- Benthic algae (periphyton) assemblages,
- Zooplankton assemblages and,
- Benthic invertebrate assemblages,
- and their interactions during the 2024 field season¹¹.

We postulated that the application of these treatments would have measurable direct and indirect effects on chemistry and the four assemblages. In addition, we expected that treatment effects would alter nutrient cycling and water quality in complicated interactions within the food web (please review Williams et al. 2023, Richards et al. 2023, 2019, Richards and Miller 2019a, and Richards and Miller 2017 for a holistic overview of Utah Lake’s unique food web and ecology).

We have discussed in detail in our previous mesocosm reports (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024) the condition of Utah Lake’s ecosystem function, including the effects of carp, loss of native species, particularly mollusks and aquatic vegetation, that resulted in more frequent uncontrolled wind driven wave turbulence, consequently preventing ecosystem recovery without deliberate and focused intervention. Our 2024 limnocorral studies presented in this progress report provide further documentation on the direct and indirect effects of wind driven wave action and nutrient addition on light attenuation, chemistry, phytoplankton, benthic algae, zooplankton, and benthic invertebrate assemblages during summer season 2024.

Limnocorral Design 2024

Figure 1 shows the layout of corrals. Limnocorrals were modified in 2024 from previous years. See our past progress reports on previous designs (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, and 2024). For detailed information on corral design and installation methods contact Timpanogos Special Service District, Attn: Richard Mickelsen, District Manager.

¹⁰ **Ecological restoration**, “placing the ecosystem on a trajectory of recovery but not necessarily recovery to its former state so that it can persist, and its species can adapt and evolve” (Society Ecological Restoration).

¹¹ Utah Lake’s environmental factors and biotic populations can vary substantially from year to year. Hence, it was imperative to conduct limnocorral studies over several years. Fortunately for us, we were able to conduct our studies during low water years (2021, 2022) and high-water years (2023, 2024). A comprehensive report comparing our results for all four years is needed.

Phosphorus Additions

Phosphorus additions occurred on July 19 in Corrals 1, 5 and 6 and on Sept 11 in Corrals 2, 3, and 9 (Figure 1). See Goel et al. (2025 in prep) for detailed description of phosphorus treatments and results.

Figure 1. Schematic of mesocosm (limnocorral) experimental design. Hollow large circles are C = corral, solid blue small ovals are LC = lake control site. Phosphorus additions occurred on July 19, 2024, in corrals C1, C5, and C6, and on September 11, 2024, in corrals C2, C3 and C9. Untreated controls were corrals C4, C7, and C8.

Several researchers at Timpanogos Special Service District (TSSD) were involved in collection and compiling of data including, Brian Selck, Megan Pope, and River York. They collected chemistry and light attenuation data regularly from June through October 2024. Data used in these analyses were from: July 5, July 19, July 30, August 5, August 26, September 6, September 9, September 23, September 30, and October 8.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

TSSD who dedicated much blood, sweat, and tears to make this research possible. The 2024 study would not be possible without all these capable and enthusiastic team members.

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Chapter 2: Chemistry

Introduction

Chemistry¹² is the foundation for Utah Lake's food web and ecosystem function. The chemical variables measured for this study were assumed to interact directly and/or indirectly within the lake's ecosystem. They were assumed to affect and be affected by these interactions within the food web. Several of the variables were considered nutrients including phosphorus and nitrogen compounds, as well as metals that are either considered micronutrients in small doses or toxins in large quantities. We stress that chemical elements and compounds are only considered nutrients in the context of biology; without biology, nutrients are simply chemicals. Although nutrients are essential for all life; excess or underutilized nutrients can have detrimental effects to the biota within an ecosystem and subsequently negatively affect its functions.

Three phosphorus compounds were measured in the 2024 study, total phosphorus (TP)¹³, dissolved phosphorus (dP), and ortho phosphorus (OrthoP) and three nitrogen compounds were measured, NO₂, NO₃, and NH₃. These nutrients were considered important for algal growth and subsequent food web interactions. Five metals were measured Al, Ca, Fe, Mg, and K and are often important in algal metabolism, particularly Fe and Mg for cyanobacteria metabolic function. Al was also measured in this study and occurs in very high concentrations in the lake (see past progress reports). Al compounds were naively suggested for use as an algicide treatment for controlling Utah Lake HABs and were subsequently used as one of our corral treatments in 2021 and 2022. We have since abandoned that avenue of research; no Al treatments were made in 2024, and we don't consider Al a viable treatment for the lake.

Chemical oxygen demand (COD) measured the total amount of oxygen required to oxidize both organic and inorganic compounds in water. Oxygen reduction potential (ORP) measured electron activity in water that relates to the relative amount of oxidant or reductant. Higher ORP levels can be correlated with improved water quality. ORP data can become more valuable if used as an indicator over time and/or with other common parameters (e.g., pH, dissolved oxygen, turbidity, conductivity) to help develop a complete picture of the water quality in the lake. Conductivity (electrical conductivity (EC)) measured the lake's ability to carry an electrical current. Water can conduct electricity because of the ion concentration within the water, which comes from dissolved solids and inorganic materials like carbonate compounds, chlorides, and sulfides like sodium (salt). The conductivity range also depends on the ion's potential to bind with water. Our past research has shown that Utah Lake conductivity typically ranged from 1200 to 1700 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ indicative of slightly saline or brackish water conditions.

¹² Although temperature is not chemistry, it can affect chemistry and is included in this category for this report. As a reminder, temperature was only measured during the study, primarily summer months not other seasons. Temperature effects on phytoplankton are in Chapter 4.

¹³ Total Phosphorus = Particulate Phosphorus + Dissolved Phosphorus = Mineral Phosphorus + Organic Phosphorus

Suspended solids including total suspended solids (TSS), total dissolved solids (TDS), and volatile suspended solids (VSS) were also measured. TSS and TDS measure the amount of particulate matter floating in water. This included particles from algae, other organic matter, silt and clay, and other inorganic substances (such as minerals, salts and metals). VSS measured the undissolved organic matter in the water column.

Note: Our previous progress reports, primarily authored by Williams et al. (2022, 2023, 2024), discuss the importance and chemistry findings in Utah Lake in more detail.

Methods

The chemical variables measured in our mesocosm study inside and outside of corrals in the water column are listed in Table 1. Chlorophyll and phycocyanin are indirect surrogate measures of algal and cyanobacteria biovolume. These variables were used in this chapter and Chapter 3 but not subsequent chapters because phytoplankton and periphyton taxa were later identified and their individual biovolumes per sample estimated. Phytoplankton and periphyton taxa are the direct ultimate measure of the food web and ecosystem function not chlorophyll or phycocyanin, and several phytoplankton taxa are the focus of Utah Lake managers. However, taxa and biovolume measurements were not always collected on the same dates as variables listed in Table 1, hence the use of those variables in this chapter and Chapter 3.

Table 1. Chemical variables measured in this study 2024.

Temperature °C	Chlorophyll (ug L ⁻¹)	Conductivity
DO (mg L ⁻¹)	Phycocyanin (ug L ⁻¹)	Al (mg L ⁻¹)
pH	TP (mg L ⁻¹)	Ca (mg L ⁻¹)
TSS (mg L ⁻¹) (Total suspended solids)	Dissolved P (mg L ⁻¹) (dP)	Fe (mg L ⁻¹)
TDS (mg L ⁻¹) (Total Dissolved Solids)	Ortho P (mg L ⁻¹) (OrthoP)	Mg (mg L ⁻¹)
VSS (%) (Volatile Suspended Solids)	NO ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)	K (mg L ⁻¹)
COD (mg L ⁻¹)(chemical oxygen demand)	NO ₃ (mg L ⁻¹)	
ORP (uS/cm) (oxygen reduction potential)	NH ₃ (mg L ⁻¹)	

Statistical Analyses

Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMS) ordination was evaluated to compare chemistry “assemblage”¹⁴ dis(similarity) relationships statistically and visually between corrals and dates. Ordination techniques are often more informative than hypothesis-testing approaches for exploring relationships between multivariate ecological assemblages or communities (McCune and Grace 2002). In general, ordination is the ordering of objects along axes according to their (dis)similarities; the main objective of ordination is to reduce many-dimensional relationships into a small number of more easily interpretable dimensions (i.e., axes on a plot). The strongest correlation structure in the data is extracted and is then used to position objects in ordination space. Objects that are close in the ordination space are more similar than objects distant in ordination space (McCune and Mefford 2018).

¹⁴ We use the term chemistry assemblage in this chapter in the same context as phytoplankton, zooplankton, or benthic invertebrate assemblages in subsequent chapters.

NMS was evaluated in these analyses because it has been shown to be robust and highly informative for understanding ecological relationships. NMS ordination is often more broadly applicable for ecological studies than other ordination techniques because it does not require relationships among variables to be linear (McCune and Mefford 2018, Peck 2010). NMS ordination permits the visualization of the multidimensional relationships of chemistry assemblages into a more easily visualized, lower dimensional space. Dimensional reduction obviously creates some distortion in relationships between samples. The level of reduction in distortion is measured as ‘stress’, where lower stress values equal less distortion. NMS plots with stress values of 15% (0.15) or less are typically considered to be a good representation of the data and stress values lower than 10% (0.10) are considered excellent representations (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010).

Chemistry data were relativized by maximum values of each variable because chemistry variables were measured on different scales (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010). Several distance measures were used and evaluated including Sorensen (Bray-Curtis), Relative Sorensen, Jaccard, Euclidean, Relative Euclidean, and Morisita-Horn. The Euclidean distance matrix was found to be the best fit to our data and used for the final NMS model. NMS analysis was run for 250 iterations using the real data and 250 iterations in randomized Monte Carlo simulations. Best-fit models were selected based on stable final stress < 0.15 and 3-dimensional solutions or less. NMS ordinations were rotated using varimax rotation to maximize variation along the axes and extracted as univariate scores. Consequently, the final ordinations can be rotated either vertically or horizontally without effecting the results. Centroid labels and convex hulls of months were added to the ordinations to aid in the interpret the relationships. Post hoc proportion of variance represented by each axis was calculated based on the R^2 value between distance in the ordination space and distance in the original space.

Multiple Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP), a non-parametric multivariate method was used to formally test the hypothesis of no differences in chemistry assemblages between sampling dates. MRPP has the advantage of not requiring distributional assumptions such as multivariate normality and homogeneity of variance and thus is often preferred over perMANOVA for analyzing multivariate ecological data (McCune and Grace 2002). The same distance measure was used for each MRPP analyses as was for corresponding NMS models. The chance-corrected within-group test statistic, A (and associated p-value) was used to evaluate the hypothesis of no difference in groupings (McCune and Grace 2002). Post hoc multiple comparisons were also made when appropriate.

We used Indicator Species Analysis (ISA) in PC-ORD to statistically determine chemistry variables that were strong indicators of sampling events or inside vs. outside of corrals, that is they had their greatest values or occurred most frequently on those dates or locations. We used Dufrene and Legendre's (1997) method of calculating species indicator values that provided a simple, intuitive solution. The method combined information on chemistry variables for each sample event and the faithfulness of occurrence of a variable in a particular sample event. ISA produced indicator values for each variable in each group. These were then tested for statistical significance using the randomization technique in PC-ORD (see McCune and Grace 2002 for more detailed information on ISA method).

All multivariate and several additional analyses including rank abundance and descriptive summary statistics were made using PC-ORD for Windows Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018) using Parallels Desktop 19.2.1 for Mac virtual platform.

Regression analyses were selected using the most appropriate model including linear, Poisson, fractional, and negative binomial. Candidate predictors (factors) were screened using Lasso regression. Lasso regression is a machine learning method that allows for selection of subsets of best fit models from many candidate factors. The final best fit regression models were then reevaluated from the lasso regression selected models and chosen based on lowest log likelihood, AIC, and BIC values. ANOVAs and MANOVAs were also conducted where appropriate. Descriptive statistics were also calculated for select data. Nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis' equality of populations rank test were applied when data were not near normally distributed after transformation. Box and whisker plots were developed for non-normally distributed data. Box plots used median, 25th, 75th, lower and upper adjacent values and outside values. Statistical analyses and graphics were made using Stata 16.1 for Mac (Intel 64-bit) (StataCorp 2021). Graphical representations of statistical models were made using either Stata or PC-ORD. Details of additional statistical methods not listed here are described in individual Results sections.

Results

Many of the chemistry variables were correlated. Correlations between chemistry variables are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Correlation heat map of chemistry variables. ns (not significant) is $p > 0.05$. r is correlation coefficients.

Assemblages

Our best fit nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMS) model showed that chemistry assemblages differed between sampling dates. NMS final stress = 8.65, final instability < 0.001, iterations = 66 and was considered an excellent fit (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010). NMS axis 1 $R^2 = 0.681$, axis 2 $R^2 = 0.207$, axis 3 $R^2 = 0.075$, cumulative $R^2 = 0.963$.

The NMS ordination Axis1 and Axis 2 shown in Figure 3 shows that the chemistry assemblages generally differed between early season June through July (lower right quadrant) and mid-late season September 16 through September 30 (upper left quadrant). The October 7 assemblage began to cycle back to earlier conditions, and assemblages at other sampling dates tended toward average conditions, except August 5 assemblage, which was quite a bit different than other assemblage dates (Figure 3).

Figure 3. NMS Axis 1 and Axis 2 chemistry assemblage dis(similarities).

Figure 4. NMS Axis 1 and Axis 3 chemistry assemblage dis(similarities).

NMS Axis 1 that explained about 68% of the chemistry assemblage dissimilarity mostly separated nitrogen and phosphorus related variables including phycocyanin, Chl A, and TSS in the mid-late September assemblages (left side of Axis 1) from temperature, TDS, VSS, Cond, and DO in the earlier season assemblages (right side of Axis 1) (Figure 3, Table 2). Axis 2 explained about 21% of chemistry assemblage dissimilarity and separated nitrogen and temperature measures (bottom of Axis 2 origin) from factors including Do, Cond, VSS, Phyco, ChlA, and pH(upper portion of Axis 2 origin) (Figure 3, Table 2). Axis 1 vs. Axis 3 explained about 76% variability with results comparable to Axis 1 vs. Axis 2 (Figure 4, Table 2). Axis 2 vs. Axis 3 only provided 28% cumulative explanation, subsequently that ordination map is not presented.

Table 2. NMS Axis 1 and Axis 2 correlations with chemistry variables.

Axis 1		Axis 2		Axis 3	
NO ₂	-0.82	NO ₂	-0.42	NH ₃	-0.48
TSS	-0.80	Temp	-0.38	TSS	-0.44
OrthoP	-0.78	NO ₃	-0.32	Cond	-0.28
NO ₃	-0.78	NH ₃	-0.27	TDS	-0.24
Phyco	-0.73	ORP	-0.05	OrthoP	-0.22
TP	-0.62	TSS	0.01	ChlA	-0.05
ChlA	-0.51	OrthoP	0.03	Phyco	-0.05
NH ₃	-0.51	DP	0.29	DP	-0.02
DP	-0.42	TP	0.35	pH	0.02
pH	-0.29	TDS	0.37	TP	0.09
ORP	-0.28	DO	0.39	Temp	0.12
DO	-0.13	Cond	0.44	ORP	0.24
Cond	-0.06	VSS	0.49	NO ₂	0.27
TDS	0.09	Phyco	0.56	DO	0.38
VSS	0.13	ChlA	0.67	NO ₃	0.39
Temp	0.38	pH	0.69	VSS	0.69

Multiple response permutation procedure (MRRP) provided strong evidence that all chemistry assemblages differed from each other on every sampling date and assemblages differed between inside and outside of corrals.

Table 3. Multiple response permutatin procedure MRPP for chemistry assemblage dis(similarities) by sample date and inside vs. outside of corrals. All chemistry assemblages strongly differed between and among each sampling date (post hoc pairwise comparisons $p < 0.001$)

	T	A	p
Sample date	-68.32	0.45	< 0.0001
In vs Out	-4.66	0.008	0.003

Chemistry Assemblage Indicators

Chemistry assemblage indicators¹⁵ for sampling date are in Table 4. Temperature was an indicator of July 15 sampling event because water temperature was highest on that date. September 16 had the most indicators including ORP, TSS, DP, OrthoP, NO₂, and NO₃.

¹⁵ An indicator is a variable, in this case chemistry variable, that has its highest values

Chemistry indicators for September 23 sample event showed the effects of the largest algal bloom during the study (see Chapter 4 Phytoplankton) and included pH, DO, ChlA, and Phyco.

Five chemistry variables were indicators of inside corrals including, ChlA, VSS, OrthoP, TP, and DP (Table 4). DO was an indicator for lake water outside of corrals.

Table 4. Chemistry assemblage indicators by sampling date and in vs. outside of corrals.

Sample date

			IV from randomized groups		
Variable	Sample Date	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	Mean	S. Dev	p
Temp	15-Jul	7	6.5	0.12	< 0.001
VSS	5-Aug	11.9	7.7	0.43	< 0.001
NH ₃	12-Aug	11.3	7.7	0.42	< 0.001
Cond	12-Aug	6.4	6.3	0.09	< 0.001
TDS	26-Aug	6.6	6.4	0.1	< 0.001
ORP	16-Sep	7.9	6.7	0.15	< 0.001
TSS	16-Sep	15.4	8.3	0.59	< 0.001
DP	16-Sep	12	8.3	0.68	< 0.001
Ortho P	16-Sep	12.4	8	0.61	< 0.001
NO ₂	16-Sep	15.4	8.3	0.94	< 0.001
NO ₃	16-Sep	19.4	9.4	1.05	< 0.001
pH	23-Sep	6.5	6.3	0.09	< 0.001
DO	23-Sep	8.2	6.8	0.18	< 0.001
ChlA	23-Sep	18.1	9.6	1.04	< 0.001
Phyco	23-Sep	17	8.8	0.76	< 0.001
TP	30-Sep	28.4	11.1	1.51	< 0.001

In vs. out

			IV from randomized groups		
Variable	In vs. Out	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	Mean	S. Dev	p
Chl A	In	59.1	52.8	2.25	0.01
VSS	In	53.7	50.9	1.23	0.01
Ortho P	In	53	48.1	1.79	0.01
TP	In	59.5	53.8	2.94	0.04
DP	In	52.6	49.9	1.63	0.06
DO	Out	52.2	50.5	0.81	< 0.01

Chemical variability and corral effects

There was strong evidence that many water column chemical variables increased throughout the study period including, pH, DO, conductivity, TSS, VSS, TP, dissolved P, ortho P, NH₃, COD, Al, K, and Mg; water temperature and Ca decreased (Figure 5, Appendix 1). Variables also differed between inside and outside of corrals regardless of phosphorus treatments within corrals (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Variability of chemistry factors inside vs outside of corrals from June 12 to October 7, 2024.

Phycocyanin was often higher inside corrals suggesting cyanobacteria biovolume was also greater inside corrals than in the lake. This was verified in Chapter 3: Phytoplankton.

Treatment Effects

There were two treatment effects examined in this section, wave reduction (all nine corrals) and phosphorus addition on July 19 (P1) and September 11 (P2). Data in this section of analyses were analyzed starting from July 22 just prior to first phosphorus treatment using mixed effects, multilevel regression models with date as a random variable.

We found evidence ($p \approx < 0.05$) that temperature was lower in the phosphorus treated corrals than the lake but not the control corrals and the lake. pH was greater in corrals for all treatments than the lake. DO and conductivity were less in all three corral treatments than the lake. VSS was greater in the second phosphorus treatment (P2) and control corral than the lake but not the first phosphorus treatment (P1). TDS was less in the control corrals than the lake, but the two phosphorus treated corrals were not. TP and dissolved P were greater in all three treatments than the lake. Ortho P was greater in the two phosphorus treatments than the lake, but control corral Ortho P was not. NO_3 was greater in the two phosphorus treatments than the lake and possibly control corral ($p = 0.08$). NH_3 was less in P2 and control corrals than the lake but P1 wasn't. COD was greater in P2 than the lake but P1 and control corrals were not. Ca was greater in the three treatment corrals than the lake (Figure 6 and Appendix 2).

Figure 6. Chemistry variables as a function of date (starting July 22, 2025) and treatment.

Discussion

Results from the two corral treatment effects, wave break/bioturbator reduction and phosphorus additions, demonstrate that there were measurable differences in chemistry inside corrals vs. in the lake but there was also enough water movement through the corrals to somewhat obfuscate results. In addition, corral treatments likely caused direct and indirect interactions of the chemical variables with biota (see Chapter 4: Phytoplankton and Chapter 5: Zooplankton). The chemistry assemblage changed rapidly between sample events which was quite surprising and indicated that that lake ecosystem was very dynamic, at least during our study in the summer season 2024. Results from this section need to be taken in context with other components of Utah Lake's ecosystem including, phytoplankton, periphyton, zooplankton, and benthic invertebrates that are presented in following chapters and with fish assemblages that were not monitored in this study. However, fish were not observed in the corrals and these results reflect their absence.

Results from this chapter and the other chapters in this progress report only reflect what we observed in 2024. Subsequent analyses of all years of our mesocosm studies combined will likely provide a much better understanding of the effects of the corrals and treatments on chemistry assemblages, as well as other changes to the ecosystem within our study area.

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Chapter 3: Light Attenuation

Ecosystem Function and Restoration Implications

Chapter figure: Linear regression (with 95% CIs) of attenuation of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) as a function of depth inside and outside of mesocosm corral in Utah Lake 2024. Dashed vertical line is theoretical photosynthetic light limit.

Summary

Understanding light attenuation in Utah Lake, including factors that influence attenuation, such as the role of wave action on sediment disturbance and concomitant resuspension of calcium carbonate precipitates on ecosystem function is critical for management and restoration. 2024 mesocosm (limnocorral) data were analyzed to better understand light attenuation in the lake.

Light attenuation, the rate at which light diminishes as depth increases, as measured by PAR (photosynthetically active radiation), varied throughout the duration of the study, among corral, and within the lake. Differences between PAR inside corral and in the lake were primarily due to reduction in wave action disturbance, as part of our experimental design. Slopes of regression lines of *ln* mean PAR vs depth varied by date and were steeper inside corral, except on August 26 during an algal bloom. PAR was higher at shallower depths and less at deeper depths in the lake than inside corral. The theoretical photosynthesis light limit ($0.01 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) also varied and was predicted to occur at lower depths inside corral on most dates with strong evidence that on average it was deeper inside corral. This was likely due to reduction in calcium carbonate, CaCO_3 crystal precipitate inside corral that can cause light backscatter. Other

covariates likely affected light attenuation including phytoplankton densities (as measured by Chl *A*), conductivity, and ORP (oxygen reduction potential).

Wave action disturbance on easily resuspended sediments, including CaCO₃ precipitates, in Utah Lake alters light attenuation and is a major factor affecting ecosystem function, hindering restoration efforts. Ecological and restoration implications of improved light attenuation via reduced disturbance are immense for Utah Lake including improved food web interactions and trophic transfer of energy. Restoration measures necessary to reduce attenuation include, establishment of benthic algae, macrophytes, and native mollusks, and improved water level management or mechanical stabilization.

More intensive analyses of 2021 to 2024 mesocosm data including adding covariates such as wind and weather conditions are highly recommended to more completely understand the effects of light attenuation on ecosystem function and to help guide restoration of Utah Lake.

Introduction

The role of light penetration is critical to aquatic ecosystem functioning. Light regulates phytoplankton, benthic algae, and submerged aquatic macrophyte primary production, and allows visual predators to find prey (Karlsson et al. 2009; Kemp et al. 2005; Weiskerger et al 2018). Light can also reduce or prevent hypoxia via primary production photosynthesis and can influence cyanobacteria blooms (Medrano et al. 2013; Weiskerger et al. 2018).

Light attenuation, the rate at which light diminishes as depth increases in a water body, can be influenced by various factors, including suspended solids, phytoplankton density, dissolved organic carbon, and, in some systems, the amount of calcium carbonate crystal precipitate. For instance, eutrophic lakes exhibit much greater attenuation compared to less productive oligotrophic and mesotrophic lakes. Shallow eutrophic lakes, such as Utah Lake, with significant amounts of easily resuspended unconsolidated calcium carbonate precipitates within the water column, can experience even greater light attenuation, impacting entire ecosystem function. Light is not able to reach the sediments in a large portion of Utah Lake because the lake has undergone major detrimental ecosystem shifts that prevent benthic algae and macrophytes from competing with water column phytoplankton and stabilizing easily resuspended sediments.

Understanding light attenuation in Utah Lake, including factors that influence attenuation, such as the role of wave action on sediment disturbance and concomitant resuspension of calcium carbonate precipitates on ecosystem function, is critical for management and restoration. This technical report provides groundwork evidence for understanding light attenuation and its role in Utah Lake's ecosystem based on mesocosm experiments conducted in 2024.

Methods

Light attenuation

Light attenuation data using a PAR (photosynthetically active radiation) meter (LiCOR LI-1500 light sensor logger with dual LI-192 Underwater Quantum Sensors) were collected at 2, 24, 67, 87, 107, 127, and 147 cm depths within each corral and at the five lake control site locations during the sample dates.

Statistical methods

Light attenuation values for each depth, each sample site (corrals and lake controls), and each sample date were graphed for visual interpretation. Linear regression of natural log (\ln) transformed PAR ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) as a function of depth (cm) on mean PAR inside corrals and for lake controls were then compared for each sample date. This regression analysis was based on the widely used simple Beer-Lambert model (Ingle and Crouch 1988) and was considered appropriate for shallow lakes (i.e., Utah Lake) (Welskerger et al. 2018)¹⁶. These and other chemical variables were subsequently examined as additional factors that influenced light attenuation.

The theoretical minimum light requirement of photosynthesis of $0.01 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Hoppe et al. 2024, Hancke et al. 2018; Randelhoff et al. 2020; Raven et al. 2000) was used as a benchmark to better understand light limitation in the lake. Predicted mean depths (95% CIs) where the theoretical photosynthesis light limitation occurred (\ln of $0.01 = -4.60 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) were made based on simple regression models for each date inside and outside of corrals and then graphed for comparisons. A table of the mean light attenuation comparison between inside and outside corrals at increasing depth was made that included comparisons an outside corral vs inside corral ratio and an outside minus inside corral comparison. Box plots of light attenuation between inside and outside corrals for each depth and date were also made.

Chemistry data analyzed to determine relationships with light attenuation included: Chlorophyll ($\mu\text{g/L}$), Phycocyanin ($\mu\text{g/L}$), ORP ($\mu\text{S/cm}$), Conductivity, TSS (mg/L), VSS (%), TDS (mg/L), and COD (mg/L). Chemistry data were either log, square root transformed or not transformed to more normalize the data for regressions and ANOVAs based on ladder of power statistics. All analyses were conducted using Stata/IC 16.1 for Mac statistical package.

Results

Light attenuation/availability varied among the nine corrals and lake control sites and during each sampling date (Figure 7). In general, there was more light availability in the lake than inside corrals at shallower depths, however, light penetration depth was greater inside corrals (Figure 7).

Slopes of regression lines of \ln mean PAR vs depth varied by date and were steeper inside corrals, except on August 26 during an algal bloom (Figure 8). Also, PAR was higher at shallower depths and lower at deeper depths in the lake than inside corrals (Figure 8). Regression model results are in appendices.

¹⁶ Other more complicated and perhaps informative attenuation models that include algal Chl *A*, DOC, and solids, etc. should be considered for future research (see Appendix 4).

Figure 7. PAR ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) readings for each sample location (corrals are C1-C9, lake locations are LC1-LC5) at each depth recording and each sample date.

Figure 8. Linear regression fit lines of light attenuation PAR ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) as a function of depth inside and outside of corals at each sample date. Dashed black x-axis reference line is $\ln(0.01 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1})$ theoretical photosynthesis light limit.

Table 5. Predicted mean (95% CIs) depth (cm) at theoretical photosynthesis light limit based on regression models illustrated in Figure 8 and in appendices.

Date	Mean Depth (cm) (95% CIs)	
	In	Out
5-Jul	114(110, 118)	100 (95, 104)
19-Jul	148 (140, 150)	141 (133, 150)
30-Jul	104 (100, 120)	100 (96, 104)
5-Aug	155 (138, 180)	165 (141, 190)
26-Aug	96 (89, 105)	110 (102, 118)
6-Sep	118 (106, 133)	113 (90, 148)
9-Sep	118 (106, 133)	134 (105, 168)
23-Sep	80 (69, 92)	70 (64, 75)
30-Sep	76 (74, 78)	79 (75, 83)
8-Oct	102 (96, 110)	108 (96, 124)
All dates	101 (99, 104)	81 (77, 85)

Reduced disturbance inside corrals compared to disturbance conditions in the lake allowed light to penetrate deeper in July and early August. This was prior to algal bloom onset in summer months. However, variability at sample locations and regression fit predictions due to small sample size (N = 7 for each date) prevented statistical evidence based on CIs to support this finding. Wave reduction also allowed slightly better light penetration on September 6, September 30, and October 8 when phytoplankton densities were higher in the system but not on September 9 when phytoplankton densities were greater inside corrals than in the lake.

Even though PAR varied inside and outside of corrals at each date, overall PAR at the theoretical photosynthetic limit was significantly greater inside corrals than in the lake (Table 5, Figure 9). Reduced wave disturbance can have beneficial ecosystem function effects that will be described in the discussion section (see Discussion Ecological and Restoration Implications).

Figure 9. Linear regression fit line of light attenuation PAR ($\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) as a function of depth inside and outside of corrals. Dashed black x-axis reference line is $\ln(0.01 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1})$ the theoretical photosynthesis light limit. Numbers are predicted mean and 95% CIs at light limit from linear regression in appendix.

On September 9, light limitation was greater inside corrals than in the lake (Figure 10). This was possibly due to significantly greater phytoplankton densities, as measured as Chl A ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), inside corrals (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Chl A ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) inside and outside of corrals on September 9, 2024. There was strong evidence that Chl A ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) was greater inside than outside based on Kruskal-Wallis nonparametric test.

CaCO₃ Backscatter

Table 6 presents a mean light attenuation ($\mu\text{mols photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) comparison between inside and outside corrals at increasing depth, a ratio of outside to inside light availability, and the difference between outside and inside corrals light availability for each sample event. Figure 11 presents these findings that shows the variability within corrals and in the lake.

There were consistently more light photons in the upper layer of water column in the lake than inside corrals (Figure 8, Table 6, Figure 11). Alternatively, often fewer light photons reached deeper layers outside of corrals than inside (Figure 8, Table 6, Figure 11). The phenomenon assumed to be responsible for this is CaCO₃ crystal backscatter¹⁷. It appears that CaCO₃ precipitate in the form of microcrystals contributed to more backscatter outside of corrals primarily due to wave action sediment resuspension starting in August. This will be discussed in more detail in other chapters in our mesocosm report.

Table 6. Mean light attenuation ($\mu\text{mols photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$) comparison between inside and outside corrals at increasing depth. Out/In = ratio of outside to inside light availability. Out - In = difference between outside and inside corrals light availability.

5-Jul	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	74.69	163.80	2.19	89.11
	47	11.67	10.62	0.91	-1.05
	67	5.17	4.30	0.83	-0.87
	87	2.46	1.62	0.66	-0.84
	107	1.49	0.76	0.51	-0.73
	127	0.62	0.26	0.43	-0.35
	147	0.29	0.00	0.00	-0.29
19-Jul	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	116.50	166.84	1.43	50.34
	47	28.37	38.28	1.35	9.91
	67	17.11	20.40	1.19	3.29
	87	9.18	10.04	1.09	0.86
	107	4.57	4.11	0.90	-0.45
	127	1.96	1.72	0.88	-0.24
	147	0.82	0.58	0.70	-0.24
30-Jul	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	55.61	73.95	1.33	18.33
	47	8.66	12.09	1.40	3.43
	67	4.92	4.63	0.94	-0.29
	87	2.37	1.94	0.82	-0.43
	107	0.98	0.70	0.72	-0.28
	127	0.49	0.34	0.69	-0.15

¹⁷ Light backscatter is a well-known phenomenon to underwater photographers and videographers.

	147	0.13	0.08	0.62	-0.05
5-Aug	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	76.16	124.23	1.63	48.06
	47	25.76	43.71	1.70	17.95
	67	14.39	27.40	1.90	13.01
	87	8.84	15.76	1.78	6.92
	107	5.66	7.92	1.40	2.26
	127	3.15	4.26	1.35	1.11
	147	0.70	0.79	1.13	0.09
26-Aug	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	107.01	168.13	1.57	61.12
	47	10.16	23.28	2.29	13.12
	67	4.15	9.23	2.22	5.08
	87	1.97	3.80	1.93	1.84
	107	0.80	1.44	1.80	0.64
	127	0.32	0.54	1.69	0.22
	147	0.04	0.08	2.02	0.04
6-Sep	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	68.58	87.36	1.27	18.78
	47	14.90	20.05	1.35	5.15
	67	7.99	10.86	1.36	2.87
	87	4.87	6.15	1.26	1.27
	107	2.11	3.05	1.45	0.94
	127	0.86	1.29	1.49	0.43
	147	0.16	0.03	0.20	-0.12
9-Sep	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	83.32	136.70	1.64	53.38
	47	21.15	47.65	2.25	26.50
	67	10.90	30.20	2.77	19.30
	87	6.46	18.39	2.84	11.92
	107	3.19	8.87	2.78	5.68
	127	1.18	2.44	2.06	1.26
	147	0.08	0.09	1.14	0.01
23-Sep	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	34.75	38.80	1.12	4.05
	47	3.31	4.34	1.31	1.04

	67	1.40	1.34	0.95	-0.07
	87	0.64	0.38	0.60	-0.26
	107	0.32	0.07	0.23	-0.24
	127	0.09	0.04	0.41	-0.05
	147	0.14	0.02	0.13	-0.12
30-Sep	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	44.15	70.86	1.60	26.71
	47	4.14	7.08	1.71	2.93
	67	1.36	2.13	1.56	0.76
	87	0.66	0.77	1.17	0.11
	107	0.20	0.20	0.96	-0.01
	127	0.06	0.04	0.65	-0.02
	147	0.02	0.02	0.92	0.00
8-Oct	Depth (cm)	In mean	Out mean	Out/In	Out-In
	2	63.31	102.97	1.63	39.66
	47	10.47	22.09	2.11	11.62
	67	5.05	9.96	1.97	4.90
	87	2.43	4.58	1.88	2.15
	107	0.97	1.76	1.82	0.80
	127	0.19	0.38	1.96	0.19
	147	0.17	0.06	0.35	-0.11

Figure 11. Box plots of light attenuation, PAR ($\mu\text{mols photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) at measured depths, inside and outside of corrals, and for each sample date.

Other covariates affecting light attenuation

Phytoplankton densities can also affect light attenuation (see Discussion). Chl *A* concentrations, often used as a surrogate for phytoplankton, were used in this analysis. On eleven of sixteen (69%) sample events, Chl *A* concentrations were greater inside corrals than outside (Figure 12). Mixed effects regression analysis provided strong evidence to support this observation (Table 7). This was possibly due to less inorganic suspended solids inside corrals such as CaCO₃ crystal precipitates resulting in reduced backscatter. However, more detailed analyses are being conducted on ecological factors that may better explain higher Chl *A* concentrations inside corrals (see also Richards et al., 2021, 2022, 2023 for past explanations).

Figure 12. Chlorophyll *A* concentrations ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) inside and outside of corrals from June 25 to Oct 7, 2024.

Table 7. Mixed-effects ML regression of chlorophyll *A* ($\log\text{ChlA}$) as a function of inside vs. outside corrals and sample date modeled as a random factor.

logChlA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	-.473	.094	-5.01	0	-.658	-.288	***
Constant	3.366	.209	16.09	0	2.956	3.776	***
Mean dependent var		3.212	SD dependent var			1.070	
Number of obs		220	Chi-square			25.095	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			499.596	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Conductivity, TSS (total suspended solids), and ORP (oxygen reduction potential)¹⁸ can also affect light attenuation and can covary. There was good evidence that conductivity (Figure 13) and ORP were greater outside of corrals than inside. Mixed effects regression analysis provided strong evidence to support this observation (Table 8) but there was no evidence that TSS differed between corrals and lake. Again, this is suggestive of CaCO₃ precipitate effects on light attenuation.

Figure 13. ANOVA results of conductivity inside and outside of corrals (mean and 95% CIs).

Table 8. Best fit Mixed-effects ML regression of conductivity vs. inside and outside corrals with sample date modeled as a random variable.

conductivity	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	7.411	2.272	3.26	.001	2.958	11.865	***
Constant	1645.931	13.158	125.09	0	1620.141	1671.72	***
Mean dependent var		1649.514	SD dependent var			54.977	
Number of obs		220	Chi-square			10.638	
Prob > chi2		0.001	Akaike crit. (AIC)			1930.307	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

COD was greater inside than outside corrals (Table 9).

Table 9. Mixed-effects ML regression of COD vs. inside and outside corrals with sample date modeled as a random variable.

codmgl	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	-3.921	1.675	-2.34	.019	-7.204	-.639	**
Constant	29.092	3.116	9.33	0	22.983	35.2	***

¹⁸ ORP is a measure of the tendency of a chemical species to acquire electrons from or lose electrons to an electrode and thereby be reduced or oxidized respectively. Redox potential is expressed in volts (V). Each species has its own intrinsic redox potential; for example, the more positive the reduction potential (reduction potential is more often used due to general formalism in electrochemistry), the greater the species' affinity for electrons and tendency to be reduced (Wikipedia accessed January 27, 2025). This can include CaCO₃ crystals.

Mean dependent var	27.915	SD dependent var	17.318
Number of obs	234	Chi-square	5.483
Prob > chi2	0.019	Akaike crit. (AIC)	1885.619

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Phycocyanin is often used as a surrogate for cyanobacteria concentrations that can affect light attenuation via self-shading. Phycocyanin (sqrt transformed) was significantly greater inside corrals than in the lake ($p < 0.001$), (Table 10).

Table 10. Mixed effects regression results of phycocyanin density vs. inside and outside of corrals. Date (monthday) was modeled as random variable.

sqrtPhycoc	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	-.153	.04	-3.86	0	-.231	-.075	***
Constant	1.612	.144	11.19	0	1.33	1.895	***

Mean dependent var	1.573	SD dependent var	0.632
Number of obs	220	Chi-square	14.870
Prob > chi2	0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)	135.078

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mixed effects multilevel regression models for each PAR depth reading vs. inside or outside of corrals, conductivity, TSS, VSS, ORP, Chl *A*, and phycocyanin using date sampled as a random variable showed that the importance of each factor on light attenuation varied by depth (Table 11, Appendix 5). There was good evidence that PAR was greater outside corrals than inside at the two shallowest depths, 47 and 67 cm (Table 11, Appendix 5). Conductivity may have had a negative effect on PAR at 107 cm. There was very strong evidence that TSS negatively affected PAR at all depths, VSS had strong effects on PAR at mid-range depths, 67, 107, and 127 cm, and PAR was positively related to ORP at mid-range depths (Table 11, Appendix 5). PAR was reduced by Chl *A* at the two shallowest depths and phycocyanin was strongly negatively related to PAR at the shallowest depth and may have had an effect at lower depths (Table 11, Appendix 5).

Table 11. Mixed effects multilevel regression models for each PAR depth reading vs. inside or outside of corrals, conductivity, (log)TSS, (sqrt) VSS, (sqrt)ORP, (log)Chl *A*, and (sqrt) phycocyanin using date sampled as a random variable. Key: *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$.

Predictor	Depth (cm)					
	47	67	87	107	127	147
Inside vs. Outside	**	**				
Conductivity				*		
TSS	***	***	***	***	***	***
VSS		**	**	**		
ORP		**	***	***		
ChlA	**	*				
Phycocyanin	***		*	*		

Discussion

Wave action disturbance on easily resuspended sediments¹⁹ in Utah Lake affects light attenuation is a major problem that hinders restoration efforts. Analyses presented in this report showed that by reducing wave action via corrals (mesocosms), CaCO₃ precipitates and other easily suspended particles were able to settle out of the water column and allowed for improved light attenuation, crucial for improving ecosystem function.

Images of water column within the corrals compared to outside in the lake documented in several TSSD mesocosm progress reports showed better clarity inside corrals (Williams et al. 2021, 2022, 2023, Richards et al. 2021, 2022, 2023, and TSSD records). These reports also showed that light attenuation either using Secchi disk readings or turbidity readings (NTUs) was improved inside corrals that reduced wave action disturbance. High densities of CaCO₃ crystals precipitates have been documented by other researchers in Utah Lake (Randall et al. 2019, Taggart 2021).

The higher PAR readings in the upper sections of the water column in the lake indicated that CaCO₃ microcrystal precipitates caused light backscatter reflectance (Figure 14). Backscatter is a well-known phenomenon to underwater divers, photographers, and videographers.

Figure 14. Examples of calcium carbonate microcrystals that can cause light backscatter. From Costa and Salomao 2017, Figure 1. Both calcite and aragonite crystals are common in Utah Lake water column (Randall et al.2019, Williams et al. 2023).

Other factors also likely added to PAR variability both inside and outside of corrals including location of corrals relative to each other (e.g. corral effect wave break effect, (Figure 15), timing and length of high wind/wave and calm water events in relation to sampling dates, unsolicited corral permeability, and corral treatment effects.

The effects of corral location relative to one another was obvious to researchers working on this project. The following photographs illustrates these effects.

¹⁹ Ensor & Pilat (1971) stated that in addition to absorption and scattering by the water itself, particles can scatter light with wavelengths 0 to 4 times the particle diameter (e.g., CaCO₃ nano and microcrystals).

Figure 15. Effects of corral placement on light attenuation is clearly visible in this photo both inside and outside of corrals August 2024. Photo courtesy Rich Mickelsen, Timpanogos Special Service District.

Mesocosms (limnocorrals) demonstrating the effects of reducing wave action on water clarity and light attenuation in August 2022. Photo courtesy Rich Mickelsen, Timpanogos Special Service District.

Although corrals were designed to reduce interactions with the lake water column, leakage occurred, large waves from storm events topped over and into corrals, and corral skirts billowed with heavy wave action that stirred up sediments. This highlights that preventing sediment resuspension will be challenging to restoration efforts and that a holistic approach is necessary, as championed by the Wasatch Front Water Quality Council.

As was demonstrated in this chapter, light attenuation can also be affected by algal concentrations although they appeared to have different effects than did CaCO₃ precipitates. For example, Whittington et al. 2000 showed that Chl a concentration in subsurface accumulations was great enough to significantly attenuate PAR in a subtropical lake and the dinoflagellate, *Ceratium hirundinella* attenuated 88.6% of incident radiation, consequently a major component of underwater extinction of downwelling irradiance. *Ceratium hirundinella* is one of the most abundant and widespread phytoplankton in Utah Lake and it most certainly affects light attenuation, as can other phytoplankton taxa.

Also, microbiologically induced CaCO₃ precipitate (MICP) in the water column either inside corals or outside or both most certainly contributed to light attenuation. MICP basically is the calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) precipitation byproduct created from the metabolic pathway from photosynthetic microorganisms such as nano and picoplankton including some cyanobacteria. MICP occurs in all aquatic ecosystems that contain calcium (e.g., most) both within the water column and at the sediment water interface within complex benthic mats. MICP most certainly occurs in Utah Lake, however the role and its importance to the lake's ecosystem function including light attenuation has been overlooked. MICP is likely as equally important to CaCO₃ precipitation as are strictly and more commonly studied chemical reactions in the Utah Lake ecosystem. Interaction effects of MICP and wave disturbance on light attenuation and ecosystem function within Utah Lake requires further investigation.

Ecological and Restoration Implications

The ecological and restoration implications of improved light attenuation via reduced disturbance are immense for Utah Lake. Restoration measures are needed to stabilize sediments and ensure that CaCO₃ precipitate and other solids fall from the water column and are then sequestered as much as possible into the benthic layers. These measures include establishment of benthic algae, macrophytes, native mollusks and improved water level management or mechanical stabilization methods (Richards et al. 2021, 2022, 2023).

Turbidity in Utah Lake is now primarily caused by wind and wave driven sediment resuspension that directly affects light penetration and nutrient levels in the water column, although bioturbators (e.g., carp, catfish) also contribute to sediment resuspension to a lesser extent. Light and nutrient levels can have many anticipated and unanticipated indirect effects on Utah Lake's food web and ecosystem function including the transfer of nutrients and energy from the base of the food web (primary producers) to grazer consumers (zooplankton) to higher level trophic organisms including fishes and birds.

Trophic transfer of energy and matter from primary producers to higher trophic levels is a fundamental aspect of food web functioning (Jin et al. 2021, Richards and Miller 2024). A reduction in trophic transfer due to wave induced turbulence can potentially lead to declines of higher trophic levels in aquatic food webs including fish and waterbirds, but is generally understudied (Jin et al. 2021, Richards and Miller 2024). A Utah Lake food web model created by Richards and Miller (2024) suggested that trophic transfer efficiency in the lake was out of

balance with Lindeman's (1942) 10% 'rule'²⁰. Richards and Miller (2024) also found that zooplankton grazers in the lake did not appear to be able to utilize a large portion of the phytoplankton biomass mostly during summer months (i.e., low ecotrophic efficiency) and that much of the phytoplankton biomass was unconsumed and fell as detrital 'rain'. These findings suggest that the effects of turbidity on light levels in Utah Lake likely play a significant role in retaining Utah Lake in an unbalanced poorly functioning state.

In large shallow lake ecosystems such as Utah Lake, phytoplankton primary productivity generally becomes light limited by wave induced turbidity (Quinlan et al. 2021, Edwards et al. 2016, Scheffer 1998, Scheffer et al. 2001, Richards 2022b). Resuspension enhances release of sediment bound particles if they are not sequestered, including nutrients into the water column making them available to phytoplankton (Tammeorg et al. 2013, Tang et al. 2020, Zhang et al. 2020). However, large amounts of suspended solids (e.g. CaCO₃ precipitates) entering the water column from resuspension can interfere with nutrient and light availability for phytoplankton production (Schallenberg and Burns 2004).

The effects of mesocosms on the phytoplankton assemblage documented from previous years in the lake clearly implicates wave induced turbidity and sediment resuspension as a leading impairment to its health (Richards et al., 2021, 2022, 2023); more so than did findings from this limited study.

Utah Lake suffers from high turbidity due to several factors including,

- its shallow nature,
- strong winds and waves,
- easily suspended dissolved and fine sediments, particularly CaCO₃ derivatives,
- bioturbator fishes (primarily carp but also other non-indigenous species),
- transition from benthic and macrophyte primary producers that stabilized sediments to phytoplankton dominated primary production,
- loss of mollusks that stabilized sediments, and
- regulation as a reservoir that results in unnatural lake level fluctuations, etc.

PAR varies spatially and temporally in Utah Lake and can change hourly depending on the angle of the sun and wave action. A robust dataset where and when PAR = 0.01 needs to be generated to compare current PAR values to future changes anticipating that PAR will increase during the transition from water column primary productivity to benthic primary productivity after restoration begins.

Food web

Wind and wave action induced turbidity is a major impediment for all members of the food web. High turbidity (i.e., high light attenuation) makes it extremely difficult for visual predators (e.g., piscivorous fishes) to feed and in most of the lake when wave action is strong fish may not even attempt feeding. Turbidity acts as a cover for planktivorous fishes (e.g., all juvenile fishes in

²⁰ Lindeman's (1942) 10% rule is that the efficiency of energy transfer from one trophic level to the next is about 10% or only 10% of the net primary productivity of producers ends up as herbivores and so on through the next trophic levels.

Utah Lake) allowing them to feed on zooplankton that would have helped control phytoplankton (Trochine et al 2022). Sediment resuspension from strong waves can last for many days after a storm event in Utah Lake subsequently increasing light attenuation.

Although Utah Lake is naturally prone to turbid conditions, it was likely much less turbid prior to settlement and light penetrated much deeper in the water column with a more robust littoral zone (Janetski 1990, Williams et al. 2023, Richards et al. 2023). This is because of past abundance of macrophytes, mollusks, and the major contribution of benthic algae to filter and stabilize the substrate compared to present day dominance by water column phytoplankton, bioturbation by invasive carp, and cessation of natural flow and water level regime.

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Recommendations

These analyses were performed as a secondary subset of the ongoing chemistry and ecological analyses of the 2021 to 2024 mesocosm study funded through Timpanogos Special Service District. Initial preliminary analysis prompted the more detailed findings presented in this chapter. Additional more intensive analyses of the data including for example, adding covariates such as wind and weather conditions, modeling interactions with food web covariates, etc. are highly recommended to more completely understand the effects of light attenuation on ecosystem function and to help guide restoration remedies for Utah Lake.

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Chapter 4: Phytoplankton and Periphyton

Introduction

Primary production in Utah Lake transitioned from benthic dominated primary production to water column phytoplankton dominated primary production after a rapid and prolonged ecosystem shift post colonization by Americans of European decent starting over 100 years ago (Williams et al. 2023, Richards et al. 2021, 2022, 2023). This shift resulted in an unbalanced poorly functioning ecosystem with unpredictable stability that continues to this day (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). In a healthy state, Utah Lake primary production should have substantially more contribution from benthic sources, including benthic algae and aquatic macrophytes, given its shallow nature (Scheffer 1998, Scheffer and Jeppesen 1998). Algal blooms, including potentially toxic cyanobacteria blooms (HABs) now occur regularly during summer months. The most important factor contributing to this non-analog condition is sediment resuspension from wave action and bioturbators e.g., carp and catfish, and loss of sediment stabilizing macrophytes and bivalve mollusks (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024).

Beneficial effects of wave action reduction, carp exclusion, and limited sediment resuspension on phytoplankton and periphyton assemblages in Utah Lake were demonstrated in our previous mesocosm progress reports (Richards et al., 2022, 2023, 2024). Here we document these effects from mesocosm experiments conducted in 2024.

Methods

Phytoplankton Sampling and Processing

We used what Utah Division of Water Quality (DWQ) refers to as an ‘integrated’ sample or what Rushforth Phycology refers to as a ‘surface’ sample collection method to sample phytoplankton from inside and outside corrals. We inverted a 500 ml labeled plastic sample jar to elbow depth in the water and then slowly reinverted and lifted the jar to the surface to capture as much water equally at depth. Lugol’s solution was added to the samples. Samples were then placed on ice and delivered to Rushforth Phycology as soon as possible, usually within one day.

A total of 179 phytoplankton samples were collected and processed. See Table 1 for a list of sample dates, and samples collected inside and outside of limnocorrals.

Table 12 List of sample events (dates), samples collected inside limnocorrals (LC), and outside of limnocorrals (Out) in 2024. See Figure 1 for limnocorral locations and numbering.

Sample Event	Inside (LC)	Outside (Out)
June 18	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
July 1	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4
July 17	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4
July 22	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
July 29	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5

August 14	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
August 19	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4
August 27	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
September 4	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
September 10	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
September 17	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
September 23	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5
October 9	LC1, LC2, LC3, LC4, LC5, LC6, LC7, LC8, LC9	Out1, Out2, Out3, Out4, Out5

All algal taxonomies were performed by Rushforth Phycology (rushforthphycology.com), the leading algal taxonomy experts for Utah Lake and surrounding aquatic ecosystems. Rushforth Phycology reported phytoplankton taxonomic results as percent relative density, cell mL⁻¹, and biovolume, $\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$. We consider the most ecologically relevant measure for ecosystem studies to be biovolume ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) and used biovolumes in our previous progress reports. Subsequently, biovolume was the measure we used for this study²¹.

Periphyton Sampling and Processing

Periphyton samples were collected by inverting a 55 mm diameter (86.4 mm² area) plastic jar over the inside of a south facing corral skirt panel and scraping all periphyton into jar. Samples were collected from all nine corrals on July 17, August 15, September 4, and October 9.

Two samples were collected at each corral. One sample was taken to River Continuum Concepts lab for biomass estimates and the other sample to Rushforth Phycology for taxonomic identification. Biomass samples were corrected for the total solids (TSS, TDS (unfiltered)) of a 120 ml sample of limnocorral lake water contained in the sample (the same total volume of the periphyton scrapes). Biomass samples were dried at 60° C for 48 hrs.

Taxonomy samples were only collected from corrals C1, C2, C3, C4, and C7 on July 17; C1, C2, C4, C6, C7 and C8 on August 15. Taxonomy was to genus and species except for centric and pennate diatoms and by algal division for each taxon. Taxa values were reported by percent relative density, cell mL⁻¹, and by biovolume $\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$.

Statistical Methods

Four to five letter codes were made for each phytoplankton taxon, typically the first two letters of the genus name and the first two letters of the species name unless there were duplicates (Table 13). Seven to eight- digit location and sampling date codes were also developed for use in analyses.

Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMS) ordination was evaluated to compare phytoplankton assemblage dis(similarity) relationships statistically and visually between corrals and dates. Ordination techniques are often more informative than hypothesis-testing approaches for exploring relationships between multivariate ecological assemblages or communities (McCune and Grace 2002). In general, ordination is the ordering of objects along axes according to their (dis)similarities; the main objective of ordination is to reduce many-dimensional

²¹ All Rushforth Phycology reports that contain percent relative densities and cells mL⁻¹ are available on request.

relationships into a small number of more easily interpretable dimensions (i.e., axes on a plot). The strongest correlation structure in the data is extracted and is then used to position objects in ordination space. Objects that are close in the ordination space are more similar than objects distant in ordination space (McCune and Mefford 2011).

NMS was evaluated in these analyses because it has been shown to be robust and highly informative for understanding ecological relationships. NMS ordination is often more broadly applicable for ecological studies than other ordination techniques because it does not require relationships among variables to be linear (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010). NMS ordination permits the visualization of the multidimensional relationships of phytoplankton assemblages into a more easily visualized, lower dimensional space. Dimensional reduction obviously creates some distortion in relationships between samples. The level of reduction in distortion is measured as 'stress', where lower stress values equal less distortion. NMS plots with stress values of 15% (0.15) or less are typically considered to be a good representation of the data and stress values lower than 10% (0.10) are considered excellent representations (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010).

Several distance measures were used and evaluated including Sorensen (Bray-Curtis), Relative Sorensen, Jaccard, Euclidean, Relative Euclidean, and Morisita-Horn. NMS analysis was run for 250 iterations using the real data and 250 iterations in randomized Monte Carlo simulations. Best-fit models were selected based on stable final stress < 0.15 and 3-dimensional solutions or less. NMS ordinations were rotated using varimax rotation to maximize variation along the axes and extracted as univariate scores. Consequently, the final ordinations can be rotated either vertically or horizontally without effecting the results. Centroid labels and convex hulls of months were added to the ordinations to aid in the interpretation of the relationships. Post hoc proportion of variance represented by each axis was calculated based on the R^2 value between distance in the ordination space and distance in the original space.

Multiple Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP), a non-parametric multivariate method was used to formally test the hypothesis of no differences in phytoplankton assemblages between months. MRPP has the advantage of not requiring distributional assumptions such as multivariate normality and homogeneity of variance and thus is often preferred over perMANOVA for analyzing multivariate ecological data (McCune and Grace 2002). The same distance measure was used for each MRPP analyses as was for corresponding NMS models. The chance-corrected within-group test statistic, A (and associated p-value) was used to evaluate the hypothesis of no difference in groupings (McCune and Grace 2002). Post hoc multiple comparisons were also made when appropriate.

We used Indicator Species Analysis (ISA) in PC-ORD to determine taxa that were strong indicators of sampling events (seasonal). ISA used Dufrêne and Legendre's (1997) method of calculating species indicator values that provided a simple, intuitive solution. The method combined information on biovolumes of phytoplankton taxa abundance for each sample event and the faithfulness of occurrence of a taxon in a particular sample event. ISA produced indicator values for each taxon in each group. These were then tested for statistical significance using a randomization technique (Richards et al. 2004, McCune and Grace 2002 for more detailed information on ISA method).

All multivariate and several additional analyses including rank abundance and descriptive summary statistics were made using PC-ORD for Windows Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018) using Parallels Desktop 19.2.1 for Mac virtual platform.

Regression analyses were selected using the most appropriate model including linear, Poisson, fractional, and negative binomial. Candidate predictors (factors) were screened using Lasso regression. Lasso regression is a machine learning method that allows for selection of subsets of best fit models from many candidate factors. The final best fit regression models were then reevaluated from the lasso selected models and chosen based on lowest log likelihood, AIC, and BIC values. ANOVAs and MANOVAs were also conducted where appropriate. Descriptive statistics were also calculated for select data. Nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis equality of populations rank test were applied when data were not near normally distributed after transformation. Box and whisker plots were developed for non-normally distributed data. Box plots used median, 25th, 75th, lower and upper adjacent values and outside values. Statistical analyses and graphics were made using Stata 16.1 for Mac (Intel 64-bit) (StataCorp 2021). Graphical representations of statistical models were made using either Stata or PC-ORD. Details of additional statistical methods not listed here are described in individual Results sections.

Results

Seventy-seven phytoplankton taxa were observed in our 2024 study (Table 13). A list of taxa and codes used in analyses is in Table 13.

Table 13. 2024 phytoplankton taxa list and codes used in analyses.

Taxon	Code
<i>Actinastrum hantzschii</i> Lagerheim	ACHA
<i>Acutodesmus</i> sp.	ACSP
<i>Anabaena</i> sp.	ANSP
<i>Ankistrodesmus arcuatus</i> Korshikov (= <i>Monoraphidium arcuatum</i> (Korshikov) Hindák)	ANAR
<i>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</i> (Corda) Ralfs	ANFA
<i>Ankyra judayi</i> (Smith) Fott (= <i>Schroederia judayi</i> (Smith) Fott)	ANJU
<i>Aphanizomenon flosaquae</i> Ralfs ex Bornet & Flahault	APFL
<i>Aphanocapsa incerta</i> (Lemmermann) G.Cronberg & Komárek (= <i>Microcystis incerta</i> (Lemmermann) Cronberg & Komárek)	APIN
<i>Aphanocapsa</i> sp.	APCSP
<i>Aphanothece</i> sp.	APSP
<i>Asterionella formosa</i> Hassall	ASFO
<i>Aulacoseira distans</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira distans</i>)	AUDI
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i>)	AUGR
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i> (Müller) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i>)	AUGRA
centric diatoms species	CDSP
<i>Ceratium hirundinella</i> (Müller) Dujardin	CEHI
<i>Chlamydomonas</i> sp.	CHLSP

<i>Chroococcus dispersus</i> (Keissler) Lemmermann	CHDI
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> (Lemmermann) Lemmermann	CLLO
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> var. <i>tropica</i> West & West	CLLT
<i>Crucigenia quadrata</i> Morren	CRQU
<i>Crucigenia</i> sp.	CRSP
<i>Crucigeniella rectangularis</i> (Nägeli) Komárek (= <i>Willea rectangularis</i> (Braun) John, Wynne & Tsarenko)	CRRE
<i>Cryptomonas richei</i> Fritsch Fritsch	CRRI
<i>Cryptomonas</i> sp.	CRPTSP
<i>Desmidium</i> sp.	DESP
<i>Desmodesmus bicellularis</i> (Chodat) An, Friedl & Hegewald	DEBI
<i>Desmodesmus communis</i> (Hegewald) Hegewald	DECO
<i>Desmodesmus intermedius</i> (Chodat) Hegewald	DEIN
<i>Desmodesmus opoliensis</i> (Richter) Hegewald	DEOP
<i>Dolichospermum circinalis</i> (Brébisson) Wacklin, Hoffmann & Komárek (= <i>Anabaena circinalis</i> Rabenhorst)	DOCI
<i>Dolichospermum planctonicum</i> (Brunnthaler) Wacklin, Hoffmann & Komárek	DOPL
<i>Dolichospermum</i> sp.	DOSP
<i>Eremosphaera gigas</i> (Archer) Fott & Kalina (= <i>Oocystis gigas</i> Archer)	ERGI
<i>Euglena</i> sp.	EUSP
<i>Fragilaria crotonensis</i> Kitton	FRCR
<i>Gregiochloris lacustris</i> (Chodat) Marvan, Komárek & Comas (= <i>Quadrigula lacustris</i> (Chodat) Smith)	GRLA
<i>Gymnodinium</i> sp.	GYSB
<i>Kirchneriella lunaris</i> (Kirchner) Möbius (= <i>Kirchneriella lunata</i> Schmidle)	KILU
<i>Kirchneriella</i> sp.	KISP
<i>Komma</i> sp.	KOSP
<i>Melosira varians</i> Agardh	MEVA
<i>Merismopedia glauca</i> (Ehrenberg) Kützing	MEGL
<i>Merismopedia</i> sp.	MESP
<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i> (Kützing) Kützing	MIAE
<i>Monoraphidium contortum</i> (Thuret) Komárková-Legnerová	MOCO
<i>Monoraphidium convolutum</i> (Corda) Komárková-Legnerová (= <i>Ankistrodesmus convolutus</i> Corda)	MOCOV
<i>Monoraphidium</i> sp.	MOSP
<i>Oocystis borgei</i> Snow	OOBO
<i>Oocystis</i> sp.	OOSP
<i>Oscillatoria</i> sp.	OCSP
<i>Pandorina morum</i> (Müller) Bory	PAMO
<i>Pectinodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Hegewald, Wolf, Keller, Friedl & Krienitz (= <i>Acutodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Tsarenko)	PEPE
<i>Pediastrum angulosum</i> Ehrenberg ex Meneghini	PEAN
<i>Pediastrum duplex</i> Meyen (= <i>Pediastrum duplex</i> var. <i>clathratum</i> Meyen)	PEDU
Pennate diatoms	PD

<i>Peridinium</i> sp.	PESP
<i>Phacus</i> sp.	PHCSP
<i>Phormidium</i> sp.	PHRSP
<i>Pseudanabaena</i> sp.	PSSP
<i>Pteromonas</i> sp.	PTSP
<i>Quadrigula chodatii</i> (Tanner-Füllemann) Smith	QUCH
<i>Quadrigula</i> sp.	QUSP
<i>Scenedesmus bijugus</i> (Turpin) Lagerheim	SCBI
<i>Scenedesmus ellipticus</i> Corda	SCEL
<i>Scenedesmus obtusus</i> Meyen	SCOB
<i>Scenedesmus</i> sp.	SCSP
<i>Schroederia setigera</i> (Schröder) Lemmermann	SCSE
<i>Snowella</i> sp.	SNSP
<i>Sphaerocystis schroeteri</i> Chodat	SPSC
<i>Stephanodiscus niagarae</i> Ehrenberg	STNI
<i>Tetraëdron caudatum</i> (Corda) Hansgirg	TECA
<i>Trachelomonas</i> sp.	TRSP
<i>Tribonema</i> sp.	TRIS
Unknown colonial cyanophyte	UNCCY
Unknown spherical chlorophyte 2	UNSPCH2
<i>Willea crucifera</i> (Wolle) John, Wynne & Tsarenko (= <i>Crucigeniella crucifera</i> (Wolle) Komarek	WICR

The list of phytoplankton taxa organized by algal division is in Table 14.

Table 14. Phytoplankton taxa scientific names listed by algal divisions.

Taxon	Algal Division
<i>Aulacoseira distans</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira distans</i>)	Bacillariophyta
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i>)	Bacillariophyta
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i> (Müller) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i>)	Bacillariophyta
centric diatoms species	Bacillariophyta
<i>Fragilaria crotonensis</i> Kitton	Bacillariophyta
<i>Melosira varians</i> Agardh	Bacillariophyta
pennate diatoms	Bacillariophyta
<i>Stephanodiscus niagarae</i> Ehrenberg	Bacillariophyta
<i>Actinastrum hantzschii</i> Lagerheim	Chlorophyta
<i>Acutodesmus</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Ankistrodesmus arcuatus</i> Korshikov (= <i>Monoraphidium arcuatum</i> (Korshikov) Hindák)	Chlorophyta
<i>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</i> (Corda) Ralfs	Chlorophyta
<i>Ankyra judayi</i> (Smith) Fott (= <i>Schroederia judayi</i> (Smith) Fott)	Chlorophyta
<i>Chlamydomonas</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> (Lemmermann) Lemmermann	Chlorophyta

<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> var. <i>tropica</i> West & West	Chlorophyta
<i>Crucigenia quadrata</i> Morren	Chlorophyta
<i>Crucigenia</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Crucigeniella rectangularis</i> (Nägeli) Komárek (= <i>Willea rectangularis</i> (Braun) John, Wynne & Tsarenko)	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmidium</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus bicellularis</i> (Chodat) An, Friedl & Hegewald	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus communis</i> (Hegewald) Hegewald	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus intermedius</i> (Chodat) Hegewald	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus opoliensis</i> (Richter) Hegewald	Chlorophyta
<i>Eremosphaera gigas</i> (Archer) Fott & Kalina (= <i>Oocystis gigas</i> Archer)	Chlorophyta
<i>Gregiochloris lacustris</i> (Chodat) Marvan, Komárek & Comas (= <i>Quadrigula lacustris</i> (Chodat) Smith)	Chlorophyta
<i>Kirchneriella lunaris</i> (Kirchner) Möbius (= <i>Kirchneriella lunata</i> Schmidle)	Chlorophyta
<i>Kirchneriella</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Komma</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Monoraphidium contortum</i> (Thuret) Komárková-Legnerová	Chlorophyta
<i>Monoraphidium convolutum</i> (Corda) Komárková-Legnerová (= <i>Ankistrodesmus convolutus</i> Corda)	Chlorophyta
<i>Monoraphidium</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Oocystis borgei</i> Snow	Chlorophyta
<i>Oocystis</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Pandorina morum</i> (Müller) Bory	Chlorophyta
<i>Pectinodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Hegewald, Wolf, Keller, Friedl & Krienitz (= <i>Acutodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Tsarenko)	Chlorophyta
<i>Pediastrum angulosum</i> Ehrenberg ex Meneghini	Chlorophyta
<i>Pediastrum duplex</i> Meyen (= <i>Pediastrum duplex</i> var. <i>clathratum</i> Meyen)	Chlorophyta
<i>Pteromonas</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Quadrigula chodatii</i> (Tanner-Füllemann) Smith	Chlorophyta
<i>Quadrigula</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Scenedesmus bijugus</i> (Turpin) Lagerheim	Chlorophyta
<i>Scenedesmus ellipticus</i> Corda	Chlorophyta
<i>Scenedesmus obtusus</i> Meyen	Chlorophyta
<i>Scenedesmus</i> species	Chlorophyta
<i>Schroederia setigera</i> (Schröder) Lemmermann	Chlorophyta
<i>Sphaerocystis schroeteri</i> Chodat	Chlorophyta
<i>Tetraëdron caudatum</i> (Corda) Hansgirg	Chlorophyta
Unknown spherical chlorophyte 2	Chlorophyta
<i>Willea crucifera</i> (Wolle) John, Wynne & Tsarenko (= <i>Crucigeniella crucifera</i> (Wolle) Komarek)	Chlorophyta
<i>Cryptomonas richei</i> Fritsch Fritsch	Cryptophyta
<i>Cryptomonas</i> species	Cryptophyta
<i>Anabaena</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> Ralfs ex Bornet & Flahault	Cyanophyta

<i>Aphanocapsa incerta</i> (Lemmermann) G.Cronberg & Komárek (= <i>Microcystis incerta</i> (Lemmermann) Cronberg & Komárek)	Cyanophyta
<i>Aphanocapsa</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Aphanothece</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Chroococcus dispersus</i> (Keissler) Lemmermann	Cyanophyta
<i>Dolichospermum circinalis</i> (Brébisson) Wacklin, Hoffmann & Komárek (= <i>Anabaena circinalis</i> Rabenhorst)	Cyanophyta
<i>Dolichospermum planctonicum</i> (Brunnthal) Wacklin, Hoffmann & Komárek	Cyanophyta
<i>Dolichospermum</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Merismopedia glauca</i> (Ehrenberg) Kützing	Cyanophyta
<i>Merismopedia</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i> (Kützing) Kützing	Cyanophyta
<i>Oscillatoria</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Phormidium</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Pseudanabaena</i> species	Cyanophyta
<i>Snowella</i> species	Cyanophyta
Unknown colonial cyanophyte	Cyanophyta
<i>Ceratium hirundinella</i> (Müller) Dujardin	Dinophyta
<i>Gymnodinium</i> species	Dinophyta
<i>Peridinium</i> species	Dinophyta
<i>Asterionella formosa</i> Hassall	Euglenophyta
<i>Euglena</i> species	Euglenophyta
<i>Phacus</i> species	Euglenophyta
<i>Trachelomonas</i> species	Euglenophyta
<i>Tribonema</i> species	Xanthophyceae

Chlorophyte taxa richness made up more than 50% of phytoplankton assemblage followed by cyanophytes and then bacillariophytes (Figure 16). Dinophytes, chrysophytes, euglenophytes, cryptophytes, and xanthophytes were also present but at lower diversity (Figure 16).

Figure 16. Number of phytoplankton taxa and percentage in each division.

We estimated that there were between 94 and 104 taxa in the study area based on rarefaction analysis, first-order jackknife, second-order jackknife, and Chao estimators given our sampling effort.

Several taxa dominated the phytoplankton assemblage in our study both by biovolume and by frequency of occurrences (number of samples taxon occurred in), primarily *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL)(cyanophyte), *Ceratium hirundinella* (CEHI)(dinophyte), *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI)(cyanophyte), and *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHSP)(chlorophyte) (Table 15).

Aphanizomenon flosaquae (APFL), a potential HAB taxon, had the highest abundance (biovolume) throughout the study and was present in 96% of the samples (Table 15). *Ceratium hirundinella* occurred in 99% of samples, ranked second in biovolume. *Ceratium hirundinella* is rarely discussed in Utah Lake ecology studies or water quality evaluations (Table 15), consequently we give a brief literature review of its biology and ecology in Appendix 35. *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI), another potential HAB taxon, occurred in 91% of the samples and ranked third in overall biovolume (Table 15). Because of their relatively small size, pennate diatoms (PD) ranked six in biovolume but occurred in 97% of the samples (Table 15), and centric diatoms (CDSP) were also very abundant. See Table 15 for rank abundance, rank frequency, and frequency of each taxon and Appendix 9 for summary statistics of each taxon's biovolume by sample date inside and outside of corrals.

Table 15. Phytoplankton taxa rank abundance, rank frequency, and frequency of occurrences. Total number of samples = 179. Taxa names are in Table 13.

Taxon	Rank Abundance (biovolume)	Rank Frequency	Frequency
APFL	1	3	171
CEHI	2	1	175
DOCI	3	5	163
CHLSP	4	4	167
OCSP	5	8	109
PHRSP	6	18	29
CRPTSP	7	9	106
PD	8	2	173
CLLT	9	13	60
CDSP	10	6	151
EUSP	11	10	72
ANSP	12	17	32
AUGRA	13	7	110
CLLO	14	21	21
PEDU	15	23	20
MIAE	16	56	2
STNI	17	38	4
OOBO	18	15	34
KOSP	19	11	64
AUGR	20	28	14
ANJU	21	14	39
OOSP	22	26	16
SCSE	23	16	33
PESP	24	30	6
SPSC	25	47	3
GYSP	26	25	16
PHCSP	27	19	26
FRCR	28	70	1
DOPL	29	41	3
UNCCY	30	72	1
PAMO	31	48	3
ASFO	32	36	5
TRIS	33	50	3
ANFA	34	12	60
SCEL	35	32	5
CRR1	36	59	2
DESP	37	65	1
DECO	38	27	16
TRSP	39	24	17

ERGI	40	42	3
MEVA	41	35	5
DEOP	42	29	11
DOSP	43	53	2
PTSP	44	20	24
PEPE	45	40	4
DEBI	46	22	20
APCSP	47	44	3
PEAN	48	49	3
CRQU	49	45	3
SCSP	50	55	2
CHDI	51	34	5
APIN	52	52	2
SNSP	53	75	1
SCOB	54	63	1
SCBI	55	37	4
CRSP	56	73	1
CRRE	57	77	1
QUCH	58	68	1
ACHA	59	33	5
PSSP	60	31	6
ACSP	61	66	1
GRLA	62	43	3
DEIN	63	51	3
QUSP	64	60	1
AUDI	65	67	1
WICR	66	74	1
APSP	67	76	1
KISP	68	54	2
ANAR	69	46	3
MEGL	70	39	4
KILU	71	57	2
UNSPCH2	72	69	1
TECA	73	64	1
MOCOV	74	61	1
MESP	75	62	1
MOCO	76	71	1
MOSP	77	58	2

Phytoplankton Assemblages

There was strong evidence of seasonal phytoplankton assemblage patterns using NMS and MRPP. The best fit NMS model had an excellent 2-dimensional solution, with final stress = 8.40, final instability < 0.001 at 36 iterations using a Relative Sorensen distance matrix. The NMS model explained 0.96 seasonal variability in assemblages with Axis 1 = 0.10 and Axis 2 = 0.86 (Figure 17). The NMS model showed that phytoplankton assemblages varied by sampling date but that there was not a seasonal progression, as we have reported elsewhere in Utah Lake or as occurs throughout temperate regions in aquatic ecosystems. This could have been due to bloom effects that occurred circa July 1, August 14, and September 23 (NMS ordination lower left quadrant in Figure 4) and often exponentially increased in less than a week. Individual taxa biovolumes in Utah Lake can differ annually (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). Some of the less common taxa varied more so than did the common taxa annually (see Appendix 9). 2024 was also a high-water year compared to previous years and likely affected assemblages and taxa relative abundances as a result.

Figure 17. Best fit NMS ordination map with sample date centroids. Taxa codes are labeled nearby to help visualization.

Multiple response permutation procedure (MRPP) provided strong evidence that phytoplankton assemblages differed between sample dates ($T = -36.46$, $A = 0.50$, $p < 0.001$). Post hoc pairwise comparisons gave strong evidence that assemblages differed from each other for all dates, except Sept 4 vs. Sept 23, and Sept 10 vs. Sept 17 (Appendix 8). However, MRPP did not provide

evidence that assemblages inside and outside of corrals were different ($T = -0.45$, $A = 0.002$, $p = 0.20$) when all collection date samples were combined.

Many taxa were seasonal and had greatest biovolumes at different dates. Indicator Species Analysis provided evidence that many taxa were strong indicators for ten of the thirteen sampling dates (Table 16).

Table 16. Indicator Species Analysis results. Listed are taxa that were considered indicators for those dates.

Taxon	Sample Date	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	IV from randomized groups		
			Mean	S. Dev	p
ANFA	June18	39.4	8.2	2.33	0.0002
ASFO	June18	35.7	4.8	3.01	0.0002
OOSP	June18	52.8	5.4	2.54	0.0002
SCSE	June18	83.6	7.1	2.73	0.0002
PEDU	June18	20.9	5.5	2.27	0.0006
DECO	June18	22.2	6.2	3.09	0.0014
GRLA	June18	21.4	4.5	3.05	0.0052
STNI	June18	19	5	2.91	0.0054
PAMO	June18	21.4	4.4	3.02	0.0058
CHDI	June18	15.5	5.7	3.05	0.0224
APIN	June18	14.3	4.5	2.84	0.0744
APFL	July1	25.4	12.6	1.72	0.0002
AUGRA	July1	20.7	9.9	1.88	0.0002
SPSC	July1	12.5	4.4	3.05	0.0166
CHLSP	July17	49.8	25.1	4.16	0.0002
ACHA	July29	35.7	4.8	2.83	0.0002
GYPSP	July29	61.2	5.6	2.6	0.0002
KOSP	July29	33.9	8.4	2.32	0.0002
PHCSP	July29	26.6	5.8	2.21	0.0002
PTSP	July29	54.4	5.8	2.38	0.0002
DOPL	July29	21.4	4.9	2.83	0.006
MEGL	July29	16.1	4.2	3.09	0.0154
APCSP	July29	11.3	4.4	2.92	0.0658
PSSP	July29	8.6	4.6	2.72	0.0706
ANJU	Aug14	31.8	7.1	2.46	0.0002
CEHI	Aug14	23.3	12.8	1.74	0.0002
ANSP	Aug14	20.7	6.5	2.35	0.0004
DOSP	Aug14	14.3	4.5	2.74	0.0684
SCSP	Aug14	14.3	4.6	2.9	0.078
PHRSP	Aug19	40.4	6.8	2.63	0.0002

PESP	Aug27	32	4.6	2.74	0.0002
TRSP	Sept4	12.6	5.2	2.23	0.0122
DOCI	Sept23	22.8	12	1.61	0.0002
EUSP	Sept23	40.2	9.1	2.42	0.0002
CRPTSP	Sept23	21.7	11.1	2.48	0.002
CLLO	Sept23	16.2	5.6	2.34	0.0026
OCSP	Oct9	29.6	11.1	2.44	0.0002
CLLT	Oct9	19.9	7.9	2.24	0.0008

Although MRPP did not provide evidence for differences in assemblage composition inside vs. outside of corrals, four taxa were found to be indicators of conditions inside corrals over the entire 2024 study, *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHLSP) (chlorophyte), pennate diatoms (PD)(bacillariophyte), *Cryptomonas* sp. (CRPTSP) (cryptophyte), and *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI) (cyanophyte). One taxon was an indicator of outside corrals, *Desmodesmus intermedius* (DEIN) (chlorophyte) (Table 17). However, *D. intermedius* was rare and only occurred outside of corrals at very low abundance ($< 2500 \mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) on June 18 and July 29 (see Appendix 9).

Table 17. Indicator Species Analysis results. Listed are taxa that were considered indicators for inside or outside of corrals.

Taxon	Inside vs. Outside	IV from randomized groups			
		Observed Indicator Value (IV)	Mean	S. Dev	p
CHLSP	Inside	79.5	56.9	6.4	0.0002
PD	Inside	84.8	63.3	5.18	0.0002
CRPTSP	Inside	44.6	34.1	3.57	0.0098
DOCI	Inside	55.9	49.6	3.16	0.0426
DEIN	Outside	4.8	1.9	0.97	0.0406

Pennate diatoms are primarily associated with stable conditions including benthic substrate or grow as part of the periphyton community (e.g., on sides of corrals). Improved stable conditions inside corrals allowed pennate diatoms to increase in abundance and become indicator species. This is well worth noting and will be discussed further.

Figure 18 shows phytoplankton taxa relations with sample dates and corrals using a two-way cluster dendrogram and heat map distribution. Biovolumes ($\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$) of the most abundant taxa by date and between corrals and open lake water are shown in boxplots in Figure 19. Summary statistics for all taxa by date are shown in Appendix 9.

Figure 18. Two way cluster dendrogram and heat map distribution .This figure is more easily read if viewed on a computer screen and enlarged.

Figure 19. Relationships between the ten most abundant (biovolume) and frequency of occurrence phytoplankton taxa with sampling dates and inside and outside of corals. Median, 25th, 75th, upper adjacent values, and outside values.

Algal blooms appeared on three occasions during the 2024 study. They occurred circa July 1, August 14, and September 23 and often exponentially increased starting in less than a week prior (see Figure 19 graph of total phytoplankton biovolume by date and inside vs. outside corrals).

Phytoplankton taxa in relation to sample date, inside vs. outside corrals, temperature, and blooms

As was shown in Figure 19, taxa biovolumes varied by sampling date. Best fit regressions were made of the ten most abundant taxa by volume or greatest frequency of occurrences (N = 13 taxa) in relation to sample date, inside vs. outside of corrals, and blooms. There was strong evidence that all thirteen taxa biovolumes differed by sample date. Some of these taxa were associated with blooms, and four taxa had greater biovolumes inside than outside of corrals, including *Dolichospermum circinalis* (cyanophyte), *Chlamydomonas* sp. (chlorophyte) *Cryptomonas* sp. (cryptophyte), and pennate diatoms (bacillariophyte) (Table 18). As stated earlier, these four taxa were also considered indicator taxa for conditions inside corrals (Table 17).

Table 18. Ten most abundant taxa by volume or greatest frequency of occurrences in relation to total biovolumes (blooms) and whether biovolumes were greater inside than outside of corrals. Y = yes, N = no, + = indicator species.

Taxon	Total biovolume	Inside vs. outside
<i>Aphanizomenon flos-aquae</i> (cyanophyte)	Y	N
<i>Ceratium hirundinella</i> (dinoflagellate)	Y	N
<i>Dolichospermum circinalis</i> (cyanophyte)	Y	Y+
<i>Chlamydomonas</i> sp. (chlorophyte)	Y	Y+
<i>Oscillatoria</i> sp. (cyanophyte)	Y	N
<i>Phormidium</i> sp. (cyanophyte)	N	N
<i>Cryptomonas</i> sp. (cryptophyte)	Y	Y+
Pennate diatoms (bacillariophyte)	N	Y+
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> (chlorophyte)	N	N
centric diatoms species (bacillariophyte)	N	N
<i>Euglena</i> sp. (euglenophyte)	Y	N
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i> ²² (bacillariophyte)	N	N
Total biovolume	NA	N

Phytoplankton Richness and Diversity

Five universally used diversity indices were evaluated, 1) taxa richness (s), 2) effective number of taxa (ENT), 3) evenness (e), 4) Shannon diversity (h), and 5) Simpson diversity (d). All five indices varied by sampling date and there was good evidence ($p < 0.05$ to < 0.10) that all five diversity indices were greater inside corrals vs outside (Figure 20) signifying improved conditions within the corrals (Figure 20, Appendix 15 through Appendix 19).

²² *Aulacoseira granulata* var. *angustissima* is a non-motile, unattached, planktonic diatom that commonly forms colonies (Spaulding et al. 2021)

Figure 20. Richness and diversity indices by month inside and outside of corral, and total inside and outside corral.

Regression analyses also provided strong evidence ($p < 0.01$) that taxa richness (s), effective number of taxa (ENT), evenness (e), Shannon’s and Simpson’s diversity indices were all affected by total phytoplankton biovolume, varied by sample date, and were greater inside than outside corral (Appendix 15 through Appendix 19). Taxa richness was positively related to total phytoplankton biovolume, while the other indices were negatively related to total phytoplankton biovolume (Appendix 15 through Appendix 19) indicating that as phytoplankton biovolume increased (i.e., blooms), the number of taxa also increased however, diversity decreased and became dominated by only a few taxa.

The following table (Table 19) summarizes the differences between taxa richness and effective number of taxa (ENT) demonstrating that Utah Lake’s phytoplankton assemblages are out of balance, with only two to three ENT at any given time in the study area. However, improved conditions inside corral increased ENT (Appendix 16).

Table 19. Comparison of summary statistics of taxa richness vs. effective number of taxa, ENT.

	Mean	s.e. (Mean)	p25	Median	p75
Number of taxa	11.55	.28	9.00	11	13
ENT	2.45	.07	1.81	2.25	2.98

Temperature and Solar Radiation effects

Phytoplankton blooms are associated with warm summer temperatures and long days of solar radiation in temperate regions throughout the world. Our study occurred from late June to early October with seasonally warm water temperatures and relatively long daylight hours. Subsequently, analyses evaluating temperature and daylight effects on phytoplankton blooms were limited to those conditions. However, some interesting results were found.

Blooms mostly occurred later in summer as temperatures and sunlight hours (total solar radiation) decreased (Figure 21). Temperatures were greatest in late June early July and decreased by almost by 6 °C by the end of our study in October. Sunlight hours also decreased from June 21 until October. Many bloom taxa had greater densities in late summer- early autumn (Figure 19). It only takes a few days for phytoplankton to double in biovolume (exponential increase) into bloom biovolumes. This suggests that even with increasing temperature and solar radiation starting in late spring- early summer initiate blooms, blooms were not dependent on the warmest summer temperatures or on maximum daylight hours. Obviously, other factors and interactions were at play such as interspecific competition for resources such as Ca, Fe, Mg, Al, K, nutrients, zooplankton predation, etc. or unmeasured factors such as wind speeds and strong wind duration prior to sampling.

Figure 21. Relationship between phytoplankton biovolume (log transformed) and temperature and number of days away from astronomical summer solstice, June 21. Shaded areas are 95% CIs.

One important factor that we documented in our 2023 progress report was Fe. Fe was also an important predictor of phytoplankton biovolume in this year's study (Figure 22).

Figure 22. Relation between phytoplankton biovolume and Fe.

However, when other measured factors (predictors) were modeled, phytoplankton biovolume was apparently not strongly related to Fe but more positively related to Al, Mg, TSS, ORP, and negatively related to conductivity and NO₂ ($R^2 = 0.69$, $p < 0.01$) (Appendix 20). Note: Phosphorus constituents (TP, dissolved P, or OrthoP) were not found to be useful predictors of total phytoplankton biovolume.

Although total phytoplankton biovolume was related to some factors but not others, each taxon reacted differently to the same measured factors. *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL) was positively related to TSS and K but negatively related to conductivity and dissolved P (Appendix 21) likely because it up took up P from the water column; the more *A. flosaquae* present the less dissolved P was in the water column.

Dolichospermum circinalis (DOCI) was positively related to pH, NO₃, Mg, and Fe, and negatively related to OrthoP, conductivity, and DO (Appendix 22). *Oscillatoria* sp. (OCSP) was positively related to Mg, ORP, AL, and NO₃, but negatively related to TP (Appendix 23). *Phormidium* sp. (PHRSP) was positively related to Al and negatively related to Ca and Mg (Appendix 24). *Ceratium hirundinella* (CEHI) was positively related to TSS, TP, and conductivity, negatively related to Ca (Appendix 25). *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHLSP) was positively related to NO₂, VSS, and Ca; negatively related to COD, NH₃, and dissolved P although not significantly with NH₃, and dissolved P at $p < 0.05$ (Appendix 26).

The best predictors of pennate diatoms (PD) evaluated from all chemistry and dominant phytoplankton taxa were inside vs. outside of corals, sample date, and centric diatoms (CD). Centric diatoms (CD) had more predictors than did pennate diatoms (PD). Some predictors were not statistically significant (e.g. Ca, temperature), but the model performed better with their inclusion, so we infer that they had some indirect influence on CDs (see SEM results below).

Relationships of cyanobacteria (HABs) with Fe, Mg, Ca, nutrients, and other dominant phytoplankton taxa

There is concern about the potential for harmful algal blooms (cyanobacteria) in the lake particularly during summer months. In addition, cyanobacteria often require metals such as Fe and Mg for metabolism and photosynthesis. Cyanobacteria may also compete for limited resources. This section analyses these potential factors on cyanobacteria biovolumes.

Methods

The most abundant (by biovolume) cyanobacteria taxa in this study were *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL), *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI), *Oscillatoria* sp. (OCSP), and *Phormidium* sp. (PHRSP). The dinophyte, *Ceratium hirundinella* (CEHI) and chlorophyte, *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHLSP) also dominated. The relations with and between these taxa and Al, Ca, Fe, Mg, total phosphorus (TP), orthophosphate (OrthoP), dissolved P, NO₂, NO₃ were modeled using structural equation models (SEM).

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is a sophisticated statistical technique that allowed us to examine complex relationships among these observed factors. SEM combines elements of factor analysis and multiple regression analysis. SEM is not exploratory but more confirmatory based on assumed interactions and relationships. Unlike most regression models, SEM is also able to measure indirect effects by following paths in the model²³. The best fit SEM was developed by conducting many iterations of additions or subtractions of direct paths and covariances determined by model- result- information criteria, our understanding of phytoplankton ecology in Utah Lake, and by keeping paths and covariates that had low p-values. Maximum likelihood was used for parameter estimation.

Results

The best fit SEM model diagram is presented in Figure 23. Taxa and chemistry variables not shown in the model were determined to be unimportant and reduced the SEM fit (e.g., dP, NO₂, NO₃, NH₃). SEM equation level goodness of fit, direct, indirect, and total effects are in Appendix 14, Appendix 29, Appendix 31, and Appendix 32. This model had excellent equation fit; Wald tests χ^2 for all four cyanobacteria taxa p-values < 0.001, likelihood ratio baseline vs. saturated model χ^2 p-value < 0.001, and overall equation-level goodness of fit $R^2 = 0.91$.

²³ Estimating indirect effects is extremely important for understanding Utah Lake ecosystem function.

Figure 23. Best fit SEM of interactions between the most dominant cyanobacteria taxa, *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* APFL, *Dolichospermum circinalis* DOCI, *Oscillatoria* sp. OCSP, and *Phormidium* sp. PHRSP, the dominant dinophyte *Ceratium hirundinella* CEHI, the dominant chlorophyte *Chlamydomonas* sp. CHLSP, Ca, Mg, and Fe, total phosphorus (TP) and orthophosphate (OrthoP). All taxa biovolumes were sqrt transformed. Solid green lines are paths between cyanobacteria taxa. Solid black lines are paths between Fe, Ca, Mg, TP, OrthoP to phytoplankton taxa. Direction of arrow signifies directional effect. Double arrowed curved lines are covariates. Values are standardized coefficients. Negative sign in front of coefficients signifies negative relationships. All direct effect coefficients had low p-values. See appendices for direct, indirect, and total effects results.

There was good to strong evidence of positive and negative interactions between and among phytoplankton taxa and nutrients. *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI) and *Ceratium hirundinella* (CEHI) either coexisted or facilitated *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL), but facilitation was not reciprocal. *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL) seemed to positively affect *Oscillatoria* sp. (OCSP) but not the opposite. *Dolichospermum circinalis* was negatively associated with *Phormidium* sp. *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* facilitated *Oscillatoria* sp. but it was not reciprocal (Figure 23).

Aphanizomenon flosaquae was positively associated with Ca and negatively with OrthoP. *Oscillatoria* sp. was negatively associated with TP and positively associated with Mg but not the reverse. *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI) was positively associated with Ca, Mg, and TP and negatively associated with OrthoP. *Phormidium* sp. (PHRSP) was positively associated with Fe and negatively associated with Ca. *Ceratium hirundinella* (CEHI) was positively associated with Fe, TP, and OrthoP and negatively associated with Ca (Figure 23).

There were numerous indirect effects on *Aphanizomenon flosaquae*, *Oscillatoria* sp., and *Phormidium* sp., but none on *Dolichospermum circinalis*. *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* and *Oscillatoria* sp. even had indirect and total negative effects on themselves, possibly signifying self-regulation (Appendix 31 and Appendix 32).

These SEM results suggest that direct and indirect interspecific competition with themselves and for nutrients occurred, however, caution is needed to conclude competition at this time²⁴. The model also suggests strong correlations between Fe, Mg, and Ca (Figure 23) that have been documented elsewhere.

Corral and phosphorus treatment effects on dominant phytoplankton taxa

There was strong evidence that corrals themselves had the most effect on abundant phytoplankton taxa including *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL), *Dolichospermum circinalis* (DOCI), *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHLSP), *Cryptomonas* sp. (CRPTSP), pennate diatoms (PD), *Euglena* sp. (EUSP), and *Aulacoseira granulata* var. *angustissima* (AUGRA). However, phosphorus additions also had positive effects. All these taxa tended to be at least more abundant inside some of the treated corrals or control corrals than outside (Figure 24, Appendix 7).

Euglena sp. (EUSP) and *Aulacoseira granulata* var. *angustissima* (AUGRA) seemed to have benefitted the most from the first phosphorus addition but were not more abundant in the second treatment corrals or the control corrals from the lake.

Multilevel mixed effects regression results for these taxa are in Appendix 7. Only those taxa with significant results are presented. Date analyzed was after July 17 the start of the phosphorus addition treatment.

²⁴ Even though competition is one of the most well-known phenomena in community ecology, conclusively documenting competition continues to be a challenge to ecologists based on observational data because of other confounding factors including their shared evolutionary history. Well designed and controlled experiments are required to help determine competition.

Figure 24. Phytoplankton taxa biovolume in relation to phosphorus treatments and corrals vs. lake. Only those taxa with significant results are presented. Date analyzed was after July 17, start of treatment.

Periphyton

Attached algal growth that formed the periphyton²⁵ community on the bottom of corrals and on the sides of the corrals were abundant and, in some instances, luxurious particularly inside the

²⁵ A periphyton community is comprised of an autotrophic assemblage made up of diatoms, green algae, and cyanobacteria, and a heterotrophic assemblage consisting of bacteria, protozoa, fungi, and other microorganisms (Wijewardene et al. 2022). We mostly focus on the autotrophs in this section.

deeper open water corrals later in the season (August through October). Periphytic algae on the sides of corrals were observed to be denser with longer filaments on southern facing areas of the corrals.

Superficially the periphytic filamentous algae appeared to be composed of only one or two taxa however, on microscopic examination, its community was often diverse with many other algal taxa found within their filaments for a total of thirty taxa (Table 20 Table 22).

Table 20. Periphyton assemblage taxa found and codes

Taxon	Code	Division
<i>Actinastrum</i> species	ACSP	Chlorophyta
<i>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</i> (Corda) Ralfs	ANFA	Chlorophyta
<i>Aulacoseira distans</i> (Ehrenberg) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira distans</i>)	AUDI	Bacillariophyta
<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i> (Müller) Simonsen (= <i>Melosira granulata</i> var. <i>angustissima</i>)	AUGR	Bacillariophyta
centric diatoms species	CD	Bacillariophyta
<i>Chroococcus minor</i> (Kützing) Nägeli	CHMI	Cyanophyta
<i>Cladophora glomerata</i>	CLGL	Chlorophyta
<i>Closteriopsis longissima</i> var. <i>tropica</i> West & West	CLLO	Chlorophyta
<i>Closterium ehrenbergii</i> Meneghini ex Ralfs	CLEH	Chlorophyta
<i>Coelastrum</i> species	COSP	Chlorophyta
<i>Cosmarium</i> species	COSSP	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus bicellularis</i> (Chodat) An, Friedl & Hegewald	DEBI	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus communis</i> (Hegewald) Hegewald	DECO	Chlorophyta
<i>Desmodesmus opoliensis</i> (Richter) Hegewald	DEOP	Chlorophyta
<i>Geitlerinema</i> species	GESP	Cyanophyta
<i>Golenkinia</i> species	GOSP	Chlorophyta
<i>Kirchneriella</i> species	KISP	Chlorophyta
<i>Melosira varians</i> Agardh	MEVA	Bacillariophyta
<i>Micractinium pusillum</i> Fresenius	MIPU	Chlorophyta
<i>Monoraphidium</i> species	MOSP	Chlorophyta
<i>Oedogonium</i> species	OESP	Chlorophyta
<i>Oscillatoria princeps</i> Vaucher ex Gomont	OSPR	Cyanophyta
<i>Oscillatoria</i> species	OSSP	Cyanophyta
<i>Pectinodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Hegewald, Wolf, Keller, Friedl & Krienitz (= <i>Acutodesmus pectinatus</i> (Meyen) Tsarenko)	PEPE	Chlorophyta
pennate diatoms	PD	Bacillariophyta
<i>Phormidium</i> species	PHSP	Cyanophyta
<i>Phormidium</i> species 2	PHSP2	Cyanophyta
<i>Pleurosira laevis</i> (Ehrenberg) Compère (= <i>Biddulphia laevis</i> Ehrenberg)	PLLA	Euglenophyta
<i>Pseudanabaena</i> species	PSSP	Cyanophyta

<i>Snowella lacustris</i> (Chodat) Komárek & Hindák (= <i>Gomphosphaeria lacustris</i> Chodat)	SNLA	Cyanophyta
<i>Stephanodiscus niagarae</i> Ehrenberg	STNI	Bacillariophyta

Periphyton assemblages were dominated by just a few taxa including pennate diatoms (PD), *Cladophora glomerata* (CLGL), *Phormidium* sp. (PHSP) and a few others (Table 21).

Table 21. Periphyton relative abundances by biovolume

Taxa	Biovolume
PD	61
CLGL	37
PHSP	17
OESP	8
KISP	6
MEVA	6
OSSP	6
CD	5
AUGR	4
MOSP	4
CHMI	3
PHSP2	3
DECO	2
MIPU	2
PLLA	2
ACSP	1
ANFA	1
AUDI	1
CLEH	1
CLLO	1
COSP	1
COSSP	1
DEBI	1
DEOP	1
GOSP	1
OSPR	1
PEPE	1
PSSP	1
SNLA	1
STNI	1

The number of periphyton taxa varied by sample date and between phosphorus (P) treatments (Figure 25). The number of taxa was greatest on September 4 and there appeared to be more taxa in the P treated corral on September 4 and October 9 for the second round of P treatment (Figure 25) but we did not find statistical evidence, mostly because of limited number of samples.

Figure 25. Number of periphyton taxa by date and P treatment.

Periphyton biomass increased over the study period starting around September 4 (Figure 26, Appendix 33), and there appeared to be greater biomass in the P treated corral on August 15 and September 4 (Figure 26). However, we did not find statistical evidence for differences.

Figure 26. Periphyton biomass by date and P treatment.

The following table, Table 22 provides biomass summary statistics for each sample date and P treatment.

Table 22. Periphyton dry weight biomass (grams) summary statistics.

17-Jul						
treatment	N	mean	se(mean)	p50	p25	p75
Control	9	0.067	0.018	0.043	0.029	0.093

15-Aug						
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treatment	N	mean	se(mean)	p50	p25	p75
Control	6	0.160	0.039	0.185	0.067	0.228
P1	3	0.237	0.082	0.269	0.081	0.360
Total	9	0.185	0.037	0.200	0.081	0.268

4-Sep

treatment	N	mean	se(mean)	p50	p25	p75
Control	6	0.332	0.118	0.238	0.133	0.385
P1	3	0.606	0.327	0.290	0.267	1.260
Total	9	0.423	0.130	0.290	0.179	0.385

9-Oct

treatment	N	mean	se(mean)	p50	p25	p75
Control	3	0.495	0.139	0.495	0.254	0.737
P1	3	0.445	0.112	0.338	0.327	0.669
P2	3	0.457	0.255	0.238	0.168	0.966
Total	9	0.466	0.090	0.338	0.254	0.669

Discussion

Phytoplankton

The positive effects of limnocorrals on the phytoplankton assemblage clearly implicates wave induced turbidity, mostly in the form of sediment resuspension, as a leading impairment to Utah Lake's health. Bioturbation also continues to be a problem that needs to be rectified. All five commonly used diversity indices showed improved conditions inside the corrals. These metrics are widely used to monitor water quality and are well known indicators of biodiversity, i.e., health and integrity, that are already impaired in Utah Lake (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). These finding alone should send a signal to all Utah Lake management agencies tasked with protecting this ecosystem that the lake is impaired and in need of restoration. In addition, the effective number of taxa, ENT was only between roughly 2 and 3 or even fewer taxa on any given sample date (Table 19). This is very concerning. However, there was significant increase in ENT inside corrals showing that restoration will improve phytoplankton diversity. A more diverse, balanced, and phytoplankton rich assemblage in Utah Lake will help dampen the intensity and occurrences of harmful algal blooms and should be a main goal of restoration.

Extensive discussions were made on the phytoplankton assemblages in Utah Lake in relation to limnocorrals and ecosystem function in previous progress reports (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, and 2024). Results from this year's study adds to this knowledge. Readers are encouraged to review those past discussions. For example, one important finding from these studies is the oft overlooked dominant taxon, the dinoflagellate, *Ceratium hirundinella*. We discussed this species somewhat in the previous chapter on light attenuation (Chapter 3) and we discuss *C. hirundinella* in more detail in Appendix 35.

Diatoms are extremely important in lake ecosystems but were poorly represented in this study. However, pennate diatoms had greater abundances within coralls because of stable skirt substrate with which to attach. This demonstrated that pennate diatoms will likely increase in abundance and diversity as restoration stabilizes sediments and provides attachment habitat on increased aquatic vegetation (i.e., as epiphytes). Pennate diatoms in the form of epiphytes and periphyton will also allow for increased abundances of grazers including gastropods further improving ecosystem function (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). The loss of gastropod diversity and abundance in Utah Lake in the past century has contributed to its ecosystem shift and was discussed in previous reports.

The simple ratio of pennate diatom biovolume to centric diatom biovolume (PC/CD) can be used as an informative metric to help measure restoration. Figure 27 and Appendix 34 illustrate the use of this metric on our 2024 data. These show that the P/D ratio was less outside of coralls and differed by sampling date.

Figure 27. Pennate to centric diatom ratio (PD/CD) inside vs outside of coralls by date.

Three additional taxa from three different algal divisions were also indicators of conditions inside coralls, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Cryptomonas* sp., and *Dolichospermum circinalis* using indicator species analysis. Changes in their biovolumes via restoration that reduces wave action and sediment resuspension will likely directly or indirectly affect the food web and ecosystem processes. Their biovolumes and ecosystem effects need to be closely monitored as restoration progresses.

Although it seems unlikely that phosphorus levels in Utah Lake will increase as dramatically as was added as treatments in this study, we found no evidence that any of the dominant phytoplankton taxa increased in biovolume because of phosphorus additions. However, other interactions such as zooplankton grazing and competition with periphyton may have had indirect effects on these outcomes as we have shown in our previous progress reports.

It is now widely accepted that trace metals, such as Fe or Zn, can colimit phytoplankton growth (Hutchins & Bruland 1998; Takeda 1998; Hutchins *et al.* 2001; Quéguiner 2001; Leblanc *et al.* 2005) in addition to macronutrients, such as nitrate and phosphate, and light (Poggiale *et al.* 2010). Our findings included in this progress report and from our past progress reports further support this accepted idea. However, trace metals, other than Al, were not used as treatments in in this or in our past studies but are highly recommended for future mesocosm experiments, particularly Fe and Mg.

The structured equation model (SEM) presented in Figure 23 provided new insights into phytoplankton relationships including some indirect relationships. SEMs are data intensive and although useful for 2024, updated SEMs will provide much improved insights when all four years of data from our past studies are combined. Findings from this and our previous mesocosm studies can also be used in ecosystem function-food web models such as those developed by Richards and Miller (2004) that may prove invaluable for scientifically based restoration of Utah Lake.

Periphyton

Some periphyton taxa were also found in the water column as phytoplankton, and some were not, but were found in our previous mesocosm studies. This is likely the periphyton assemblage taxa base available for recolonization during and after restoration.

Growth of attached algae and the periphyton community on the insides, outsides, and bottoms of corrals but not in the lake demonstrated that suitable stable habitat for periphyton community establishment was nonexistent in Utah Lake within our study area. It also demonstrates that these types of algae simply need stable substrates in order to compete with water column phytoplankton for nutrients and to add additional trophic level complexity. In addition, all filamentous algal samples were laden with fine sediments, demonstrating that the autotrophic periphyton assemblages within the matrix not only compete with phytoplankton for nutrients but also filter large amounts of suspended sediments from the water column, an added benefit for improving water clarity, the food web, and ecosystem function (see Light Attenuation chapter). For a more detailed description of the importance of periphytic algal communities to food webs and ecosystem functioning see Vadeboncoeur and Steinman (2002), Wijewardene *et al.* (2022), and others in Literature Cited section.

Results from this study confirmed that wave and to a lesser extent carp induced turbidity, as well as planktivorous fish predation can have direct and indirect effects on phytoplankton and periphyton communities in Utah Lake. Our observed abundance of periphytic algae on the bottoms and sides of the corrals demonstrated that three limiting factors were altered, 1) limited light to the benthos, 2) chronic sediment resuspension, and 3) sediment stabilization. Restoration of these key factors alone will allow for a measurable transition from water column dominated primary production to benthic primary production and less nutrient availability to phytoplankton including HABs. Additional benthic periphyton benefits (*i.e.*, functions) are numerous and further described.

Benthic periphyton (algae) ecosystem functions include significant contributions to gross primary production (Velasco et al. 2003, Vadeboncoeur et al. 2002), trophic interactions (Moulten et al. 2004), ecosystem engineering (e.g., biostabilization of sediments; Dodds 2003; Droppo et al. 2007; Spears et al. 2007) and regulation of nutrient cycling across the sediment–water interface (Dodds 2003, Poulickova et al. 2008, Vadeboncoeur et al., 2003). Benthic algae are also vastly underappreciated contributors to pelagic fisheries (Vadeboncoeur et al. 2002) and increase retention of nutrients. According to Dodds (2003), periphyton can:

- Remove nutrients from the water column and cause a net flux of nutrients toward the sediments,
- slow water exchange across the sediment/water column boundary thus decreasing advective transport of P away from sediments,
- intercept nutrients diffusing from the benthic sediments or senescent macrophytes,
- cause biochemical conditions that favor P deposition and can,
- trap particulate material from the water column (Adey et al. 1993).

Vadeboncoeur and Steinman (2002) suggested that the balance between phytoplankton and periphyton primary production can be affected by differences in grazing pressure (e.g., zooplankton), habitat suitability, disturbance, and pelagic trophic structure (e.g., a balanced fishery). Benthic (epiphytic and periphytic) algae are still present in Utah Lake but are limited by a paucity of available stable substrate attachment surfaces. The vast majority of the lake’s substrate is a loose, unconsolidated mixture of silt, clay, and organic matter. Our study showed that benthic algae are present and on call waiting for stabilization of sediment habitat via restoration so that they can help balance the nutrient cycle and improve the lake’s food web. See Richards et al. (2022) for more discussion on periphyton importance. More intensive research on the periphytic and benthic algae assemblages of Utah Lake are needed, particularly for restoration purposes.

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Chapter 5: Zooplankton

“What we already know to be true: zooplankton are not fish, and nor are they phytoplankton”
Heneghan et al. (2016)

Introduction

Zooplankton are the key intermediary between phytoplankton primary production and fish assemblages. They are the main consumers of phytoplankton, can be omnivorous or predatory, and are prey of small fish including juvenile white bass, and even large adult carp in Utah Lake (Carlotti & Poggiale, 2010; Heneghan et al., 2016; Kiorboe, 2008; Lomartire et al., 2021; Mitra & Davis, 2010, Richards et al. this report, Richards et al. 2023, Richards and Miller 2024). Zooplankton are the epicenter of Utah Lake’s food web, trophic level energy transfer, nutrient cycling, and ecosystem function (Richards et al. 2023, Richards and Miller 2024, Heneghan et al. 2016). However, zooplankton are poorly studied by Utah Lake researchers and managers who tend to focus their attention on charismatic top predators (i.e., fish) or by water quality agencies that mostly focus on nutrients, phytoplankton, and HABs (Thorpe 2023, Richards et al. 2023).

Ecosystem effects of zooplankton grazing (and predation) are dependent on the taxonomic composition of the zooplankton assemblage and lake trophic state (Bess et al. 2021, Rollwagen-Bollens et al. 2013). The roles and importance of zooplankton taxa assemblage may diverge as primary production, including eutrophication or improved nutrient utilization via restoration, occurs in Utah Lake, as was suggested by Bess et al. 2021 for Lake Tahoe. Zooplankton can also change the structure of the phytoplankton community and the response of phytoplankton to variations in nutrients (Severiano et al. 2017). Also, the zooplankton assemblage in Utah Lake reflects current conditions of the non-analog trophic state discussed by us in this and previous reports. For example, prior to the extirpation of the native bivalve, *Anodonta* sp., the zooplankton assemblage was likely governed by this once abundant bivalve ecosystem engineer, and together they interacted to help control algal blooms and increase water quality (see Addendum at the end of this chapter). Consequently, it is now imperative to understand the biology, life history, and ecology of Utah Lake’s zooplankton assemblage that can rapidly change and adapt²⁶ to

²⁶ As we discussed in previous progress reports, the zooplankton assemblage in Utah Lake can only change or adapt given those taxa the now survive in the lake.

ecosystem shifts, if we are to scientifically manage Utah Lake and hope to put it on a path to recovery.

In this chapter, we present our findings on the zooplankton assemblages inside and outside of limnocorrals deployed in 2024 and factors that may have influenced these assemblages. We also highlight each individual zooplankton taxon responses to these factors emphasizing the fact that each taxon has its own ecological niche and will respond differently to stressors, improvements, and other changes within the food web.

Methods

Field

Zooplankton samples were collected from within all nine corrals and five lake sites on:

- June 18
- July 16
- July 29
- August 14
- August 27
- September 4
- September 23
- October 9.

We used a 64 μm mesh zooplankton net to collect zooplankton samples using a vertical tow from bottom to top of each of the corrals. Contents of net collection jars were gently sprayed using a spray bottle into sample jars. Care was taken to fill the sample jar to the brim and to keep jars upright to not allow zooplankton to dry on the sides or inside top of jar which can prevent accurate taxonomic identification. Water depth and net diameter were measured to determine zooplankton taxa counts per unit volume. The field team preserved samples to a final dilution of 70% isopropyl in properly labeled plastic sample jars and zooplankton samples were delivered to the River Continuum Concepts laboratory.

River Continuum Concepts, led by Mr. Brett Marshall, taxonomically analyzed samples, and wrote a brief summary report. The RCC lab and Oreohelix Ecological have developed the most accurate Utah Lake zooplankton taxonomic list to date derived from samples provided by Oreohelix Ecological and Wasatch Front Water Quality Council (Richards and Miller 2019). We consider RCC as the nation's most qualified lab for taxonomic identification of Utah Lake zooplankton.

Laboratory

Upon arrival at the lab, all samples were inventoried and logged into RCC's sample tracking database which assigned unique sample identifier numbers, site codes, dates, and replicate numbers. Samples were gently rinsed through a 63-micron stainless steel sieve and rinsed into a quadrant-splitter petri dish using 75% aqueous isopropanol. The contents of the splitting dish were mixed with a pipette until the distribution of animals within quadrants appeared roughly equivalent in abundance and size. If the sample contained significant detritus, it was separated

from the zooplankters under a dissecting microscope using the most effective magnification (10-100x) to ensure that no specimens were attached to the detritus removed. Once all the detritus was removed, we used a 4-sided die to randomly select one of the quadrants, which was transferred by pipette to a 6x6 gridded rectangular petri dish. Specimens were spread evenly across the gridded surface and two 6-sided dice were cast to determine which of the 36 grids was selected for identification. All specimens were removed from the selected grid and identified. After all the specimens from the first grid were removed, enumerated, and identified, another grid was randomly selected using the dice and the process was repeated until the total number of identified organisms exceeded 200 animals. If the first quarter was completely processed and the total number of animals remained below 200 animals, another quarter was randomly selected from the quadrant splitter dish using the four-sided die, and that quarter was transferred to the gridded dish and grids were randomly selected with pairs of six-sided dice. This process was repeated, when necessary, until the total number of animals exceeded 200 animals. The total number of specimens reported for a remained < 200 animals only for samples that were completely (100%) identified.

The subsample factor was used to estimate the total abundance of animals. The subsample factor is the reciprocal of the percent of the sample processed to attain 200 animals. Thus, if 10 grids were used from the first quarter of the sample, then the percentage of the sample used is 6.944% ($0.25 \times (10/36)$). In this case the total of 200 animals is corrected to density by dividing the sample abundance by 0.06944, resulting in an abundance of 2880 per sample ($200/0.06944$). The community density dataset applies this factor to each, and every species identified from the sample.

The fixed count method of processing zooplankton samples was selected because it provides timely and cost-effective analysis of the dominant species present and is used by state agencies as endorsed by the U.S. E.P.A. for biological assessment of lake zooplankton communities. However, there are some limitations to fixed count subsample methods, and those limitations become more relevant as the portion of the sample identified becomes very small (<~1%). Therefore, for this report, when densities are used, we are cautious when comparing the occurrence or non-occurrence of lower abundant taxa from samples that were heavily subsampled. The effects of subsampling must always be considered when conducting research and the level of subsampling needs to be balanced by the goals of the research and cost effectiveness. For example, in all instances when subsampling is conducted, absence of a taxon from a sample or location cannot be concluded. All biological sample methods used in 2024 were similar to previous methods and can be found in more detail in Richards et al. (2021).

Statistical Methods

Four to five letter codes were made for each zooplankton taxon, typically the first two letters of the genus name and the first two letters of the species name unless there were duplicates (Table 23). Seven to eight- digit location and sampling date codes were also developed for use in analyses.

Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMS) ordination was evaluated to compare zooplankton assemblage dis(similarity) relationships statistically and visually between corrals and dates. Ordination techniques are often more informative than hypothesis-testing approaches for

exploring relationships between multivariate ecological assemblages or communities (McCune and Grace 2002). In general, ordination is the ordering of objects along axes according to their (dis)similarities; the main objective of ordination is to reduce many-dimensional relationships into a small number of more easily interpretable dimensions (i.e., axes on a plot). The strongest correlation structure in the data is extracted and is then used to position objects in ordination space. Objects that are close in the ordination space are more similar than objects distant in ordination space (McCune and Mefford 2011).

NMS was evaluated in these analyses because it has been shown to be robust and highly informative for understanding ecological relationships. NMS ordination is often more broadly applicable for ecological studies than other ordination techniques because it does not require relationships among variables to be linear (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010). NMS ordination permits the visualization of the multidimensional relationships of phytoplankton assemblages into a more easily visualized, lower dimensional space. Dimensional reduction obviously creates some distortion in relationships between samples. The level of reduction in distortion is measured as 'stress', where lower stress values equal less distortion. NMS plots with stress values of 15% (0.15) or less are typically considered to be a good representation of the data and stress values lower than 10% (0.10) are considered excellent representations (McCune and Mefford 2011, Peck 2010).

Several distance measures were used and evaluated including Sorensen (Bray-Curtis), Relative Sorensen, Jaccard, Euclidean, Relative Euclidean, and Morisita-Horn. NMS analysis was run for 250 iterations using the real data and 250 iterations in randomized Monte Carlo simulations. Best-fit models were selected based on stable final stress < 0.15 and 3-dimensional solutions or fewer. NMS ordinations were rotated using varimax rotation to maximize variation along the axes and extracted as univariate scores. Consequently, the final ordinations can be rotated either vertically or horizontally without effecting the results. Centroid labels for sample dates were added to the ordinations to aid in the interpretation of the relationships. Post hoc proportion of variance represented by each axis was calculated based on the R^2 value between distance in the ordination space and distance in the original space.

Multiple Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP), a non-parametric multivariate method was used to formally test the hypothesis of no differences in zooplankton assemblages between sample dates and inside vs. outside of corrals. MRPP has the advantage of not requiring distributional assumptions such as multivariate normality and homogeneity of variance and thus is often preferred over perMANOVA for analyzing multivariate ecological data (McCune and Grace 2002). The same distance measure was used for each MRPP analyses as was for corresponding NMS models. The chance-corrected within-group test statistic, A (and associated p-value) was used to evaluate the hypothesis of no difference in groupings (McCune and Grace 2002). Post hoc multiple comparisons were also made when appropriate.

We used Indicator Species Analysis (ISA) in PC-ORD to determine zooplankton taxa that were strong indicators of sampling events (seasonal). ISA used Dufrêne and Legendre's (1997) method of calculating species indicator values that provided a simple, intuitive solution. The method combined information on biovolumes of phytoplankton taxa abundance for each sample event and the faithfulness of occurrence of a taxon in a particular sample event. ISA produced indicator

values for each taxon in each group. These were then tested for statistical significance using a randomization technique (Richards et al. 2004, McCune and Grace 2002 for more detailed information on ISA method).

All multivariate and several additional analyses including rank abundance and descriptive summary statistics were made using PC-ORD for Windows Version 7.08 (McCune and Mefford 2018) using Parallels Desktop 19.2.1 for Mac virtual platform.

Regression analyses were selected using the most appropriate model including linear, Poisson, fractional, and negative binomial. Candidate predictors (factors) were screened using Lasso regression. Lasso regression is a machine learning method that allows for selection of subsets of best fit models from many candidate factors. The final best fit regression models were then reevaluated from the lasso selected models and chosen based on lowest log likelihood, AIC, and BIC values. ANOVAs and MANOVAs were also conducted where appropriate. Descriptive statistics were also calculated for select data. Nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis equality of populations rank test were applied when data were not near normally distributed after transformation. Box and whisker plots were developed for non-normally distributed data. Box plots used median, 25th, 75th, lower and upper adjacent values and outside values. Statistical analyses and graphics were made using Stata 16.1 for Mac (Intel 64-bit) (StataCorp 2021). Graphical representations of statistical models were made using either Stata or PC-ORD. Details of additional statistical methods not listed here are described in individual Results sections.

Results

Taxa

Only seventeen zooplankton taxa were found during summer months and only five taxa dominated, *Acanthocyclops americanus*, *Daphnia retrocurva*, *Leptodiaptomus sicilis*, *Diaphanosoma cf. heberti*, and *Daphnia mendotae*. Table 23 lists species and their total abundances and number of occurrences. Appendix 36 contains summary statistics of each zooplankton taxon between inside and outside of corrals and by date.

Table 23. Zooplankton taxa found in mesocosm study 2024 from July 18 to October 9.

Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Taxon	Code	Total abundance	Number of occurrences
Arthropoda	Copepoda	Cyclopoida	Cyclopidae	<i>Acanthocyclops americanus</i>	ACAM	8551.97	112
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia retrocurva</i>	DARE	5111.01	112
Arthropoda	Copepoda	Calanoida	Diaptomidae	<i>Leptodiaptomus sicilis</i>	LESI	3373.38	109
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Sididae	<i>Diaphanosoma cf. heberti</i>	DIHE	2823.22	112
Arthropoda	Copepoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia mendotae</i>	DAME	574.58	100
Arthropoda	Copepoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Ceriodaphnia dubia</i>	CEDU	464.18	56
Arthropoda	Copepoda	Calanoida	Diaptomidae	<i>Leptodiaptomus siciloides</i>	LESC	180.62	38
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Leptodoridae	<i>Leptodora kindti</i>	LEKI	116.43	56
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Daphniidae	<i>Daphnia pulex</i> gr.	DAPU	98.48	34
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Chydoridae	<i>Coronatella cf. circumfimbriata</i>	COCI	28.82	6
Rotifera	Monogononta	Ploima	Brachionidae	<i>Keratella cochlearis</i>	KECO	16.30	4
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Moinidae	<i>Moina micrura</i>	MOMI	6.20	11
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Chydoridae	<i>Pleuroxus aduncus</i>	PLAD	4.27	4
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Chydoridae	<i>Chydorus brevilabrus</i>	CHBR	2.41	3
Arthropoda	Ostracoda			Ostracoda	OSTRA	3.12	1
Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida		Harpacticoida	HARP	2.81	4
Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Cladocera	Bosminiidae	<i>Bosmina longirostris</i> complex	BOLO	1.56	6

Assemblage level

An excellent NMS ordination of zooplankton assemblages mapped by sample date had a 3-dimensional solution, final stress = 7.01, final instability < 0.001, at 61 iterations. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.52$, Axis 2 $R^2 = 0.26$, and Axis 3 $R^2 = 0.18$. These ordination map showed the zooplankton assemblages dis(similarities) by sample date.

Figure 28. NMS ordination maps Axis 1 vs. Axis 2, and Axis 2 vs. Axis 3 of zooplankton assemblages by sample date. Axis 1 vs. Axis 3 not shown. Date in ordination map are centroid locations. Taxa code names are in Table 23.

Multiple Response Permutation Procedure (MRPP) provided strong evidence that the zooplankton assemblage differed between each sample date ($T = -5.07$, $A = 0.02$, $p = 0.001$) and differed inside corrals vs. outside corrals ($T = -35.48$, $A = 0.40$, $p < 0.001$). All MRPP post hoc pairwise comparisons of zooplankton assemblages strongly differed between sample dates ($p < 0.001$) except for June 18 vs. July 29 and July 16 vs. August 14 ($p = 1.00$).

Indicator species analysis found several taxa as strong indicators of sample date(s) and inside vs outside of corrals (Table 24).

Table 24. Indicator species analysis for zooplankton assemblages by sample date and inside vs. outside. Taxa names are in Table 23.

Taxon	Sample Date	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	IV from randomized groups		
			Mean	S. Dev	p
DAPU	18-Jun	47	10.8	3.27	0.0002
CEDU	18-Jun	29	14.5	3.69	0.004
ACAM	27-Aug	57.5	21.6	3.49	0.0002
COCI	27-Aug	26.5	9.3	4.59	0.001
KECO	27-Aug	12.5	6	3.86	0.06
LESI	4-Sep	28.6	18	2.23	0.001
LEKI	4-Sep	33.1	14.5	3.71	0.001
LESC	9-Oct	31.3	12.6	4.06	0.001
Inside vs Outside					
DAME	Inside	63.1	49.7	3.89	0.004
DIHE	Outside	62.9	53.2	2.53	0.001
MOMI	Outside	15.3	8.2	2.70	0.02

Total zooplankton abundance (density) was highest on the August 27 sample date and coincided with an algal bloom (Figure 29). We found strong evidence that total zooplankton densities were greater in the lake than inside corrals before September 4 (ANOVA $F = 13.95$, $p < 0.01$) but then may have been greater inside corrals than in the lake after August 27, although there was no statistical support for this observation (ANOVA $F = 0.72$, $p = 0.40$)(Figure 29).

Figure 29. Total zooplankton abundance (density L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, by P-treatment, and by date sampled (upper figure). Control=corrals without P treatment, P1 = corrals with P treatment on July 19 and P2 = corrals with P treatment on September 11 and \log_{10} transformed total zooplankton inside vs outside corrals before Sept4 and after Aug27 (lower figures).

The only predictors of zooplankton abundance in our best fit regression model were date sampled and pennate diatoms (Appendix 39). Zooplankton abundances were significantly greatest on August 27 and were negatively correlated with pennate diatom biovolume (also see MRPP results). Zooplankton abundances were positively associated with phytoplankton biovolumes but not significantly. Overall, zooplankton abundance was not predicted well by any of the chemistry or phytoplankton variables nor our best fit model ($R^2 = 0.42$).

Richness and Diversity

Taxa richness (number of taxa), effective number of taxa (ENT), evenness, and Shannon and Simpson Diversity indices were calculated for each corral treatment and by sample date and are presented in the following figures.

Figure 30. Zooplankton richness and diversity indices inside and outside corrals (Lake), P treatment and sample date. P treatments were on July 19 (P1) and September 11 (P2). Control = corral without P treatment. Outliers labeled by corral and lake location.

We consider the effective number of taxa (ENT) to be a better measure of richness than taxa richness because of the dominance of fewer taxa interacting in the environment. Mean ENT was greater inside corrals than in the lake from June 18 through September 23 (Appendix 37) and we found statistical evidence to support that ENT was greater inside corrals than in the lake on August 27 (ANOVA $F = 4.11$, $p = 0.07$) and September 4 (ANOVA $F = 4.70$, $p = 0.05$).

Mean Shannon diversity was greater inside corrals than in the lake June 18 through September 23 (Appendix 37) but we only found statistical evidence to support this on August 27 (ANOVA $F = 4.43$, $p = 0.06$) and September 4 (ANOVA $F = 5.03$, $p = 0.04$). Similar results were found for Simpson Diversity. We didn't find evidence of differences in evenness between corrals and the lake.

Individual Taxa

Because there were only seventeen zooplankton taxa found in our 2024 study and only a handful dominated, we elected to evaluate each major taxon individually. We strongly advocate that it is more important to understand each individual taxon's biology, ecology, and occurrences in Utah Lake than by lumping zooplankton into less informative groupings such as copepods, cladocerans, and rotifers. Critical information is lost by lumping taxa, often resulting in erroneous conclusions.

Three species of daphnids occurred in our 2024 study, *Daphnia retrocurva*, *D. mendotae* and *D. pulex* gr. in order of abundances from 2, 5, and 9 (Table 23).

Daphnia retrocurva (DARE) was the most abundant daphnid in our samples and was most abundant in mid-summer (Figure 31). It was also the second most abundant taxon overall (Table 23). *Daphnia retrocurva* was more abundant in the lake than inside corrals on June 18 (ANOVA $F = 11.39$, $p = 0.01$) and on July 29 (ANOVA $F = 11.39$, $p = 0.01$) but there was no evidence that abundances differed between the lake and inside corrals on the other sampling dates. There were, however, sampling date differences.

Figure 31. *Daphnia retrocurva* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Starting in mid-August, *D. mendotae* (DAME) (also known as *D. galeata mendota* a north American subspecies of *D. galeata*) occurred in greater abundances inside corrals than in Utah Lake on most sample dates (Figure 32).

Figure 32. *Daphnia mendotae* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Table 25. *Daphnia mendotae* (DAME) (sqrt transformed) ANOVA inside corrals vs lake by date. Only significant results are presented.

	Corral vs. Lake	F	p
June 18	L > C	8.69	0.01
July 16	C > L	7.14	0.02
July 29	L > C	8.69	0.01
August 14	C > L	7.14	0.02
August 27	C > L	4.12	0.07
September 4	C > L	32.10	< 0.01

Daphnia pulex gr. (DAPU) mostly occurred earlier in the season and we found no differences in abundances between inside or outside of corrals. *Daphnia pulex* gr. occurred in very low densities in August 14 samples and was almost nonexistent after that date (Figure 33).

Figure 33. *Daphnia pulex* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Diaphanosoma cf. heberti (DIHE) abundances fluctuated throughout the study and was most often more abundant in the lake than within the corrals before August 27 (Figure 34). Phosphorus treatments may have resulted in increased abundances of *D. heberti* (Figure 34).

Figure 34. *Diaphanosoma cf. heberti* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Table 26. *Diaphanosoma cf. heberti* (DIHE) (sqrt transformed) ANOVA inside corrals vs lake by date. Only significant results are presented.

Date	Corral vs Lake	F	p
June 18	L > C	14.07	0.003
July 16	L > C	21.90	< 0.001
July 29	L > C	14.07	0.003

August 14	L > C	21.90	< 0.001
October 9	C > L	4.01	0.07

Ceriodaphnia dubia (CEDU) abundances fluctuated between sample dates and decreased after August 27 (Figure 35). There was no evidence that its abundances differed between the lake and inside corrals except on September 23 (ANOVA $F = 6.71$, $p = 0.02$) or October 9 (ANOVA $F = 3.72$, $p = 0.07$).

Figure 35. *Ceriodaphnia dubia* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Coronatella cf. circumfimbriata (COCI) occurred in very low abundance inside corrals on August 27 and was near absent during the other sample events (Figure 36).

Figure 36. *Coronatella cf. circumfimbriata* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Moina micrura (MOMI) occurred in corrals including phosphorus treated corrals until August 14. We did not find it in any lake samples (Figure 37).

Figure 37. *Moina micrura* abundances (densities L⁻¹) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Pleuroxus aduncus (PLAD) was rare in our samples and only occurred in a few corrals including P treated corrals (Figure 38).

Figure 38. *Pleuroxus aduncus* abundances (densities L⁻¹) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Bosmina longirostris complex (BOLO) was also uncommon (lowest abundance, 6 samples) in our study in 2024.

Acanthocyclops americanus (ACAM) was the most abundant zooplankton taxon in our study (Table 23). This species is an omnivore/predator and can have large impacts on aquatic ecosystems including Utah Lake (García et al. 2011). Sarma et al. (2019) found gut contents of field-collected adult *Acanthocyclops* contained filamentous algae and cyanobacteria and 16 zooplankton species including species that occur in Utah Lake. Its dominance supports our findings that Utah Lake ecosystem is out of balance. A brief life history summary can be found in appendix.

Acanthocyclops americanus population abundance peaked during our August 27 sample date during an algal bloom (Figure 39) and fluctuated in abundances between corrals and the lake (Table 27).

Figure 39. *Acanthocyclops americanus* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Table 27. *Acanthocyclops americanus* ACAM (log transformed) ANOVA inside vs lake. Corral vs. Lake Bonferroni multiple comparison tests.

	Corral vs Lake	F	p
June 18	L > C	11.84	0.01
July 16	C > L	21.01	< 0.01
July 29	L > C	6.25	0.03
August 14	C > L	13.38	< 0.01
August 27	C = L	2.98	0.11
September 4	C > L	8.80	0.01
September 23	C = L	0.16	0.70
October 9	C > L	5.41	0.04

Acanthocyclops americanus apparently interacted with other factors including pennate diatoms (PD), *Leptodiatomus siciloides* (LESC), dissolve oxygen, *Bosmina longirostris* complex (BOLO), *Ceratium hirundinella* CEHI, *Daphnia mendotae* (DAME), *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHLSP), Mg, NH_3 , *Oocystis borgei* (OOBO), and *Trachelomonas* sp.(TRSP) (Appendix 43).

Leptodiptomus sicilis (LESI) and *L. siciloides* (LESC) abundances exhibited either present or past competition. Their abundances were negatively correlated with each other over the study period.

Figure 40. *Leptodiptomus sicilis* (LESI) inside and outside of corrals, phosphorus treatments, and by sample date. P1 = first P treatment, P2 = second P treatment, outliers are labeled by corral.

Table 28. *Leptodiptomus sicilis* (LESI) (sqrt transformed) ANOVA post hoc Bonferroni multiple comparison tests by date inside vs outside of corrals. Only significant results are presented.

Date	Corral vs. Lake	F	p
June 18	Lake > Corrals	16.45	0.002
July 16	Lake > Corrals	13.14	0.004
July 29	Lake > Corrals	16.45	0.002
August 14	Lake > Corrals	13.14	0.004

Figure 41. *Leptodiptomus sicilis* and *L. siciloides* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of corrals by date sampled.

Leptodora kindti (LEKI) is the top predacious zooplankter in Utah Lake. It is highly transparent and a stealth predator. *Leptodora kindti* occurred in low abundances but was most abundant in our August 27 and September 4 samples (Figure 42) when total zooplankton abundances were highest (Figure 29).

Figure 42, *Leptodora kindti* abundances (densities L^{-1}) inside and outside of coralls by date sampled

Keratella cochlearis (KECO) was the only rotifer in our samples and was rare and uncommon after mid-July. This could have been due to predation from other zooplankters including *Acanthocyclops americanus* or other factors that need to be examined. Rotifer absence and rarity in our samples is of concern.

Zooplankton and P treatments

The second P treatment conducted on September 11 appeared to have allowed zooplankton to increase in abundance as a result of increased primary production (phytoplankton)(Figure 43, Appendix 42). However, lake zooplankton abundance also increased, although we could not find any statistical support for this finding likely due to large variability in spatial and temporal zooplankton abundances in coralls and lake, limited sample size, and lab sub sorting method effects (see Methods section).

Figure 43. Total zooplankton abundances (L^{-1}) by treatments from July 29 to October 9. The first phosphorus treatment was conducted on July 19 in corrals P1. The second phosphorus treatment was conducted on September 11 in corrals P2.

Phytoplankton- Zooplankton Interactions

Interactions between the primary producers, phytoplankton and their main consumers, zooplankton are highly complex. Many factors can affect these interactions including chemistry, plankton relative abundances, plankton life histories, other functional traits, and even units of measurement in a study. We have shown that chemistry and phytoplankton assemblages differed between inside and outside of corrals that certainly affected phyto-zooplankton interactions. Also, zooplankton diets are often plastic and adaptable (see past progress reports). In this study, *Daphnia mendotae* was an indicator of conditions inside corrals and is considered a herbivore (i.e. phytoplankton), whereas *A. americanus*, the most abundant zooplankter in our study, is an omnivore sometimes predator. In addition, we reported zooplankton as densities, whereas phytoplankton as biovolume. *Daphnia mendotae* is roughly 2 x longer than *A. americanus*. We have initiated a zooplankton function traits table that can be used to better understand interactions and ecosystem function. See functional traits table in Appendix 38.

That being said, we found some informative relations between phytoplankton and zooplankton. Before August 27, there did not appear to be a direct relation between phytoplankton biovolume (\log_{10} transformed) and zooplankton densities (\log_{10} transformed) (Figure 44). Phytoplankton biovolume and zooplankton densities appeared to fluctuate independently. After August 27, when phytoplankton biovolumes began to decrease there was a strong positive relation between phytoplankton biovolume and zooplankton densities, that is, as phytoplankton biovolumes decreased so did zooplankton densities (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Linear regression results of zooplankton densities as a function of phytoplankton biovolumes before August 27 and after August 27.

However, throughout the study, zooplankton densities were directly related to phytoplankton biovolumes inside corrals but not outside of corrals in the lake (Figure 45). It appears that the zooplankton assemblage was more in tune with the phytoplankton assemblage inside the corrals than in the lake. As we have shown in the phytoplankton chapter, phytoplankton assemblages differed between inside and outside of corrals, as did zooplankton assemblages (this chapter).

Figure 45. Linear regression results of zooplankton densities as a function of phytoplankton biovolumes inside corrals and outside of corrals.

Zooplankton densities were not related to any specific phytoplankton taxon inside the corrals, however, densities outside the corral, in the lake, zooplankton densities were strongly related to several phytoplankton taxa (Appendix 45). Zooplankton densities in the lake were negatively related to *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (APFL), *Chlamydomonas* sp. (CHLSP), and *Euglena* sp. (EUSP), and positively related to *Ceratium hirundinella* (CEHI), pennate diatoms (PD), and *Closteriopsis longissima* (CLLO) (Appendix 45).

Simultaneous quantile regression of zooplankton densities (\log_{10} transformed) vs. phytoplankton biovolumes (\log_{10} transformed) showed that inside corrals there was a strong positive relation between zooplankton densities and phytoplankton biovolumes up until about 4.1×10^7 (95% CIs 2.9×10^7 , 5.4×10^7) $\mu\text{m}^3 \text{mL}^{-1}$ (Appendix 44). It appears that above these phytoplankton biovolumes, zooplankton were unable to control phytoplankton blooms. Contrarily, and as

illustrated in Figure 45, there was no relation between zooplankton densities and phytoplankton biovolumes in the lake using quantile regression (Appendix 44).

To further explore zooplankton-phytoplankton relationships, we then developed a structural equation model (SEM) examining relations between dominant phytoplankton and dominant zooplankton (Figure 46). We used the same methods as was done for the phytoplankton-chemistry interaction SEM shown in Figure 23 in the previous chapter on phytoplankton. The overall zooplankton interactions SEM equation level goodness of fit $R^2 = 0.75$.

As illustrated in the following SEM diagram, most interactions were one-way, effects of zooplankton on phytoplankton or on each other. The only interaction where phytoplankton taxa influenced zooplankton was *Phormidium* sp. (PHRSP) negatively affecting *Diaphanosoma* cf. *heberti* (DIHE).

Figure 46. Best fit SEM of interactions between the most dominant phytoplankton taxa, *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* APFL, *Dolichospermum circinalis* DOCI, *Phormidium* sp. PHRSP, and *Ceratium hirundinella* CEHI with the dominant zooplankton taxa *Ceriodaphnia dubia* CEDU, *Daphnia retrocurva* DARE, *Acanthocyclops americanus* ACAM, *Diaphanosoma* cf. *heberti* DIHE, *Leptodiatomus sicilis* LESI, and *Daphnia galeata mendotae* DAME. The model was based on either sqrt or log transformed data. Direction of arrow signifies directional effect. Values are standardized coefficients. Negative sign in front of coefficients signifies negative relationships. All direct effect coefficients had low p-values. See appendices for direct, indirect, and total effects results.

The SEM structural model, indirect effects, and total effects results are in Appendix 46 and Appendix 47. This SEM model was only based on limited 2024 mesocosm results. A more informed SEM can be made with all years of study data combined.

Discussion

Results from the 2024 study presented here support our past findings that reducing turbation can have significant effects on the zooplankton assemblage in Utah Lake. These findings are important additions to our accumulating scientific knowledge of the lake's food web and ecosystem function and are invaluable for holistic, science-based restoration of Utah Lake. However, we need to combine all years of our mesocosm studies with other research to get a better understanding of the ecosystem and the effects of reduced sediment resuspension and nutrients.

The zooplankton assemblage is not only a function of the effects of recent conditions (bottom-up control), but they also contribute (top-down control). That is, food web interactions are fully two-way: zooplankton both influence and are influenced directly by primary producers and tertiary consumers. In addition, we suggest that zooplankton will likely respond differently to environmental changes, including restoration than higher trophic levels in the food web (Benedetti et al., 2018).

By reducing turbation via restoration efforts including macrophyte establishment in the littoral zone, mollusk reintroduction and establishment, and focused mechanical sediment stabilization or removal, zooplankton assemblage composition will likely rapidly change restricted by the taxa that continue to exist in the lake. Some of the uncommon taxa may be released from competition and environmental constraints and subsequently become more important to ecosystem function. Thus, our zooplankton data base that continues to be expanded will provide invaluable to evaluate changes in assemblage structure and function. Phosphorus additions didn't appear to alter the zooplankton assemblage, indicating that Utah Lake underutilizes nutrients in its degraded condition. This also points out the challenges of statistical inference based on sample size alone. Smaller limnocorrals (e.g., 10-gallon aquaria) with more replication would have allowed for better statistical inference but would have been less representative of the lake environment.

As we discussed in our previous progress reports, functional traits are important, and additional traits need to be generated and analyzed to best manage Utah Lake. There was limited functional trait values available from the literature on zooplankton species in Utah Lake. An initial functional traits table is presented in Appendix 38 that needs to be populated.

Results from this 2024 study, along with past limnocorral studies, can be used to improve ecosystem models such as SEMs developed in this report. Additionally, they can be applied to models like EcoPath with EcoSim by Richards and Miller (2024), the StrathE2E2 food web model (Heath et al., 2020, 2021), or through management strategy evaluation (MSE) methods (Mackinson et al., 2018; Punt et al., 2016; Thorpe & De Oliveira, 2019). These models can help test management strategies and assess robustness to uncertainties, including the significant, but unquantified, role of zooplankton in Utah Lake's food web.

Conclusion

Despite our comprehensive studies on Utah Lake's zooplankton assemblage, the assemblage remains poorly understood and inadequately monitored. Our 2024 mesocosm research, along

with four years of prior studies, investigated potential restoration strategies through reduced turbation and nutrient manipulation regarding the role of zooplankton assemblages and individual species in the lake's food web and ecosystem function. These studies represent the most thorough zooplankton analysis conducted to date for Utah Lake. However, the scope and spatial extent of our studies were limited, highlighting an urgent need to enhance our understanding of the role of zooplankton in Utah Lake's food web dynamics and ecosystem function. This necessitates a robust and consistent sampling program that includes species-level taxonomy, comprehensive literature reviews, coordinated experimental investigation, and modeling studies (sensu Merico et al. 2009, Thorpe 2023).

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Addendum: The importance of zooplankton and bivalve interactions in Utah Lake

We briefly evaluated and discussed at length the effects of bivalves on ecosystem function in our past mesocosm experiments that had limited replication due to management concerns. We emphasized that the reintroduction of native bivalves, particularly *Anodonta* sp. was imperative if we are to restore Utah Lake to a healthier functioning ecosystem. We cited many studies that demonstrated the positive effects of these ecosystem engineers (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024).

A recent publication in a premier aquatic ecology scientific journal, *Hydrobiologia* solidifies the importance of bivalves, “Freshwater mussels can enhance zooplankton size and their grazing potential on phytoplankton with implications for water clarity in tropical eutrophic shallow lakes” (Xie 2025). These researchers found that bivalves in mesocosm experiments:

- decreased phytoplankton abundance,
- decreased microphytoplankton and nanophytoplankton Chl a,
- increased the biomass of large zooplankton (cladocerans and copepods, but not the smaller rotifers),
- altered the zooplankton community structure,
- increased the biomass ratios of total zooplankton, rotifers, cladocerans, and copepods to phytoplankton,
- decreased total suspended solid concentrations, and
- enhanced light intensity on the sediment surface with a subsequent increase in benthic algae Chl a, while the nutrient concentrations remained unchanged.

We cannot emphasize enough how important it is to holistically restore missing components of Utah Lake that not only includes benthic algae and macrophyte restoration but also bivalve reintroduction and that in doing so, synergistic, positive feedback loops will prevail.

Chapter 6: Benthic Invertebrates

Introduction

Starting about 150 years ago, benthic invertebrate assemblages partially filled vacant functional roles in Utah Lake's degraded trophic state after the extirpation of keystone ecosystem engineering mollusks, near extirpation of macrophytes, transition to a non-native, non-analog fisheries, and the resultant ecosystem shift to a lower trophic state. Benthic conditions shifted from substrates stabilized by bivalves, macrophytes, and benthic algae to a mostly easily disturbed, unconsolidated mud-clay-silt substrate that occupies most of the top layers of the lake substrate today. The dominant benthic invertebrates in Utah Lake presently consist of just a handful of taxa, predominantly pollution tolerant chironomid (midge) larvae, segmented worms (oligochaetes and lumbricids), and non-segmented (nematode) worms, except for a few isolated locations where macrophytes exist in the littoral zone (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). As a result, much of the lake exists as profundal zone and can be considered chronically impaired with a cumulative Invertebrate Tolerance Index of 9.85 indicating a water quality rating of very poor (Richards 2022). Out of approximately twenty macroinvertebrate taxa reported by Richards and Miller (2019) evaluated from 93 benthic samples, only three taxa dominated the invertebrate biomass, larval *Chironomus* sp. (midge), larval *Tanypus* sp. (midge), and oligochaete worms. These three pollution tolerant indicators comprised 99% of the biomass (Richards and Miller 2019) and for the most part continue to do so, although it appears that midge larvae densities in the lake can fluctuate greatly from year to year and may be decreasing (Richards and Miller 2019, and this progress report). However, some areas of the lake including areas in Provo Bay and the limited macrophyte habitats outside of the bay have greater benthic invertebrate diversity (Landom and Walsworth 2021, 2023). These findings show that restoring macrophytes and benthic periphyton communities can have important improvements on ecosystem function that include reestablishment of diverse invertebrate assemblages.

Goal

The limnocorral study 2024 goal was to further understand and document changes to benthic invertebrate assemblages by comparing the assemblages 1) inside corrals, 2) outside of corrals in the lake, and 3) periphyton communities growing on the inside of corral skirts.

Methods

Benthic Invertebrate Sampling, Processing, and Taxonomic Identification

A total of 58 benthic invertebrate samples were collected, processed, and taxonomically identified. Sampled on:

- July 16
- August 13
- September 3
- October 8

Samples were collected using a petite Ponar grab (Figure 47) with area = 0.023 m² deployed from the side of the TSSD boat.

Figure 47 Petite Ponar grab similar to the one used in our study, 2023.

When sampling from within a corral, the Ponar grab was suspended above the water, laterally as far from the edge of corral as possible (about 1m). After the grab reached the bottom, it was pulled vertically on the rope/chain until the jaws set closed. If the sampler did not completely seal, it was rinsed with filtered field water and redeployed elsewhere until we attained a good seal/sample. Once a properly sealed sample was attained, it was rinsed in in a 500-micron sieve bucket until the silt and clays were purged from the sample. Samples were then preserved in new labeled jars with 99% isopropanol.

Periphyton samples were collected from inside of corral skirts using a p-cup scrape. One scrape was collected in September and one in October from Corral 5. Periphyton samples were collected by inverting a 55 mm diameter (86.4 mm² area) plastic jar (P-cup) over the inside of a south facing skirt panel and scraping all periphyton into jar. Biomass samples were corrected for total solids (TSS, TDS (unfiltered)) of a 120 ml sample of limnocorral lake water contained in the sample (the same total volume of the periphyton scrapes). Biomass estimates were made following RCC methods. Biomass samples were dried at 60° C for 48 hrs. and then weighed. Taxonomy was to lowest practical taxon, typically genus or species.

It is important to remember that periphyton scrapes were opportunistic samples because our study was not focused on periphyton invertebrates. However, their collection turned out to be invaluable to our study.

Processing and Taxonomy

In the laboratory, benthic samples were washed gently with tap water into a nested sieve system of 350-microns over a 1000-micron sieve; the larger sieve contents were used for taxonomy, and the smaller-mesh sieve's contents were preserved and retained for posterity in case they are needed later. This followed the trend using larger mesh-sizes for processing muddy samples from wetlands (e.g., Barba 2010), where silt and clay balls hinder sorting under microscopy by perpetually fouling/clouding the preservative—greatly reducing visibility. The larger mesh size

greatly reduces sorting time, the contribution of smaller animals, and the number of ambiguously identified immature animals—to order or family-level—but may result in slightly lower richness estimates (e.g., Hartwell and Fukiyama 2015).

Using the larger sieve portion also prevented our methods from obfuscating important trends in the larger invertebrates responsible for bioturbation (which may play an important role in ameliorating toxic cyanobacteria blooms). Using fixed-count subsampling protocols (e.g., Plafkin et al. 1989, Barbour et al. 1999), which are primarily influenced from high-abundance tiny invertebrates (e.g., nematodes, rotifers etc.), excludes less-ephemeral taxa from the data set (e.g., Marshall 2018, Marshall in prep), numerically excluding the larger invertebrates. This method resulted in zero subsampling for most samples and those that were subsampled (4/54) used a large portion of the sample required most of the sample to be processed. Thus, this method greatly increased the similarity of unit-effort for density determinations among different corrals and treatments.

Zooplankton were removed from benthos and included in the data sets, (mostly *Daphnia*), but were not used toward the subsample target of >200-animals per sample. Additionally, zooplankton collected with benthos were not included in the broader analyses because they were addressed in their own section as plankton. Taxonomy followed the guides of Merritt et al. (2019), Thorpe and Rogers (2016), Anderson et al. (2013) and Epler (2001)—except zooplankton, which followed the consensus taxonomy described earlier.

Statistical Analyses

Statistical analyses were similar to those used in our phytoplankton and zooplankton chapters.

Results

Sixteen macroinvertebrate taxa and six zooplankton taxa were collected and identified (Table 29). Most were chironomid taxa (N = 10).

Table 29. List of macroinvertebrate and zooplankton taxa collected benthic and periphyton samples in 2024.

Family Level or Higher	Taxon	Code
Chironomidae	<i>Procladius</i> sp.	PRSP
Chironomidae	<i>Cricotopus sylvestris</i> grp.	CRSY
Chironomidae	<i>Chironomus crassicaudatus</i>	CHCR
Chironomidae	<i>Chironomus decorus</i> grp. spp.	CHDE
Chironomidae	<i>Cryptochironomus</i> sp.	CRSP
Chironomidae	<i>Polypedilum halterale</i> grp.	POHA
Chironomidae	<i>Glyptotendipes</i>	GLSP
Chironomidae	<i>Parachironomus</i> sp.	PASP
Chironomidae	<i>Cryptotendipes</i> sp.	CRSP
Chironomidae	<i>Cladotanytarsus</i> sp.	CLSP
Nematoda/Nemata	Nematoda/Nemata	NEMA
Oligochaeta	Oligochaeta	OLIGO

Lumbricidae	<i>Eiseniella</i> sp.	EISP
Bivalvia	<i>Corbicula</i> sp.	COFL
Acari	Acari	ACARI
Ostracoda	Ostracoda	OSTR
Zooplankton		
Copepoda	<i>Acanthocyclops americanus</i>	ACAM
Cladocera	<i>Daphnia gaelata mendotae</i>	DAGA
Cladocera	<i>Daphnia retrocurva</i>	DARE
Cladocera	<i>Daphnia pulex</i> gr.	DAPU
Cladocera	<i>Diaphanosoma</i> cf. <i>heberti</i>	DIHE
Cladocera	<i>Leptodora kindtii</i>	LEKI

Benthic Invertebrate Assemblages

Our best fit NMS ordination used a Relative Sorenson's distance matrix. The NMS ordination was a 2-dimensional solution with a final stress = 9.75, final instability < 0.001, at 30 iterations. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.54$ and Axis 2 $R^2 = 0.38$. Cumulative $R^2 = 0.92$.

Figure 48. NMS ordination for benthic and periphyton invertebrate assemblages. Axis 1 $R^2 = 0.54$, Axis 2 $R^2 = 0.38$.

The NMS ordination (Figure 48) showed the large dissimilarity between the periphyton benthic invertebrate assemblage and inside corral benthos and lake benthos. It also showed to a lesser extent the dis(similarity) between inside and outside corral benthos.

MRPP provide strong evidence that the benthic invertebrate assemblages differed between sample dates and between inside vs. outside vs. periphyton (Table 30).

Table 30. Multiple response permutation procedure test of differences between benthic invertebrate assemblages inside vs. outside corals vs. periphyton assemblages, and between sample dates. *T* = test statistic, *A* = chance-corrected within-group agreement, *p* = probability of smaller or equal delta.

	T	A	p
Inside vs. outside vs. periphyton	-8.18	0.11	0.05
Sample dates	-12.64	0.18	< 0.001

Post hoc pairwise comparisons. Note: p values not corrected for multiple comparisons.

Sample Dates

Dates compared	T	A	p
16-Jul vs. 13-Aug	-8.90	0.14	< 0.001
16-Jul vs. 3-Sep	-4.91	0.07	< 0.001
16-Jul vs. 8-Oct	-8.02	0.15	< 0.001
13-Aug vs. 3-Sep	-9.90	0.19	< 0.001
13-Aug vs. 8-Oct	-3.93	0.07	0.01
3-Sep vs. 8-Oct	-7.21	0.15	< 0.001

Locations

Locations Compared	T	A	p
Out vs. In	-7.63	0.07	< 0.001
Out vs. Periphyton	-5.09	0.15	< 0.001
In vs. Periphyton	-4.49	0.07	< 0.001

Figure 49 shows differences in invertebrate taxa densities by sample date and inside vs. outside vs. periphyton locations.

Figure 49. Box plots of invertebrate taxa densities m^{-2} by sample date and inside corral substrate vs. outside corral substrate vs periphyton growing on insides of corals. Peri = periphyton invertebrates. Note: Total densities are \log_{10} transformed.

Densities

We did not find any evidence that benthic invertebrate assemblage densities differed between inside and outside of corrals (Table 31a). However, there was strong evidence that densities were greater in the periphyton community (Table 31b).

Table 31. T-test and ANOVA density m^{-2} (\log_{10} transformed) comparisons between locations.

a. T-test comparing densities (\log_{10} transformed) between inside and outside macroinvertebrate assemblages.

N-inside	N-outside	Mean-inside	Mean-outside	dif	St Err	t value	p value
36	20	3.47	3.48	-.001	.011	-.05	.94

b. ANOVA comparing densities (\log_{10} transformed) between inside, outside, and periphyton macroinvertebrate assemblages.

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	6.00	2	3.00	17.98	< 0.01
Within groups	9.18	55	0.17		
Total	15.18	57		0.27	

Several summary statistics of overall densities and densities by taxon are in Appendix 48 and Appendix 49.

Indicator Species

Two species of chironomids were indicators of the benthic substrate community inside corrals, *Cladotanytarsus* sp. and *Glyptotendipes* sp. One species of lumbricid worm, *Eiseniella* sp. was an indicator of the benthic substrate community outside of corrals in the lake. Six taxa were indicators of the periphyton community within the periphyton growing on the insides of corrals, *Glyptotendipes* sp., *Cricotopus sylvestris* grp., *Parachironomus* sp., Oligochaeta, Naididae, and Ostracoda (Table 32).

Table 32. Indicator taxa inside and outside of corrals and within periphyton community.

Taxon	Location	Observed Indicator Value (IV)	IV from randomized groups		
			Mean	Std. Dev	p
<i>Cladotanytarsus</i> sp.	Inside corrals	89.3	46.4	7.01	0.000
<i>Glyptotendipes</i> sp. ¹	Inside corrals	22.2	12.3	4.26	0.045
<i>Eiseniella</i> sp.	Lake	41.3	21.4	5.19	0.002
<i>Glyptotendipes</i> sp.	Periphyton	99.9	18.7	11.23	0.0002
<i>Cricotopus sylvestris</i> grp.	Periphyton	99.8	16.1	11.59	0.0004
<i>Parachironomus</i> sp.	Periphyton	99.9	10.8	10.65	0.0006

Oligochaeta	Periphyton	85.4	49.7	9.5	0.0006
Naididae	Periphyton	100	7	8.54	0.0008
Ostracoda	Periphyton	100	7.8	10.74	0.0008

¹ *Glyptotendipes* sp. was an indicator for inside corral between inside and outside corral comparison without periphyton assemblages included in analysis. It was a better indicator for periphyton assemblages (see Figure 49).

Appendix 56 contains brief summaries of the important taxa found. In addition, we discussed the ecology and importance of chironomids to Utah Lake’s ecosystem in previous progress reports (Richards et al. 2022, 2023, 2024). Readers are encouraged to review these, particularly Richards et al. 2024.

Richness and Diversity Metrics

The effects of the limnocorrals had a measurable improvement on invertebrate taxa richness (number of taxa), evenness, two diversity indices (Shannon and Simpson), and the effective number of benthic macroinvertebrate taxa (see following). These metrics did however decrease over the study period reflecting changes in seasonal conditions and increased dominance by a few taxa.

Taxa richness, S decreased from July 16 to October 8 inside and outside of corral except richness increased inside corral on October 8, similar to July 16 richness. Taxa richness was substantially greater inside corral than the lake on July 16 and October 8 but similar inside corral and the lake on August 13 and September 3 (Figure 50). Taxa richness was also significantly predicted by sample date and inside vs. outside of corral (Appendix 51).

Figure 50. Taxa richness (number of taxa) by date and location inside corral (In), outside corral (Out), and in periphyton community on insides of corral (Peri),

Effective number of taxa (ENT) decreased significantly over the study period and was significantly greater inside corals than in the lake (Appendix 55, Figure 51).

Figure 51. Effective Number of Taxa by date and location inside corals (In), outside corals (Out), and in periphyton community on insides of corals (Peri),

Evenness, E decreased from July 16 to October 8 and was generally greater inside corals than the lake (Appendix 52, Figure 52).

Figure 52. Evenness by date and location inside corals (In), outside corals (Out), and in periphyton community on insides of corals (Peri),

Shannon and Simpson diversity metrics, H' and D' , also decreased from July 16 to October 8 and were generally better inside corals (Figure 53, Figure 54 Appendix 53, Appendix 54).

Figure 53. Shannon Diversity by date and location inside corals (In), outside corals (Out), and in periphyton community on insides of corals (Peri),

Figure 54. Simpson Diversity by date and location inside corals (In), outside corals (Out), and in periphyton community on insides of corals (Peri).

Discussion

The extreme low effective number of benthic invertebrate taxa is of great concern because it reflects the degraded condition of Utah Lake's benthic environment. Dominance by only three pollution tolerant taxa is a red flag in all biological assessments of water quality throughout the world. However, these remaining three dominant taxa are now the default keystone ecosystem engineers that struggle to maintain the lake's present ecological state and are a crucial component of the lake's food web (Richards and Miller 2019). Their presence and role in Utah Lake's ecosystem should not be underestimated nor undervalued. Midge larvae are responsible for much of the lake's benthic/sediment function and interaction with the water column given their biovolume, biomass, secondary production, and ecology (Richards and Miller 2019, Holker et al. 2015); and as reported by Randal et al. (2017) and Hogsett et al. (2019), the sediment water interface appears to be a major controlling factor of phosphorus recycling and subsequent algal blooms. Although midge larvae densities can exceed 10,000 m⁻² in the lake, primary production estimates suggest that their numbers should be substantially greater (Richards 2022). For example, in Lake Myvatn (Midge Lake), Iceland, midge larval density often exceeds 500,000 m⁻². The reason for the relatively low density of midge larvae in Utah Lake can be attributed to heavy predation from fishes and to a lesser extent unsuitable conditions. Midge larvae are the most common prey item of all fish species in the lake, including those fishes that typically should focus their diets on other smaller fishes (Richard 2022). This conundrum of low biomass and preferred food item of large numbers of fish suggest that midge larvae secondary production is very high (i.e., the production to biomass ratio could be near 100 or more) and that Utah Lake's food web is severely out of balance. Science based restoration is needed.

Benthic invertebrate densities excluding periphyton invertebrates, were much lower than expected in 2024 (mean \cong 4,200, 25th = 1,378, 75th = 6,501). These low densities show that in some locations within the lake (e.g., our study area), the benthic invertebrate assemblage is stressed, mostly due to unstable substrate composed of easily disturbed fine sediments (e.g., silt, clay, fine sand, organic matter) that cannot support large densities of invertebrates or support higher trophic levels dependent on benthic/periphyton associated invertebrates. Other factors may also contribute to low densities including predation by benthivorous fishes such as carp and catfish, pollution, or other undocumented factors. These findings have important restrictions on restoration, if not considered and accounted for.

Even though there was no evidence that the benthic invertebrate assemblage densities differed between inside and outside of corrals, their taxonomic composition differed (Table 30, Table 32). This suggests that some improvement in benthic invertebrate assemblage structure could start to be observed in the lake within just a few weeks to months after wave action and bioturbation is reduced and will likely greatly improve over time.

More importantly, not only will there be an improvement in invertebrate taxa composition (see Richness and Diversity Metrics section above, and Table 30, Table 32), but densities will likely increase by several orders of magnitude if benthic periphyton and macrophyte communities can become established (Figure 49). A few of the many benthic invertebrate ecosystem functions that can be restored via positive feedback loops if periphyton communities are established in Utah Lake include improvements in:

- Gross primary production,

- trophic interactions,
- ecosystem engineering,
- contributions to pelagic fisheries,
- increase retention of nutrients,
- essential habitat for secondary consumers and predators
- food resources for secondary consumers and predators,
- sediment stabilization (bivalves), and
- regulation of nutrient cycling across the sediment–water interface (see discussions from past progress reports).

Conclusion

Results presented in this chapter reinforce our findings from past progress reports and our understanding of Utah Lake ecology; reducing wave disturbance and bioturbation and creating stable substrate habitat will initiate positive changes in invertebrate assemblage structure and function and will substantially increase densities within the benthic periphyton community as these all-important communities become firmly established. These improvements will be a major step in putting Utah Lake on the road to recovery.

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Chapter 7: Recommendations

Based on results from all four years of mesocosm experiments and our collective knowledge of Utah Lake's ecology, food web, and ecosystem functioning, we recommend the following.

Research

- 1) Combine 2021 – 2024 mesocosm results into one analysis. This dataset will provide a much larger sample size for greater power that will allow for analysis of yearly effects, as well as treatment effects.
- 2) Designate each phytoplankton, periphyton, zooplankton, and macroinvertebrate taxon from our mesocosm research to specific functional groups and tolerance values based on updated literature. Functional traits are often more informative than taxonomic descriptions. OreoHelix Ecological and Rushforth Phycology compiled a comprehensive functional trait database for phytoplankton of Utah Lake (see Richards 2021), however several of the dominant taxa found in our studies including *Aphanizomenon* and *Dolicospermum* had limited, or no functional trait values assigned. We began designation of zooplankton functional traits in this 2024 progress report that needs substantial upgrading. Functional traits values for macroinvertebrates are readily available, particularly functional feeding groups. Conduct statistical and ecological analyses of these functional traits similar to what was done in our mesocosm progress reports for taxonomic level assignments.
- 3) Our experiments lasted for < 5 months/year over a four-year time frame compared to the long-term time scale of ecological recovery which perhaps could take up to a century or longer (Benayas et al. 2009). We suggest that Utah Lake ecosystem functional recovery will take many years or decades (Maccaulay et al. 2025). Thus, continued funding and use of TSSD limnocorrals for additional long term, continuous studies are imperative to help evaluate restoration progress (sensu Aarhus University mesocosm studies on nutrient effects on a shallow lake ecosystem that has run continuously for over two decades (Liboriussen et al. 2005, Jeppesen et al. 2021, Saar et al. 2022)). TSSD corrals are valuable assets for needed ecological studies and are available for use, free of charge, by qualified researchers with well-planned research projects.

Restoration

“Ecological recovery and restoration are prolonged processes”
(Maccaulay et al. 2025)

We have discussed at length the importance of holistic and adaptive restoration efforts for Utah Lake in each of our progress reports. These include:

- 1) stabilizing sediments,
- 2) reestablishment of benthic algae, macrophytes, and mollusks,

- 3) increasing light penetration to the benthos,
- 4) reducing the effects of invasive fish species particularly carp,
- 5) reintroduction of Bonneville Cutthroat Trout, and
- 6) restoring more natural water levels and fluctuations.

These synergistic efforts will put the lake on the road to recovery and are well within lake managers capabilities. Citizens and scientists need to petition for their implementation.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Linear regression results of chemistry variables that either significantly increased or decreased from June to October during entire study period.

TempC	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	-.05	.003	-15.86	0	-.056	-.043	***
Constant	1195.347	73.909	16.17	0	1049.49	1341.203	***
Mean dependent var		22.939	SD dependent var			2.127	
R-squared		0.587	Number of obs			179	
F-test		251.631	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		622.784	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			629.159	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

ph	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.003	0	9.10	0	.002	.004	***
Constant	-60.005	7.539	-7.96	0	-74.883	-45.128	***
Mean dependent var		8.634	SD dependent var			0.169	
R-squared		0.319	Number of obs			179	
F-test		82.896	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-194.444	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-188.069	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

DO	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.022	.004	6.37	0	.015	.029	***
Constant	-517.416	82.628	-6.26	0	-680.479	-354.352	***
Mean dependent var		8.658	SD dependent var			1.694	
R-squared		0.186	Number of obs			179	
F-test		40.535	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		662.708	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			669.083	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

ORP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.337	.263	1.28	.202	-.182	.856	
Constant	-7795.237	6206.198	-1.26	.211	-20042.904	4452.429	
Mean dependent var		161.141	SD dependent var			115.284	
R-squared		0.009	Number of obs			179	
F-test		1.644	Prob > F			0.202	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		2208.892	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			2215.266	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

conductivity	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.675	.081	8.36	0	.515	.834	***
Constant	-14267.364	1905.808	-7.49	0	-18028.395	-10506.333	***

Mean dependent var	1661.022	SD dependent var	41.615
R-squared	0.283	Number of obs	179
F-test	69.853	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	1786.222	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	1792.596

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TSS	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.196	.065	3.01	.003	.067	.325	***
Constant	-4578.974	1537.445	-2.98	.003	-7613.055	-1544.892	***

Mean dependent var	48.355	SD dependent var	29.146
R-squared	0.049	Number of obs	179
F-test	9.059	Prob > F	0.003
Akaike crit. (AIC)	1709.329	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	1715.704

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

VSS	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.002	0	4.62	0	.001	.002	***
Constant	-39.568	8.647	-4.58	0	-56.632	-22.503	***

Mean dependent var	0.394	SD dependent var	0.169
R-squared	0.108	Number of obs	179
F-test	21.358	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-145.349	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-138.974

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TDS	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	-.423	.397	-1.07	.288	-1.206	.36	
Constant	10974.153	9366.057	1.17	.243	-7509.359	29457.665	

Mean dependent var	984.838	SD dependent var	173.734
R-squared	0.006	Number of obs	179
F-test	1.138	Prob > F	0.288
Akaike crit. (AIC)	2356.224	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	2362.599

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.002	0	5.12	0	.001	.003	***
Constant	-54.825	10.741	-5.10	0	-76.022	-33.629	***

Mean dependent var	0.214	SD dependent var	0.213
R-squared	0.129	Number of obs	179
F-test	26.258	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-67.717	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-61.342

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

dP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	0	0	4.62	0	0	.001	***
Constant	-9.084	1.978	-4.59	0	-12.988	-5.18	***

Mean dependent var	0.061	SD dependent var	0.039
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R-squared	0.108	Number of obs	179
F-test	21.368	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-673.368	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-666.994

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Ortho P	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	0	0	2.67	.008	0	0	***
Constant	-4.79	1.819	-2.63	.009	-8.379	-1.2	***

Mean dependent var	0.064	SD dependent var	0.034
R-squared	0.039	Number of obs	179
F-test	7.122	Prob > F	0.008
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-703.487	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-697.112

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

NO ₂	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	0	0	-1.56	.12	0	0	
Constant	1.632	1.029	1.59	.115	-3.399	3.663	

Mean dependent var	0.025	SD dependent var	0.019
R-squared	0.014	Number of obs	179
F-test	2.439	Prob > F	0.120
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-907.358	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-900.983

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

NO ₃	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	0	.001	0.17	.862	-.001	.001	
Constant	-1.917	12.482	-0.15	.878	-26.55	22.717	

Mean dependent var	0.261	SD dependent var	0.231
R-squared	0.000	Number of obs	179
F-test	0.030	Prob > F	0.862
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-13.930	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-7.555

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

NH ₃	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	0	0	-4.87	0	-.001	0	***
Constant	8.943	1.816	4.92	0	5.359	12.528	***

Mean dependent var	0.091	SD dependent var	0.036
R-squared	0.118	Number of obs	179
F-test	23.750	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-703.956	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-697.581

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

COD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.283	.029	9.88	0	.226	.339	***
Constant	-6642.337	675.31	-9.84	0	-7975.032	-5309.641	***

Mean dependent var	27.944	SD dependent var	15.552
R-squared	0.355	Number of obs	179

F-test	97.562	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	1414.800	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	1421.175

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Al	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.003	.001	3.18	.002	.001	.005	***
Constant	-66.082	20.957	-3.15	.002	-107.632	-24.533	***
Mean dependent var		0.621	SD dependent var			0.349	
R-squared		0.087	Number of obs			108	
F-test		10.131	Prob > F			0.002	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		72.152	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			77.516	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Ca	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	-.067	.018	-3.78	0	-.102	-.032	***
Constant	1644.36	417.486	3.94	0	816.654	2472.066	***
Mean dependent var		64.321	SD dependent var			7.074	
R-squared		0.119	Number of obs			108	
F-test		14.324	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		718.375	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			723.739	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Fe	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.001	.001	1.74	.085	0	.003	*
Constant	-33.394	19.495	-1.71	.09	-72.045	5.257	*
Mean dependent var		0.550	SD dependent var			0.314	
R-squared		0.028	Number of obs			108	
F-test		3.032	Prob > F			0.085	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		56.533	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			61.897	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mg	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.109	.006	17.24	0	.096	.121	***
Constant	-2505.424	148.689	-16.85	0	-2800.214	-2210.635	***
Mean dependent var		58.637	SD dependent var			4.613	
R-squared		0.737	Number of obs			108	
F-test		297.374	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		495.377	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			500.742	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

K	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date	.059	.003	18.57	0	.053	.066	***
Constant	-1379.908	75.325	-18.32	0	-1529.247	-1230.569	***
Mean dependent var		18.957	SD dependent var			2.471	
R-squared		0.765	Number of obs			108	
F-test		344.884	Prob > F			0.000	

Akaike crit. (AIC)	348.489	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	353.853
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*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 2. Mixed-effects ML regression results of chemistry vs. treatments starting from July 22. Phosphorus treatments began July 19. P1 = first treatment on July 19, P2 = second treatment on September 11; C = corral control with no treatment, Lake = lake outside of corrals and was the baseline for comparisons.

Temp	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	-.199	.06	-3.31	.001	-.317	-.081	***
P2	-.143	.06	-2.37	.018	-.26	-.025	**
C	-.029	.06	-0.49	.627	-.147	.089	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	22.543	.642	35.11	0	21.284	23.801	***
Constant	.707	.224	.b	.b	.38	1.315	
Constant	-1.35	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		22.436	SD dependent var			2.035	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			13.903	
Prob > chi2		0.003	Akaike crit. (AIC)			98.604	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

pH	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.051	.015	3.43	.001	.022	.081	***
P2	.044	.015	2.96	.003	.015	.074	***
C	.054	.015	3.61	0	.025	.083	***
Treatment: base	0	
Lake							
Constant	8.626	.052	164.92	0	8.524	8.729	***
Constant	-1.815	.226	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-2.741	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		8.660	SD dependent var			0.176	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			19.262	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			-310.604	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

DO	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	-.438	.179	-2.44	.015	-.79	-.087	**
P2	-.487	.179	-2.71	.007	-.838	-.135	***
C	-.41	.179	-2.29	.022	-.762	-.059	**
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	9.048	.545	16.60	0	7.98	10.116	***
Constant	.523	.227	.b	.b	.224	1.225	
Constant	-.256	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		8.776	SD dependent var			1.874	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			10.636	
Prob > chi2		0.014	Akaike crit. (AIC)			377.250	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

ORP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
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P1	-31.55	29.443	-1.07	.284	-89.258	26.157	
P2	-30.304	29.443	-1.03	.303	-88.011	27.403	
C	-27.557	29.443	-0.94	.349	-85.264	30.15	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	183.317	19.497	9.40	0	145.105	221.53	***
Constant	3.116	.744	.b	.b	1.951	4.976	
Constant	4.844	.062	.b	.b	4.724	4.968	
Mean dependent var		164.051	SD dependent var			130.251	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			1.762	
Prob > chi2		0.623	Akaike crit. (AIC)			1756.775	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Cond	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	-12.108	2.721	-4.45	0	-17.441	-6.775	***
P2	-8.975	2.721	-3.30	.001	-14.308	-3.642	***
C	-11.742	2.721	-4.32	0	-17.075	-6.409	***
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	1681.308	4.265	394.18	0	1672.948	1689.668	***
Constant	2.518	.238	.b	.b	2.092	3.03	
Constant	2.463	.062	.b	.b	2.343	2.588	
Mean dependent var		1674.288	SD dependent var			17.994	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			28.839	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			1119.098	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TSS	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	-7.732	2.91	-0.25	.801	-6.435	4.97	
P2	-3.809	2.91	-1.31	.19	-9.512	1.894	
C	-2.732	2.91	-0.94	.348	-8.435	2.97	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	52.789	8.969	5.89	0	35.21	70.368	***
Constant	3.325	.227	.b	.b	2.908	3.8	
Constant	2.53	.062	.b	.b	2.41	2.655	
Mean dependent var		51.414	SD dependent var			30.654	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			2.112	
Prob > chi2		0.549	Akaike crit. (AIC)			1152.047	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

VSS	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.018	.024	0.77	.44	-.028	.065	
P2	.056	.024	2.35	.019	.009	.103	**
C	.062	.024	2.60	.009	.015	.109	***
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	.382	.044	8.66	0	.295	.468	***
Constant	-2.029	.233	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-2.276	.062	.b	.b	.	.	

Mean dependent var	0.412	SD dependent var	0.170
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	9.403
Prob > chi2	0.024	Akaike crit. (AIC)	-194.449

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TDS	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	1.468	4.846	0.30	.762	-8.03	10.967	
P2	-4.365	4.846	-0.90	.368	-13.864	5.133	
C	-17.699	4.846	-3.65	0	-27.197	-8.2	***
Treatment : base Lake	0	
Constant	986.132	5.753	171.40	0	974.855	997.408	***
Constant	2.744	.253	.b	.b	2.291	3.287	
Constant	3.04	.062	.b	.b	2.92	3.164	

Mean dependent var	981.655	SD dependent var	27.155
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	16.679
Prob > chi2	0.001	Akaike crit. (AIC)	1273.140

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

TP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.14	.035	3.98	0	.071	.209	***
P2	.086	.035	2.44	.015	.017	.155	**
C	.091	.035	2.58	.01	.022	.16	***
Treatment : base Lake	0	
Constant	.167	.055	3.03	.002	.059	.276	***
Constant	-1.827	.238	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-1.884	.062	.b	.b	.	.	

Mean dependent var	0.237	SD dependent var	0.228
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	17.686
Prob > chi2	0.001	Akaike crit. (AIC)	-89.138

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

dP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.02	.008	2.53	.011	.005	.036	**
P2	.019	.008	2.34	.019	.003	.034	**
C	.014	.008	1.82	.069	-.001	.03	*
Treatment : base Lake	0	
Constant	.053	.008	6.62	0	.038	.069	***
Constant	-3.899	.27	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-3.372	.062	.b	.b	.	.	

Mean dependent var	0.065	SD dependent var	0.041
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	8.898
Prob > chi2	0.031	Akaike crit. (AIC)	-513.366

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

OrthoP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
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P1	.019	.005	4.09	0	.01	.028	***
P2	.013	.005	2.79	.005	.004	.022	***
C	.005	.005	1.04	.297	-.004	.014	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	.057	.009	6.34	0	.039	.074	***
Constant	-3.618	.232	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-3.922	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.065	SD dependent var			0.034	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			19.475	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			-651.200	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

NO ₂	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.002	.001	1.58	.114	-.001	.005	
P2	0	.001	0.21	.834	-.003	.003	
C	-.001	.001	-0.66	.51	-.004	.002	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	.02	.005	4.10	0	.01	.029	***
Constant	-4.193	.226	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-5.067	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.020	SD dependent var			0.016	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			4.343	
Prob > chi2		0.227	Akaike crit. (AIC)			-958.317	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

NO ₃	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.08	.023	3.42	.001	.034	.125	***
P2	.051	.023	2.20	.028	.006	.097	**
C	.041	.023	1.75	.079	-.005	.087	*
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	.193	.068	2.83	.005	.06	.327	***
Constant	-1.556	.227	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-2.296	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.232	SD dependent var			0.236	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			12.673	
Prob > chi2		0.005	Akaike crit. (AIC)			-190.663	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

NH ₃	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	-.006	.004	-1.38	.167	-.014	.002	
P2	-.01	.004	-2.30	.021	-.018	-.001	**
C	-.008	.004	-1.86	.063	-.016	0	*
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	.092	.009	9.76	0	.074	.11	***
Constant	-3.552	.23	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-4.014	.062	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.087	SD dependent var			0.034	

Number of obs	139	Chi-square	6.509
Prob > chi2	0.089	Akaike crit. (AIC)	-673.619

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

COD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	3.527	2.452	1.44	.15	-1.28	8.333	
P2	4.86	2.452	1.98	.047	.054	9.667	**
C	2.627	2.452	1.07	.284	-2.18	7.433	
Treatment : base Lake	0	
Constant	28.906	3.882	7.45	0	21.298	36.515	***
Constant	2.425	.238	.b	.b	2.001	2.94	
Constant	2.359	.062	.b	.b	2.24	2.484	
Mean dependent var		31.417	SD dependent var			15.581	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			4.497	
Prob > chi2		0.213	Akaike crit. (AIC)			1090.414	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Al	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.028	.054	0.51	.607	-.078	.134	
P2	.011	.054	0.21	.837	-.095	.117	
C	.006	.054	0.10	.918	-.1	.111	
Treatment : base Lake	0	
Constant	.722	.139	5.21	0	.45	.994	***
Constant	-1.119	.295	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-1.82	.087	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.733	SD dependent var			0.367	
Number of obs		72	Chi-square			0.296	
Prob > chi2		0.961	Akaike crit. (AIC)			-22.262	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Ca	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	4.5	1.762	2.55	.011	1.046	7.954	**
P2	3.483	1.762	1.98	.048	.029	6.938	**
C	3.761	1.762	2.13	.033	.307	7.216	**
Treatment : base Lake	0	
Constant	59.55	2.46	24.20	0	54.728	64.372	***
Constant	1.648	.314	.b	.b	1.135	2.393	
Constant	1.665	.087	.b	.b	1.503	1.845	
Mean dependent var		62.486	SD dependent var			7.667	
Number of obs		72	Chi-square			7.756	
Prob > chi2		0.051	Akaike crit. (AIC)			471.334	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Fe	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.103	.059	1.74	.082	-.013	.219	*
P2	.092	.059	1.56	.118	-.024	.208	

C	.07	.059	1.18	.236	-.046	.186	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	.554	.127	4.38	0	.306	.802	***
Constant	-1.229	.298	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-1.73	.087	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.620	SD dependent var			0.347	
Number of obs		72	Chi-square			3.675	
Prob > chi2		0.299	Akaike crit. (AIC)			-11.737	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mg	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	-.5	.351	-1.42	.154	-1.188	.188	
P2	-.528	.351	-1.50	.133	-1.216	.16	
C	-.178	.351	-0.51	.612	-.866	.51	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	61.383	1.079	56.91	0	59.269	63.497	***
Constant	.944	.293	.b	.b	.514	1.734	
Constant	.052	.087	.b	.b	.002	1.408	
Mean dependent var		61.082	SD dependent var			2.807	
Number of obs		72	Chi-square			3.195	
Prob > chi2		0.362	Akaike crit. (AIC)			249.463	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

K	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	.106	.184	0.57	.566	-.255	.466	
P2	.094	.184	0.51	.608	-.266	.455	
C	.25	.184	1.36	.174	-.11	.61	
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	20.139	.741	27.18	0	18.687	21.591	***
Constant	.58	.291	.b	.b	.217	1.55	
Constant	-.595	.087	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		20.251	SD dependent var			1.885	
Number of obs		72	Chi-square			1.889	
Prob > chi2		0.596	Akaike crit. (AIC)			159.738	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 3, Summary statistics for chemistry variables by date and inside vs. outside corral.

In, June 1

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	22.900	0	22.900	22.900
pH	9	8.630	0	8.630	8.630
DO	9	8.660	0	8.660	8.660
ORP	9	161.100	0	161.100	161.100
Cond	9	1661	0	1661	1661
TSS	9	18.622	5.499	14.400	32.800
VSS	9	0.257	0.041	.2	.33
TDS	9	1222.889	746.130	940	3212
TP	9	0.062	0.005	0.056	0.071
dP	9	0.032	0.008	0.021	0.044
OrthoP	9	0.039	0.006	0.029	0.045
NO2	9	0.028	0.005	0.022	0.037
NO3	9	0.445	0.043	0.396	0.535
NH3	9	0.092	0.019	0.072	0.128
COD	9	14.222	7.678	6	27
Al	9	0.367	0.087	.3	.5
Ca	9	66.144	1.424	64.100	68.100
Fe	9	0.311	0.033	.3	.4
Mg	9	50.411	1.053	49	52
K	9	15.356	0.292	14.900	15.900

In, July 1

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	25.1	0	25.1	25.1
pH	9	8.504	0.048	8.43	8.6
DO	9	7.396	0.465	6.74	8.37
ORP	9	158.178	28.514	103	180.4
Cond	9	1522.778	0.972	1521	1524
TSS	9	68.2	4.435	63	77
VSS	9	0.353	0.051	0.29	0.43
TDS	9	869	109.261	685	1042
TP	9	0.183	0.033	0.149	0.247
dP	9	0.065	0.014	0.04	0.083
OrthoP	9	0.114	0.017	0.082	0.138
NO2	9	0.053	0.008	0.035	0.063
NO3	9	0.546	0.172	0.19	0.75
NH3	9	0.131	0.011	0.113	0.145
COD	9	19.444	9.888	8	41
Al	9	0.589	0.105	0.4	0.7
Ca	9	72.611	2.414	67.8	75.4
Fe	9	0.65	0.071	0.5	0.72
Mg	9	52.311	1.093	50.3	53.8
K	9	15.989	0.369	15.4	16.5

In, July 17

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	26.200	0.087	26.100	26.300
pH	9	8.482	0.106	8.380	8.740
DO	9	8.027	0.441	7.210	8.450
ORP	9	126.889	10.450	112.400	145.600

Cond	9	1651.333	2.121	1648	1655
TSS	9	25.267	9.993	12.700	48
VSS	9	0.552	0.137	.35	.84
TDS	9	957.778	10.975	935	971
TP	9	0.217	0.211	0.009	0.745
dP	9	0.078	0.009	0.059	0.089
OrthoP	9	0.069	0.007	0.059	0.085
NO2	9	0.061	0.014	0.037	0.081
NO3	9	0.284	0.048	0.222	0.364
NH3	9	0.084	0.017	0.055	0.106
COD	9	14.222	4.381	8	20
Al	9	0.244	0.053	.2	.3
Ca	9	64.978	2.245	62	69.300
Fe	9	0.243	0.040	.2	.3
Mg	9	57.633	1.795	54.700	60.100
K	9	17.544	0.575	16.600	18.200

In, July 22

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	8	26.175	0.089	26	26.3
pH	8	8.424	0.043	8.36	8.48
DO	8	6.309	0.37	5.95	6.86
ORP	8	147.188	5.499	142.1	159.1
Cond	8	1669.25	2.55	1665	1674
TSS	8	23.262	5.643	15.3	30.7
VSS	8	0.295	0.136	0.11	0.57
TDS	8	991.125	24.145	953	1028
TP	8	0.07	0.011	0.053	0.083
dP	8	0.053	0.015	0.038	0.084
OrthoP	8	0.052	0.016	0.028	0.072
NO2	8	-0.003	0.005	-0.011	0.004
NO3	8	-0.001	0.013	-0.019	0.015
NH3	8	0.073	0.01	0.062	0.09
COD	8	11	0.756	10	12
Al	0				
Ca	0				
Fe	0				
Mg	0				
K	0				

In, July 29

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	24.733	0.218	24.500	25.100
pH	9	8.661	0.067	8.580	8.790
DO	9	8.146	1.113	6.820	10.490
ORP	9	132.100	19.474	104.700	154.100
Cond	9	1645.333	5.268	1637	1652
TSS	9	42	7.858	30	59
VSS	9	0.452	0.071	.37	.56
TDS	9	994.778	17.669	972	1026
TP	9	0.217	0.088	0.117	0.416
dP	9	0.058	0.015	.04	0.082
OrthoP	9	0.033	0.010	0.015	0.048
NO2	9	0.025	0.004	0.021	0.034
NO3	9	0.284	0.084	0.201	0.491

NH3	9	0.109	0.018	0.084	0.144
COD	9	23.778	6.648	16	36
Al	9	0.367	.05	.3	.4
Ca	9	59.144	1.357	56.300	60.600
Fe	9	0.306	0.031	.25	.34
Mg	9	59.678	0.618	58.400	60.600
K	9	18.600	0.527	17.500	19.100

In, Aug 14

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	23.9	0.071	23.8	24
pH	9	8.473	0.023	8.44	8.51
DO	9	6.337	0.33	5.81	6.87
ORP	9	133.211	4.385	127	142.4
Cond	9	1685.778	8.105	1676	1700
TSS	9	89.889	8.268	79	107
VSS	9	0.311	0.024	0.28	0.36
TDS	9	984.111	11.33	964	998
TP	9	0.225	0.024	0.179	0.264
dP	9	0.036	0.007	0.027	0.053
OrthoP	9	0.076	0.046	0.038	0.142
NO2	9	0.021	0.002	0.019	0.025
NO3	9	0.111	0.023	0.07	0.149
NH3	9	0.148	0.015	0.13	0.171
COD	9	27	9.46	12	41
Al	9	1.389	0.093	1.3	1.5
Ca	9	69.156	1.611	67	72
Fe	9	1.178	0.094	1.06	1.35
Mg	9	60.378	0.574	59.8	61.4
K	9	19.222	0.211	19	19.5

In, Aug 19

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	22.411	0.127	22.200	22.500
pH	9	8.589	0.042	8.510	8.650
DO	9	7.082	0.397	6.310	7.590
ORP	9	124.578	4.650	118.900	133.300
Cond	9	1667.889	4.226	1662	1677
TSS	9	51.556	3.844	47	57
VSS	9	0.259	0.051	.18	.33
TDS	9	995.333	14.739	977	1021
TP	9	0.146	0.018	0.128	0.178
dP	9	0.049	0.039	0.026	.12
OrthoP	9	0.079	0.006	0.068	0.086
NO2	9	0.009	0.001	0.007	.01
NO3	9	0.054	0.019	0.019	0.077
NH3	9	0.093	0.010	0.072	0.103
COD	9	31.333	5.315	26	43
Al			0		
Ca			0		
Fe			0		
Mg			0		
K			0		

In, Aug 27

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	22.111	0.462	21.5	23
pH	9	8.774	0.083	8.66	8.89
DO	9	10.974	0.972	9.53	12.75
ORP	9	153	8.973	135.8	167.7
Cond	9	1677.778	2.635	1673	1682
TSS	9	54.222	13.358	37	73
VSS	9	0.437	0.08	0.33	0.52
TDS	9	1008.778	37.446	963	1073
TP	9	0.358	0.166	0.13	0.603
dP	9	0.076	0.02	0.051	0.116
OrthoP	9	0.091	0.009	0.075	0.1
NO2	9	0.023	0.005	0.014	0.03
NO3	9	0.286	0.073	0.162	0.41
NH3	9	0.08	0.022	0.04	0.106
COD	9	41.333	10.464	29	63
Al	9	0.611	0.127	0.5	0.8
Ca	9	56.156	2.039	53.8	59.9
Fe	9	0.471	0.076	0.36	0.56
Mg	9	57.756	0.57	56.6	58.5
K	9	18.433	0.235	18.1	18.8

In, Sept 4

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	21.111	0.252	20.800	21.600
pH	9	8.559	0.119	8.410	8.690
DO	9	8.208	0.923	6.940	9.5
ORP	9	163.989	13.684	134	185.900
Cond	9	1675.889	12.454	1657	1693
TSS	9	26.778	7.345	17	40
VSS	9	0.607	0.205	.33	1
TDS	9	960	15.636	940	985
TP	9	0.153	0.031	0.111	0.198
dP	9	0.061	0.028	0.025	0.121
OrthoP	9	0.063	0.020	0.024	0.085
NO2	9	0.017	0.008	0.004	0.027
NO3	9	0.146	0.077	0.014	0.291
NH3	9	0.059	0.011	0.043	0.073
COD	9	29	6.062	24	41
Al			0		
Ca			0		
Fe			0		
Mg			0		
K			0		

In, Sept 10

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	23.4	0.245	23	23.7
pH	9	8.768	0.062	8.67	8.84
DO	9	10.406	0.649	9.03	10.98

ORP	9	161.978	9.058	148.1	177.3
Cond	9	1675	9.721	1661	1693
TSS	9	22.889	7.356	11	34
VSS	9	0.513	0.098	0.4	0.68
TDS	9	974.667	18.193	956	1004
TP	9	0.136	0.042	0.098	0.226
dP	9	0.06	0	0.06	0.06
OrthoP	9	0.019	0.006	0.013	0.027
NO2	9	0.007	0.003	0.003	0.01
NO3	9	0.102	0.026	0.077	0.157
NH3	9	0.048	0.01	0.03	0.06
COD	9	32.111	5.84	26	41
Al	9	0.922	0.083	0.8	1
Ca	9	76.711	2.071	73.5	80.2
Fe	9	1.087	0.082	0.98	1.19
Mg	9	59.433	0.939	58.1	61.2
K	9	21.378	0.363	20.9	22

In, Sept 17

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	20.822	0.067	20.700	20.900
pH	9	8.739	0.027	8.710	8.790
DO	9	8.979	0.416	8.430	9.590
ORP	9	196.711	11.645	166.900	206.200
Cond	9	1673.444	2.833	1668	1676
TSS	9	98	14.569	72	124
VSS	9	0.293	0.042	.25	.38
TDS	9	955.222	14.007	937	974
TP	9	0.667	0.412	0.242	1.530
dP	9	0.143	0.092	0.073	0.299
OrthoP	9	0.111	0.028	0.058	0.158
NO2	9	0.054	0.007	0.043	0.062
NO3	9	0.806	0.079	0.698	0.945
NH3	9	0.098	0.026	0.071	0.152
COD	9	43.667	3.775	37	50
Al			0		
Ca			0		
Fe			0		
Mg			0		
K			0		

In, Sept 23

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	20.267	0.412	19.8	20.8
pH	9	8.994	0.088	8.82	9.12
DO	9	10.772	1.079	8.72	12.08
ORP	9	162.467	10.546	152.3	188.8
Cond	9	1657.111	16.722	1623	1675
TSS	9	63.444	18.228	38	97
VSS	9	0.658	0.082	0.56	0.79
TDS	9	973.222	29.308	932	1038
TP	9	0.602	0.28	0.219	1.14
dP	9	0.095	0.043	0.049	0.193

OrthoP	9	0.08	0.026	0.05	0.117
NO2	9	0.028	0.013	0.013	0.052
NO3	9	0.408	0.238	0.149	0.843
NH3	9	0.082	0.024	0.058	0.127
COD	9	57	14.045	38	80
Al	9	0.456	0.167	0.3	0.7
Ca	9	57.7	3.76	53.8	64
Fe	9	0.384	0.119	0.24	0.57
Mg	9	65.622	0.851	64.5	67.1
K	9	23.611	0.446	22.8	24.2

In, Oct 9

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	9	19.256	0.219	18.900	19.500
pH	9	8.778	0.087	8.640	8.890
DO	9	8.821	0.626	8.050	9.760
ORP	9	159.700	7.857	153.900	179.800
Cond	9	1676.556	4.746	1672	1688
TSS	9	32.778	10.557	15	48
VSS	9	0.412	0.120	.23	.6
TDS	9	957	32.381	929	1021
TP	9	0.159	0.017	0.136	0.192
dP	9	0.081	0.023	0.059	0.136
OrthoP	9	0.086	0.011	.07	.1
NO2	9	0.023	0.005	0.015	0.028
NO3	9	0.307	0.162	-0.095	0.431
NH3	9	0.052	0.017	0.016	0.071
COD	9	29.556	9.015	17	45
Al	9	0.678	0.211	.4	1
Ca	9	61.922	3.674	56.100	67.100
Fe	9	0.428	0.143	.21	.63
Mg	9	63.022	1.690	59.400	64.800
K	9	20.489	0.828	18.400	21.100

Out, June 18

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	22.9	0	22.9	22.9
pH	5	8.63	0	8.63	8.63
DO	5	8.66	0	8.66	8.66
ORP	5	161.1	0	161.1	161.1
Cond	5	1661	0	1661	1661
TSS	5	30.8	0.938	29.6	31.6
VSS	5	0.14	0.036	0.09	0.18
TDS	5	943	21.633	921	976
TP	5	0.068	0.012	0.059	0.088
dP	5	0.023	0.004	0.019	0.029
OrthoP	5	0.044	0.004	0.04	0.048
NO2	5	0.023	0.004	0.019	0.028
NO3	5	0.331	0.039	0.3	0.395
NH3	5	0.076	0.013	0.057	0.088
COD	5	19.8	5.63	13	26
Al	3	0.4	0	0.4	0.4
Ca	3	68.533	1.159	67.3	69.6

Fe	3	0.367	0.058	0.3	0.4
Mg	3	50.833	0.321	50.6	51.2
K	3	15.5	0.1	15.4	15.6

Out, July 1

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	4	25.100	0	25.100	25.100
pH	4	8.595	0.059	8.510	8.640
DO	4	9.060	0.768	7.960	9.740
ORP	4	176.075	2.909	172.800	179.600
Cond	4	1532.750	6.292	1527	1540
TSS	4	54.250	1.258	53	56
VSS	4	.3	0.092	.17	.37
TDS	4	959.250	147.766	759	1113
TP	4	0.101	0.052	0.046	0.168
dP	4	0.031	0.042	0.006	0.094
OrthoP	4	0.026	0.041	0.003	0.087
NO2	4	0.025	0.018	.01	0.052
NO3	4	0.252	0.240	0.034	.5
NH3	4	0.112	0.006	0.108	.12
COD	4	17.750	2.363	16	21
Al	3	.4	0	.4	.4
Ca	3	70.433	1.504	68.700	71.400
Fe	3	0.533	0.025	.51	.560
Mg	3	53.567	1.002	52.800	54.700
K	3	16.167	0.379	15.900	16.600

Out, July 17

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	4	26.175	0.25	25.9	26.5
pH	4	8.41	0.056	8.36	8.49
DO	4	8.405	0.323	8.04	8.8
ORP	4	128.95	8.802	121.8	141.5
Cond	4	1661.25	9.845	1650	1674
TSS	4	32.325	2.466	30.7	36
VSS	4	0.242	0.021	0.22	0.26
TDS	4	959.25	14.175	946	972
TP	4	0.112	0.045	0.061	0.161
dP	4	0.034	0.021	0.011	0.056
OrthoP	4	0.051	0.024	0.027	0.08
NO2	4	0.029	0.031	0.001	0.073
NO3	4	0.086	0.089	0.018	0.215
NH3	4	0.158	0.083	0.081	0.272
COD	4	8.5	2.646	6	12
Al	3	0.367	0.058	0.3	0.4
Ca	3	65.733	1.332	64.6	67.2
Fe	3	0.41	0.02	0.39	0.43
Mg	3	59.5	0.361	59.1	59.8
K	3	18.1	0.1	18	18.2

Out, July 22

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
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Temp	5	26.100	0.235	25.700	26.300
pH	5	8.376	0.097	8.210	8.450
DO	5	6.714	0.514	6.080	7.260
ORP	5	148.460	5.460	139	152.900
Cond	5	1656.200	25.371	1611	1671
TSS	5	24.280	9.271	12.700	36
VSS	5	0.426	0.157	.29	.63
TDS	5	979	9.721	964	989
TP	5	0.068	0.012	0.056	0.088
dP	5	0.062	0.028	0.032	0.103
OrthoP	5	0.031	0.005	0.025	0.039
NO2	5	-0.004	0.004	0.009	0.002
NO3	5	0.025	0.035	0.026	0.068
NH3	5	0.081	0.018	0.067	0.112
COD	5	12.600	1.517	11	15
Al			0		
Ca			0		
Fe			0		
Mg			0		
K			0		

Out, July 29

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	24.98	0.409	24.5	25.5
pH	5	8.612	0.027	8.58	8.64
DO	5	8.62	0.25	8.35	8.88
ORP	5	133.56	20.98	109	154.9
Cond	5	1649.6	13.465	1636	1668
TSS	5	47.2	7.918	40	58
VSS	5	0.306	0.058	0.25	0.37
TDS	5	983.4	19.398	967	1015
TP	5	0.095	0.01	0.08	0.107
dP	5	0.051	0.006	0.044	0.06
OrthoP	5	0.038	0.012	0.03	0.059
NO2	5	0.032	0.008	0.023	0.043
NO3	5	0.302	0.096	0.202	0.445
NH3	5	0.108	0.012	0.093	0.122
COD	5	8.6	8.735	0	18
Al	3	0.5	0	0.5	0.5
Ca	3	62.533	0.473	62	62.9
Fe	3	0.453	0.035	0.42	0.49
Mg	3	59.467	0.351	59.1	59.8
K	3	18.133	0.115	18	18.2

Out, Aug 14

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	23.720	0.084	23.600	23.800
pH	5	8.4	0.053	8.340	8.450
DO	5	6.680	0.448	6.060	7.290
ORP	5	132.760	4.442	127.900	139.300
Cond	5	1693.40	16.891	1673	1707
TSS	5	78	10.536	63	90
VSS	5	.26	0.046	.2	.32
TDS	5	987	11.068	979	1006
TP	5	0.085	0.014	0.067	0.102

dP	5	0.039	0.012	.03	.06
OrthoP	5	0.046	0.006	0.037	0.051
NO2	5	0.022	0.004	0.017	0.026
NO3	5	0.082	0.031	.05	0.129
NH3	5	0.153	0.016	0.141	0.179
COD	5	19.800	3.114	17	25
Al	3	1.5	.1	1.4	1.6
Ca	3	70.533	2.802	67.400	72.800
Fe	3	1.117	0.121	.98	1.210
Mg	3	59.667	0.208	59.500	59.900
K	3	19	0.173	18.900	19.200

Out, Aug 19

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	22.42	0.13	22.3	22.6
pH	5	8.59	0.058	8.5	8.66
DO	5	7.296	0.385	6.78	7.77
ORP	5	126.22	4.245	120.9	131.6
Cond	5	1676.4	20.293	1650	1701
TSS	5	61.4	5.177	55	67
VSS	5	0.258	0.042	0.19	0.3
TDS	5	990	14.44	966	1003
TP	5	0.159	0.012	0.139	0.17
dP	5	0.039	0.01	0.031	0.054
OrthoP	5	0.089	0.01	0.079	0.101
NO2	5	0.013	0.003	0.009	0.017
NO3	5	0.082	0.018	0.055	0.099
NH3	5	0.109	0.007	0.099	0.119
COD	5	32.4	3.647	28	38
Al	0				
Ca	0				
Fe	0				
Mg	0				
K	0				

Out, August 27

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	22.120	0.311	21.800	22.500
pH	5	8.652	0.037	8.620	8.710
DO	5	9.972	1.139	8.330	11.180
ORP	5	150.740	12.743	132.200	165.400
Cond	5	1689.200	7.190	1678	1698
TSS	5	43	1.871	40	45
VSS	5	.3	0.019	.27	.32
TDS	5	1029.600	25.687	991	1055
TP	5	0.179	0.092	0.118	0.334
dP	5	0.043	0.009	0.034	0.058
OrthoP	5	0.072	0.003	0.069	0.076
NO2	5	.01	0.001	0.008	0.011
NO3	5	0.144	0.078	0.094	0.278
NH3	5	0.089	0.011	0.077	0.101
COD	5	28	3.536	23	32
Al	3	0.667	0.058	.6	.7
Ca	3	55.100	1.998	53.800	57.400

Fe	3	0.517	0.021	.5	.54
Mg	3	58.200	0.625	57.700	58.900
K	3	18.633	0.153	18.500	18.800

Out, Sept 4

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	21.32	0.13	21.2	21.5
pH	5	8.544	0.036	8.49	8.59
DO	5	8.566	0.654	7.81	9.6
ORP	5	165.76	6.586	158.8	176.3
Cond	5	1683.6	3.05	1680	1688
TSS	5	24.2	3.114	21	29
VSS	5	0.672	0.036	0.64	0.71
TDS	5	960.8	14.873	942	977
TP	5	0.138	0.011	0.123	0.15
dP	5	0.049	0.011	0.042	0.068
OrthoP	5	0.057	0.004	0.054	0.064
NO2	5	0.023	0.001	0.021	0.024
NO3	5	0.162	0.02	0.134	0.186
NH3	5	0.061	0.002	0.059	0.064
COD	5	40.8	35.801	17	104
Al	0				
Ca	0				
Fe	0				
Mg	0				
K	0				

Out, Sept 10

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	23.960	0.439	23.600	24.700
pH	5	8.708	0.046	8.640	8.760
DO	5	11.634	0.406	11.230	12.190
ORP	5	156.960	7.809	148.200	166.400
Cond	5	1709.600	10.668	1696	1725
TSS	5	12.200	5.263	6	19
VSS	5	0.642	0.123	.5	.78
TDS	5	972.600	15.773	957	998
TP	5	0.109	0.100	0.058	0.287
dP	5	.06	0	.06	.06
OrthoP	5	0.001	0.006	0.004	0.011
NO2	5	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.003
NO3	5	0.072	0.011	0.055	0.085
NH3	5	0.043	0.008	0.035	0.052
COD	5	26.800	4.087	20	31
Al	3	0.367	0.058	.3	.4
Ca	3	49.500	0.173	49.400	49.700
Fe	3	0.243	0.012	.23	.25
Mg	3	61.467	1.332	60.600	63
K	3	21.367	1.007	20.300	22.300

Out, Sept 17

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	20.78	0.11	20.6	20.9
pH	5	8.698	0.019	8.67	8.72

DO	5	9.036	0.397	8.62	9.48
ORP	5	196.56	9.842	180.9	204
Cond	5	1675.4	5.413	1670	1683
TSS	5	137.6	20.354	112	161
VSS	5	0.194	0.023	0.17	0.23
TDS	5	954.2	6.14	947	961
TP	5	0.515	0.247	0.277	0.875
dP	5	0.077	0.033	0.036	0.124
OrthoP	5	0.123	0.036	0.072	0.152
NO2	5	0.062	0.009	0.051	0.075
NO3	5	0.782	0.146	0.609	0.97
NH3	5	0.124	0.048	0.09	0.206
COD	5	43.4	6.066	39	54
Al	0				
Ca	0				
Fe	0				
Mg	0				
K	0				

Out, Sept 10

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	20.680	0.148	20.500	20.900
pH	5	9.016	0.022	8.980	9.040
DO	5	12.882	0.795	11.910	13.560
ORP	5	156.280	3.043	151.800	159.200
Cond	5	1670.600	5.320	1665	1679
TSS	5	61.800	22.208	47	101
VSS	5	0.544	0.094	.47	.7
TDS	5	993.200	10.826	979	1005
TP	5	0.240	0.106	0.144	0.408
dP	5	0.077	0.059	0.016	0.168
OrthoP	5	0.050	0.017	0.032	0.077
NO2	5	0.024	0.003	.02	0.027
NO3	5	0.147	0.051	0.095	.2
NH3	5	0.086	0.029	0.059	0.135
COD	5	51.200	21.359	35	88
Al	3	.6	.1	.5	.7
Ca	3	58.300	0.346	58.100	58.700
Fe	3	0.483	0.015	.47	.5
Mg	3	65.967	0.839	65	66.500
K	3	23.167	0.751	22.400	23.900

Out, Oct 9

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Temp	5	19.34	0.182	19.1	19.6
pH	5	8.674	0.015	8.66	8.69
DO	5	8.972	0.491	8.17	9.48
ORP	5	159.84	8.315	154.2	174.4
Cond	5	1707.8	3.271	1704	1713
TSS	5	35.6	3.782	32	41
VSS	5	0.28	0.025	0.25	0.32
TDS	5	1008.8	15.786	988	1024
TP	5	0.097	0.01	0.084	0.109
dP	5	0.035	0.01	0.019	0.046
OrthoP	5	0.057	0.015	0.038	0.078

NO2	5	0.015	0.004	0.009	0.019
NO3	5	0.143	0.048	0.072	0.189
NH3	5	0.063	0.007	0.053	0.07
COD	5	25.6	3.286	23	31
Al	3	0.7	0.1	0.6	0.8
Ca	3	61.333	2.572	58.4	63.2
Fe	3	0.51	0.03	0.48	0.54
Mg	3	63.533	2.721	60.4	65.3
K	3	20.533	1.595	18.7	21.6

Appendix 4. Additional light attenuation models

The following is from:

<https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2018-05/documents/light-module.pdf>,

that shows that ChlA is important in light attenuation and can be added to models.

If the user simulates macro algae in the eutrophication module, then an additional light extinction term considers macro algal shading:

$$K_{e,MA} = K_{MA} \times M_A_$$

Where $K_{e,MA}$ is the macro algae shading coefficient [1/m], MA is the macro algae biomass [gdw/m³], and K_{MA} is the coefficient [(1/m)/(gdw/m³)], specified in the Constants section, Macro Algae group. This extinction coefficient is applied below the macro algae canopy height, which can be on the water surface or at a specified elevation above the bottom.

Within the water column, light is attenuated with depth following the Beer-Lambert equation:

$$I_z = I_0 * \exp(-K_{e,\lambda} z)$$

Where $K_{e,\lambda}$ is the light extinction coefficient [1/m], λ is the wavelength index, and z is depth below the surface [m].

The light extinction coefficients are calculated internally as a function of background water, algal chlorophyll a, DOC, and solids:

$$K_{e,\lambda} = K_{w,\lambda} + K_{chl,\lambda} \times Chl^{exp,\lambda} + K_{DOC,\lambda} \times DOC + K_{solid,\lambda} \times TSS$$

Where Chl is algal chlorophyll [ug/L], DOC is total dissolved organic carbon [mg/L], and TSS is total suspended solids [mg/L]. In the toxics module, DOC fractions are simulated as state variables. In the eutrophication module, CBOD fractions are simulated as state variables and DOC fractions are calculated from CBOD.

If the user simulates macro algae in the eutrophication module, then an additional light extinction term considers macro algal shading:

$$K_{e,MA} = K_{MA} \times MA$$

Where $K_{e,MA}$ is the macro algae shading coefficient [1/m], MA is the macro algae biomass [g_{DW}/m^3], and K_{MA} is the coefficient [(1/m)/(g_{DW}/m^3)], specified in the Constants section, Macro Algae group. This extinction coefficient is applied below the macro algae canopy height, which can be on the water surface or at a specified elevation above the bottom.]

Appendix 5. *Mixed-effects ML regression of light attenuation (PAR) for all depths measured with data sampled modeled as a random variable.*

Mixed-effects ML regression 47 cm

cm47sqrt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	.426	.184	2.32	.02	.066	.787	**
conductivity	-.001	.002	-0.60	.548	-.006	.003	.
logTSS	-1.278	.22	-5.81	0	-1.709	-.847	***
sqrtVSS	-.897	.657	-1.37	.172	-2.184	.39	.
sqrtORP	.108	.109	0.99	.324	-.106	.321	.
logChlA	-.303	.129	-2.35	.019	-.556	-.05	**
sqrtPhycoc	-.769	.283	-2.72	.007	-1.323	-.215	***
Constant	12.044	4.091	2.94	.003	4.027	20.061	***
Constant	-1.546	.593	.b	.b	.	.	.
Constant	-.104	.063	.b	.b	.	.	.
Mean dependent var		3.941	SD dependent var			1.690	
Number of obs		140	Chi-square			234.086	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			394.073	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mixed-effects ML regression 67 cm

cm67sqrt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	.353	.148	2.39	.017	.063	.643	**
conductivity	-.003	.002	-1.60	.11	-.007	.001	.
logTSS	-1.44	.191	-7.54	0	-1.814	-1.066	***
sqrtVSS	-1.162	.59	-1.97	.049	-2.319	-.005	**
sqrtORP	.218	.092	2.36	.018	.037	.399	**
logChlA	-.187	.113	-1.66	.097	-.408	.034	*
sqrtPhycoc	-.364	.25	-1.46	.144	-.854	.125	.
Constant	12.509	3.716	3.37	.001	5.226	19.792	***
Constant	-1.297	.455	.b	.b	.	.	.
Constant	-.335	.064	.b	.b	.	.	.
Mean dependent var		2.842	SD dependent var			1.438	
Number of obs		141	Chi-square			199.726	

Prob > chi2 0.000 Akaike crit. (AIC) 337.248
 *** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mixed-effects ML regression 87 cm

cm87sqrt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	.161	.12	1.34	.18	-.074	.396	
conductivity	-.003	.002	-1.58	.113	-.006	.001	
logTSS	-1.298	.156	-8.30	0	-1.605	-.992	***
sqrtVSS	-1.2	.487	-2.47	.014	-2.154	-.246	**
sqrtORP	.213	.075	2.83	.005	.065	.36	***
logChlA	-.076	.092	-0.82	.413	-.257	.106	
sqrtPhycoc	-.386	.205	-1.88	.06	-.788	.016	*
Constant	10.141	3.077	3.30	.001	4.109	16.172	***
Constant	-1.438	.408	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-.549	.064	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		2.099	SD dependent var			1.227	
Number of obs		141	Chi-square			206.845	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			277.943	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mixed-effects ML regression 107 cm

cm107sqrt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	.067	.102	0.66	.509	-.132	.266	
conductivity	-.003	.002	-1.86	.062	-.006	0	*
logTSS	-1.063	.139	-7.65	0	-1.335	-.791	***
sqrtVSS	-.916	.442	-2.07	.038	-1.783	-.05	**
sqrtORP	.184	.065	2.82	.005	.056	.312	***
logChlA	-.024	.082	-0.29	.77	-.185	.137	
sqrtPhycoc	-.321	.184	-1.75	.08	-.681	.039	*
Constant	9.069	2.868	3.16	.002	3.448	14.69	***
Constant	-1.324	.352	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-.728	.064	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		1.463	SD dependent var			1.030	
Number of obs		141	Chi-square			151.219	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			232.329	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mixed-effects ML regression 127 cm

cm127sqrt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0
Out	.07	.085	0.82	.412	-.097	.237	
conductivity	-.002	.002	-0.91	.363	-.005	.002	
logTSS	-.604	.128	-4.71	0	-.856	-.353	***
sqrtVSS	-.32	.427	-0.75	.454	-1.157	.517	
sqrtORP	.092	.057	1.63	.103	-.019	.203	
logChlA	-.036	.074	-0.48	.631	-.181	.11	
sqrtPhycoc	-.105	.171	-0.61	.54	-.44	.23	
Constant	5.095	3.097	1.64	.1	-.976	11.166	*
Constant	-.68	.279	.b	.b	.	.	

Constant	-934	.063	.b	.b	.	.
Mean dependent var		0.974	SD dependent var		0.872	
Number of obs		141	Chi-square		48.348	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)		190.827	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Mixed-effects ML regression 147 cm

cm147sqrt	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOut : base In	0	
Out	-.087	.071	-1.21	.225	-.227	.053	
conductivity	.001	.001	0.35	.723	-.002	.003	
logTSS	-.358	.108	-3.30	.001	-.57	-.145	***
sqrtVSS	-.38	.363	-1.05	.294	-1.092	.331	
sqrtORP	-.034	.048	-0.72	.472	-.128	.06	
logChlA	.006	.063	0.10	.92	-.116	.129	
sqrtPhycoc	-.057	.145	-0.39	.694	-.341	.227	
Constant	1.703	2.668	0.64	.523	-3.526	6.932	
Constant	-.727	.272	.b	.b	.	.	
Constant	-1.113	.064	.b	.b	.	.	
Mean dependent var		0.502	SD dependent var		0.644		
Number of obs		140	Chi-square		17.851		
Prob > chi2		0.013	Akaike crit. (AIC)		142.438		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 6. Linear regression results for light attenuation PAR vs depth by date and inside vs. outside of corrals. PAR data was ln transformed

July 5 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	20.8416217	1	20.8416217	F(1, 5)	=	1708.18
Residual	.06100521	5	.012201042	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9971
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9965
Total	20.9026269	6	3.48377114	Root MSE	=	.11046

july5lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.037608	.0009099	-41.33	0.000	-.0399471 - .0352689
_cons	-.3240946	.0866377	-3.74	0.013	-.546804 - .1013852

July 5 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	36.6111044	1	36.6111044	F(1, 5)	=	1011.14
Residual	.181038107	5	.036207621	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9951
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9941
Total	36.7921425	6	6.13202375	Root MSE	=	.19028

july5lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0498449	.0015675	-31.80	0.000	-.0538744 - .0458155
_cons	.3377461	.149248	2.26	0.073	-.0459082 .7214003

July 19in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	16.649107	1	16.649107	F(1, 5)	=	598.98
Residual	.138979299	5	.02779586	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9917
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9901
Total	16.7880863	6	2.79801439	Root MSE	=	.16672

july19lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0336132	.0013734	-24.47	0.000	-.0371437 - .0300827
_cons	.3642958	.1307671	2.79	0.039	.0281482 .7004434

July 19 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	21.927334	1	21.927334	F(1, 5)	=	448.67
Residual	.244360605	5	.048872121	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9890
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9868
Total	22.1716946	6	3.69528243	Root MSE	=	.22107

july19lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0385751	.0018211	-21.18	0.000	-.0432565 - .0338937
_cons	.8267482	.173396	4.77	0.005	.3810195 1.272477

July 30 In

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	23.4495563	1	23.4495563	F(1, 5)	=	594.68
Residual	.197162742	5	.039432548	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9917
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9900
Total	23.6467191	6	3.94111984	Root MSE	=	.19858

july30lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0398916	.0016358	-24.39	0.000	-.0440967 - .0356866
_cons	-.4346335	.1557528	-2.79	0.038	-.835009 - .0342581

July 30 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	31.0982204	1	31.0982204	F(1, 5)	=	936.70
Residual	.16599275	5	.033199855	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9947
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9936
Total	31.2642196	6	5.21070327	Root MSE	=	.18221

july30lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0459391	.001501	-30.61	0.000	-.0497975 - .0420806
_cons	-.0471113	.1429146	-0.33	0.755	-.4144851 .3202624

Aug 5 In

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	13.0679168	1	13.0679168	F(1, 5)	=	105.67
Residual	.618363123	5	.123672625	Prob > F	=	0.0001
				R-squared	=	0.9548
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9458
Total	13.68628	6	2.28104666	Root MSE	=	.35167

aug5lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0297795	.002897	-10.28	0.000	-.0372265 - .0223325
_cons	.0157008	.2758325	0.06	0.957	-.6933491 .7247507

Aug 5 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	15.4950978	1	15.4950978	F(1, 5)	=	77.91
Residual	.994450208	5	.198890042	Prob > F	=	0.0003
				R-squared	=	0.9397
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9276
Total	16.489548	6	2.748258	Root MSE	=	.44597

aug5lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0324274	.0036738	-8.83	0.000	-.0418713 - .0229834
_cons	.6646782	.3497962	1.90	0.116	-.2345016 1.563858

Aug 26 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	37.4978466	1	37.4978466	F(1, 5)	=	254.71
Residual	.736086382	5	.147217276	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9807
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9769
Total	38.233933	6	6.37232217	Root MSE	=	.38369

aug26lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0504449	.0031608	-15.96	0.000	-.05857 - .0423199
_cons	.2521915	.3009456	0.84	0.440	-.5214138 1.025797

Aug 26 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	37.1268893	1	37.1268893	F(1, 5)	=	307.64
Residual	.603407562	5	.120681512	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9840
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9808
Total	37.7302968	6	6.28838281	Root MSE	=	.34739

aug26lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0501948	.0028618	-17.54	0.000	-.0575512 - .0428384
_cons	.882254	.2724764	3.24	0.023	.1818311 1.582677

Sept 6 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	22.6855593	1	22.6855593	F(1, 5)	=	124.78
Residual	.909050712	5	.181810142	Prob > F	=	0.0001
				R-squared	=	0.9615
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9538
Total	23.59461	6	3.93243501	Root MSE	=	.42639

sep6lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0392364	.0035126	-11.17	0.000	-.0482657 - .0302071
_cons	.0013795	.3344395	0.00	0.997	-.8583247 .8610838

Sept 6 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	32.1607459	1	32.1607459	F(1, 5)	=	27.03
Residual	5.9501484	5	1.19002968	Prob > F	=	0.0035
				R-squared	=	0.8439
				Adj R-squared	=	0.8126
Total	38.1108943	6	6.35181571	Root MSE	=	1.0909

sep6lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0467173	.0089866	-5.20	0.003	-.0698179 - .0236166
_cons	.6609461	.8556329	0.77	0.475	-1.538528 2.86042

Sept 9 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	27.1073517	1	27.1073517	F(1, 5)	=	43.05
Residual	3.14862103	5	.629724207	Prob > F	=	0.0012
				R-squared	=	0.8959
				Adj R-squared	=	0.8751
Total	30.2559728	6	5.04266213	Root MSE	=	.79355

sep9lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Depth	-.0428902	.0065372	-6.56	0.001	-.0596945	-.0260859
_cons	.4725493	.6224203	0.76	0.482	-1.127433	2.072532

Sept 9 out

regress lnOUT depth

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	28.632419	1	28.632419	F(1, 5)	=	22.32
Residual	6.4129936	5	1.28259872	Prob > F	=	0.0052
				R-squared	=	0.8170
				Adj R-squared	=	0.7804
Total	35.0454126	6	5.8409021	Root MSE	=	1.1325

lnOUT	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
depth	-.0440802	.0093295	-4.72	0.005	-.0680625	-.0200979
_cons	5.930125	.8882884	6.68	0.001	3.646707	8.213543

Sept 23 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	24.2976744	1	24.2976744	F(1, 5)	=	111.77
Residual	1.08690805	5	.217381609	Prob > F	=	0.0001
				R-squared	=	0.9572
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9486
Total	25.3845824	6	4.23076374	Root MSE	=	.46624

sep23lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Depth	-.0406066	.0038408	-10.57	0.000	-.0504798	-.0307334
_cons	-1.35062	.3656958	-3.69	0.014	-2.290671	-.4105687

Sept 23 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	45.751333	1	45.751333	F(1, 5)	=	492.99
Residual	.464015963	5	.092803193	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9900
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9880
Total	46.2153489	6	7.70255816	Root MSE	=	.30464

sep23lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Depth	-.0557207	.0025096	-22.20	0.000	-.0621717	-.0492697
_cons	-.7423982	.2389406	-3.11	0.027	-1.356615	-.1281818

Sept 30 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	39.8519116	1	39.8519116	F(1, 5)	=	2860.34
Residual	.069662986	5	.013932597	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9983
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9979
Total	39.9215745	6	6.65359576	Root MSE	=	.11804

sep30lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0520043	.0009724	-53.48	0.000	-.0545038 - .0495047
_cons	-.703894	.0925816	-7.60	0.001	-.9418826 - .4659055

Sept 30 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	49.732945	1	49.732945	F(1, 5)	=	887.98
Residual	.280034615	5	.056006923	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9944
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9933
Total	50.0129796	6	8.3354966	Root MSE	=	.23666

sep30lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0580947	.0019496	-29.80	0.000	-.0631062 - .0530832
_cons	-.0450523	.185622	-0.24	0.818	-.5222088 .4321042

October 8 in

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	27.0364674	1	27.0364674	F(1, 5)	=	286.42
Residual	.471968863	5	.094393773	Prob > F	=	0.0000
				R-squared	=	0.9828
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9794
Total	27.5084362	6	4.58473937	Root MSE	=	.30724

oct8lnin	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0428341	.002531	-16.92	0.000	-.0493401 - .036328
_cons	-.2365384	.2409796	-0.98	0.371	-.8559961 .3829194

October 8 out

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs	=	7
Model	36.2116195	1	36.2116195	F(1, 5)	=	103.98
Residual	1.74136114	5	.348272227	Prob > F	=	0.0002
				R-squared	=	0.9541
				Adj R-squared	=	0.9449
Total	37.9529806	6	6.32549677	Root MSE	=	.59015

oct8lnout	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Depth	-.0495722	.0048615	-10.20	0.000	-.0620692 - .0370752
_cons	.7203911	.4628796	1.56	0.180	-.4694787 1.910261

Appendix 7. Mixed-effects ML regression results for dominant phytoplankton taxa in relation to phosphorus treatments. Taxa were sqrt transformed. Date was modeled as random factor. Dates started after July 17 just prior to first treatment. Base = Lake.

Aphanizomenon flosaquae

sqrtAPFL	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Treatment							
P1	338.641	383.266	0.88	.377	-412.547	1089.83	
P2	680.462	383.266	1.78	.076	-70.727	1431.65	*
C	775.19	383.266	2.02	.043	24.002	1526.378	**

Base = Lake	0
Constant	4062.99	977.492	4.16	0	2147.141	5978.839	***
Constant	8.006	.229	.b	.b	7.571	8.467	
Constant	7.41	.062	.b	.b	7.289	7.533	
Mean dependent var		4478.169	SD dependent var			3442.477	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			5.309	
Prob > chi2		0.151	Akaike crit. (AIC)			2504.967	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Dolichospermum circinalis

sqrtDOCI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	331.016	141.163	2.34	.019	54.342	607.691	**
P2	339.944	141.163	2.41	.016	63.269	616.618	**
C	388.95	141.163	2.76	.006	112.276	665.625	***
Base = Lake	0	
Constant	1238.971	281.832	4.40	0	686.59	1791.353	***
Constant	6.743	.232	.b	.b	6.303	7.213	
Constant	6.411	.062	.b	.b	6.291	6.535	
Mean dependent var		1475.418	SD dependent var			1057.970	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			10.834	
Prob > chi2		0.013	Akaike crit. (AIC)			2222.148	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Chlamydomonas sp.

sqrtCHLSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	136.163	33.021	4.12	0	71.444	200.882	***
P2	88.182	33.021	2.67	.008	23.463	152.902	***
C	115.2	33.021	3.49	0	50.481	179.919	***
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	198.623	59.711	3.33	.001	81.592	315.655	***
Constant	5.179	.234	.b	.b	4.74	5.658	
Constant	4.959	.062	.b	.b	4.838	5.082	
Mean dependent var		272.733	SD dependent var			235.286	
Number of obs		139	Chi-square			21.736	
Prob > chi2		0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)			1816.149	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Cryptomonas sp.

sqrtCRPTSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	111.125	54.404	2.04	.041	4.495	217.755	**
P2	137.72	54.404	2.53	.011	31.09	244.35	**
C	159.633	54.404	2.93	.003	53.003	266.263	***
Treatment : base	0	
Lake							
Constant	183.834	79.609	2.31	.021	27.804	339.865	**
Constant	5.431	.241	.b	.b	4.979	5.923	
Constant	5.458	.062	.b	.b	5.337	5.581	

Mean dependent var	273.165	SD dependent var	335.289
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	11.319
Prob > chi2	0.010	Akaike crit. (AIC)	1950.287

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Pennate diatoms

sqrtPD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	210.1	64.872	3.24	.001	82.953	337.247	***
P2	170.134	64.872	2.62	.009	42.987	297.281	***
C	257.874	64.872	3.98	0	130.727	385.021	***
Treatment : base	0
Lake							
Constant	191.822	59.582	3.22	.001	75.044	308.6	***
Constant	4.939	.289	.b	.b	4.405	5.538	
Constant	5.634	.062	.b	.b	5.513	5.757	

Mean dependent var	330.173	SD dependent var	331.075
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	19.804
Prob > chi2	0.000	Akaike crit. (AIC)	1987.676

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Euglena sp.

sqrtEUSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	38.303	19.78	1.94	.053	-465	77.071	*
P2	4.383	19.78	0.22	.825	-34.385	43.151	
C	5.443	19.78	0.28	.783	-33.325	44.211	
Treatment : base	0
Lake							
Constant	82.988	33.358	2.49	.013	17.607	148.368	**
Constant	4.587	.236	.b	.b	4.147	5.073	
Constant	4.446	.062	.b	.b	4.326	4.57	

Mean dependent var	93.892	SD dependent var	131.446
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	4.188
Prob > chi2	0.242	Akaike crit. (AIC)	1672.167

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Aulacoseira granulata var. *angustissima*

sqrtAUGRA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
P1	30.836	15.028	2.05	.04	1.38	60.291	**
P2	21.565	15.028	1.43	.151	-7.891	51.02	
C	4.279	15.028	0.28	.776	-25.176	33.734	
Treatment : base	0
Lake							
Constant	56.294	11.202	5.03	0	34.339	78.249	***
Constant	2.992	.396	.b	.b	2.308	3.877	
Constant	4.172	.062	.b	.b	4.051	4.295	

Mean dependent var	68.581	SD dependent var	69.226
Number of obs	139	Chi-square	5.289
Prob > chi2	0.152	Akaike crit. (AIC)	1574.547

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 8. Multiple response permutation procedure (MRPP) post hoc results for phytoplankton assemblages between dates sampled. Add Tap definitions.

Dates compared	T	A	p
18-Jun-24 vs. 1-Jul-24	-9.297	0.236	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 17-Jul-24	-13.260	0.332	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 22-Jul-24	-13.694	0.394	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 29-Jul-24	-13.397	0.286	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 14-Aug-24	-7.017	0.132	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 19-Aug-24	-14.781	0.370	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 27-Aug-24	-17.028	0.544	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 4-Sep-24	-5.248	0.098	0.001
18-Jun-24 vs. 10-Sep-24	-5.579	0.091	0.001
18-Jun-24 vs. 17-Sep-24	-4.771	0.101	0.003
18-Jun-24 vs. 23-Sep-24	-7.187	0.132	0.000
18-Jun-24 vs. 9-Oct-24	-8.823	0.182	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 17-Jul-24	-13.562	0.486	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 22-Jul-24	-14.163	0.554	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 29-Jul-24	-15.379	0.518	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 14-Aug-24	-6.434	0.209	0.001
1-Jul-24 vs. 19-Aug-24	-14.483	0.516	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 27-Aug-24	-16.190	0.683	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 4-Sep-24	-9.057	0.282	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 10-Sep-24	-7.929	0.156	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 17-Sep-24	-8.336	0.252	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 23-Sep-24	-10.556	0.338	0.000
1-Jul-24 vs. 9-Oct-24	-6.442	0.165	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 22-Jul-24	-3.760	0.076	0.008
17-Jul-24 vs. 29-Jul-24	-9.789	0.203	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 14-Aug-24	-11.595	0.320	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 19-Aug-24	-5.099	0.090	0.001
17-Jul-24 vs. 27-Aug-24	-8.929	0.206	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 4-Sep-24	-12.745	0.377	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 10-Sep-24	-12.578	0.375	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 17-Sep-24	-13.715	0.425	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 23-Sep-24	-14.065	0.424	0.000
17-Jul-24 vs. 9-Oct-24	-15.335	0.504	0.000
22-Jul-24 vs. 29-Jul-24	-9.793	0.245	0.000
22-Jul-24 vs. 14-Aug-24	-13.065	0.402	0.000
22-Jul-24 vs. 19-Aug-24	-3.909	0.076	0.006
22-Jul-24 vs. 27-Aug-24	-3.637	0.079	0.011

22-Jul-24	vs.	4-Sep-24	-13.792	0.450	0.000
22-Jul-24	vs.	10-Sep-24	-12.780	0.417	0.000
22-Jul-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-14.098	0.480	0.000
22-Jul-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-14.803	0.494	0.000
22-Jul-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-15.638	0.565	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	14-Aug-24	-14.334	0.356	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	19-Aug-24	-12.482	0.265	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	27-Aug-24	-15.201	0.442	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	4-Sep-24	-14.360	0.361	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	10-Sep-24	-13.940	0.337	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-13.984	0.376	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-15.984	0.410	0.000
29-Jul-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-17.117	0.512	0.000
14-Aug-24	vs.	19-Aug-24	-11.498	0.323	0.000
14-Aug-24	vs.	27-Aug-24	-15.593	0.543	0.000
14-Aug-24	vs.	4-Sep-24	-2.099	0.050	0.046
14-Aug-24	vs.	10-Sep-24	-6.060	0.123	0.001
14-Aug-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-4.332	0.106	0.005
14-Aug-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-2.460	0.055	0.032
14-Aug-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-6.098	0.147	0.001
19-Aug-24	vs.	27-Aug-24	-6.543	0.161	0.001
19-Aug-24	vs.	4-Sep-24	-13.957	0.408	0.000
19-Aug-24	vs.	10-Sep-24	-13.601	0.399	0.000
19-Aug-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-14.876	0.450	0.000
19-Aug-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-14.907	0.446	0.000
19-Aug-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-16.275	0.528	0.000
27-Aug-24	vs.	4-Sep-24	-16.756	0.613	0.000
27-Aug-24	vs.	10-Sep-24	-15.919	0.565	0.000
27-Aug-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-17.085	0.638	0.000
27-Aug-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-17.361	0.656	0.000
27-Aug-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-17.797	0.708	0.000
4-Sep-24	vs.	10-Sep-24	-4.748	0.085	0.003
4-Sep-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-1.552	0.040	0.077
4-Sep-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-0.050	0.001	0.334
4-Sep-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-6.465	0.151	0.001
10-Sep-24	vs.	17-Sep-24	-1.324	0.023	0.099
10-Sep-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-6.742	0.118	0.000
10-Sep-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-5.225	0.073	0.001
17-Sep-24	vs.	23-Sep-24	-2.615	0.067	0.028
17-Sep-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-4.100	0.101	0.006
23-Sep-24	vs.	9-Oct-24	-7.480	0.186	0.000

Appendix 9. Summary statistics (mean, s. d., p25, median, p75, min, and max) for each phytoplankton taxa by date sampled. Taxa names are in Table 13.

June 18

	mean	s. d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	400	1496.663	0.000	0	0	0	5600
ANSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANAR	100.8	377.159	0.000	0	0	0	1411.2
ANFA	3588.6	2568.886	1596.000	3511.2	5107.2	0	9576
ANJU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APFL	3637197.6	2270310.6	2449272.00	2939126.5	4408689.5	1102172.4	9307234
APIN	1120	2846.99	0.000	0	0	0	7840
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	11030.4	18789.629	0.000	0	12868.8	0	51475.199
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	18432	59484.385	0.000	0	0	0	223641.59
AUGRA	20592	26223.546	5544.000	13860	22176	0	99792
CDSP	59976	37748.43	28812.000	55566	78204	12348	156408
CEHI	763708.8	807630.07	201734.406	437091.19	1143161.6	0	2689792
CHLSP	36252	34075.073	9576.000	26334	47880	2394	110124
CHDI	921.6	2586.234	0.000	0	0	0	9676.8
CLLO	29488.8	49218.562	0.000	0	37531.199	0	150124.8
CLLT	8042.4	21728.096	0.000	0	0	0	75062.398
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRR1	2240	8381.313	0.000	0	0	0	31360
CRPTSP	613234.8	548867.99	170301.600	510904.8	823124.4	0	1703016
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	514.8	1065.15	0.000	0	655.2	0	3931.2
DECO	2280	2244.994	0.000	3360	3360	0	6720
DEIN	153.6	574.719	0.000	0	0	0	2150.4
DEOP	720	1945.219	0.000	0	0	0	6720
DOC1	488899.2	379515.72	174955.200	437388	787298.4	48006	1224686.4
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	2412.8	9027.871	0.000	0	0	0	33779.199
EUSP	4840	9718.385	0.000	0	0	0	24640
FRCR	14400	53879.866	0.000	0	0	0	201600
GRLA	400	834.34	0.000	0	0	0	2240
GYS1	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	36	134.7	0.000	0	0	0	504
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	7577.6	7657.441	1657.600	4972.8	13260.8	0	24864
MEVA	1544	3924.78	0.000	0	0	0	10808
MEGL	37.2	139.19	0.000	0	0	0	520.8
MESP	38.4	143.68	0.000	0	0	0	537.6
MIAE	2940	11000.473	0.000	0	0	0	41160
MOCO	26	97.283	0.000	0	0	0	364
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	2.8	10.477	0.000	0	0	0	39.2

OOBO	10001.6	14678.335	0.000	0	20003.199	0	40006.398
OOSP	15360	13964.415	0.000	13440	21504	0	43008
OCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PAMO	12000	25030.197	0.000	0	0	0	67200
PEPE	400	1496.663	0.000	0	0	0	5600
PEAN	400.8	1499.656	0.000	0	0	0	5611.2
PEDU	27160	31959.085	0.000	27160	54320	0	108640
PD	98000	81132.2	39200.000	90650	117600	0	245000
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	625.2	1689.099	0.000	0	0	0	5835.2
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	93.6	350.219	0.000	0	0	0	1310.4
PTSP	703	1160.191	0.000	259	1036	0	4144
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	240	897.998	0.000	0	0	0	3360
SCBI	504	1361.653	0.000	0	0	0	4704
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	1024	3831.457	0.000	0	0	0	14336
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	16060	7880.047	8176.000	15330	24528	4088	28616
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	51200	109535.97	0.000	0	0	0	358400
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	90	336.749	0.000	0	0	0	1260
WICR	160	598.665	0.000	0	0	0	2240
Sum	5967170.3	2685432.3	3834073.50	6298843.5	7469823	2157310.5	11687530
			0				

July 1

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANAR	18.092	65.233	0.000	0	0	0	235.2
ANFA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANJU	6188	7336.695	0.000	6384	6384	0	22344
APFL	1.091e+08	58014957	76417288.0	1.234e+08	1.455e+08	5633325.5	2.048e+08
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	2646.646	6460.383	0.000	0	0	0	17203.199
AUGRA	40940.308	28766.403	22176.000	33264	66528	0	88704
CDSP	40526.769	21899.167	24696.000	41160	49392	8232	90552
CEHI	3705015.1	3002286.7	1613875.25	3765708.8	4169177.5	403468.81	12373043
CHLSP	513052.61	455195.23	196308.000	339948	560196	81396	1484280
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	69288.368	57013.984	0.000	75062.398	75062.398	0	150124.8
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRR1	5341.538	19259.191	0.000	0	0	0	69440
CRPTSP	257635.75	302712.91	0.000	170301.6	510904.8	0	794740.8
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	302.4	785.119	0.000	0	0	0	2620.8
DECO	1292.308	2922.254	0.000	0	0	0	10080
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	516.923	1261.794	0.000	0	0	0	3360
DOC1	807485.54	688941.73	174955.200	699820.8	1049731.2	87477.6	2186940
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	7581.538	10714.932	0.000	0	12320	0	36960
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSO	1408.615	3657.179	0.000	0	0	0	12208
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	3315.2	5580.313	0.000	0	3315.2	0	16576
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	63323.077	228314.6	0.000	0	0	0	823200
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	9232.246	15527.484	0.000	0	20003.199	0	40006.398
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	67396	106562.43	0.000	0	134792	0	336980
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	863.262	3112.534	0.000	0	0	0	11222.4
PEDU	8356.923	20398.996	0.000	0	0	0	54320
PD	127400	105321.51	68600.000	98000	156800	9800	411600
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	1346.585	3496.129	0.000	0	0	0	11670.4
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	2212.431	7977.032	0.000	0	0	0	28761.6
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	314.462	1133.807	0.000	0	0	0	4088
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	14446.276	35262.924	0.000	0	0	0	93900.797
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	947.261	1800.074	0.000	0	0	0	4104.8
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

Sum	1.148e+08	57244953	78002424.0	1.275e+08	1.473e+08	10268602	2.109e+08
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July 17

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	196.431	326.783	0.000	0	319.2	0	957.6
ANJU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APFL	1592026.8	1213358.3	734781.625	1714490.4	2694199.3	0	3673908
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	199.877	720.666	0.000	0	0	0	2598.4
AUGR	5954.954	19035.47	0.000	0	0	0	68812.797
AUGRA	11514.462	7989.754	5544.000	11088	16632	0	22176
CDSP	6648.923	7977.409	0.000	4116	8232	0	24696
CEHI	6527918.3	6175576.2	1210406.37	4976115	10490189	403468.81	20038950
CHLSP	1823491.4	2966841.9	83790.000	402192	2441880	31122	10265472
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	103932.55	104092.82	0.000	75062.398	187656	0	300249.59
CRQU	799.508	2882.666	0.000	0	0	0	10393.6
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	120084.46	135209.38	28383.600	56767.2	141918	0	454137.6
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DECO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOCI	111029.26	161315.93	43738.800	87477.6	87477.6	0	612343.2
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	5686.154	11094.141	0.000	0	6160	0	36960
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSF	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	82.708	298.207	0.000	0	0	0	1075.2
KOSP	1147.569	1959.502	0.000	0	1657.6	0	6630.4
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	2308.061	5992.405	0.000	0	0	0	20003.199
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	12022.769	25278.042	0.000	0	0	0	67396
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PD	124761.54	111962.86	19600.000	102900	225400	4900	323400
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	897.723	3236.787	0.000	0	0	0	11670.4
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	239.077	583.58	0.000	0	0	0	1554
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	786.154	947.198	0.000	0	2044	0	2044
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	315.754	1138.467	0.000	0	0	0	4104.8
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	10452044	8498772.7	3108473.25	9842347	15340668	1504300	29009052
			0				

July 22

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	61.385	122.564	0.000	0	0	0	319.2
ANJU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APFL	329709.7	271013.8	122463.602	244927.2	489854.41	0	979708.81
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	552.462	1991.928	0.000	0	0	0	7182
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	1323.323	3230.191	0.000	0	0	0	8601.6
AUGRA	6396.923	8421.941	0.000	5544	5544	0	22176
CDSP	3799.385	5168.692	0.000	0	8232	0	16464
CEHI	3160505.6	2918119.5	1613875.25	2689792	3631219.3	0	11028147
CHLSP	31858.615	27232.467	11970.000	33516	43092	0	83790
CHDI	124.062	447.31	0.000	0	0	0	1612.8
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	25983.138	23660.613	0.000	37531.199	37531.199	0	75062.398
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	43667.077	109694.07	0.000	0	28383.6	0	397370.4
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

DEBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DECO	129.231	465.948	0.000	0	0	0	1680
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOCI	178319.72	164104.59	43738.800	87477.6	262432.8	0	437388
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	1299.2	4684.332	0.000	0	0	0	16889.6
EUSP	1421.538	2701.339	0.000	0	0	0	6160
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSF	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	2932.677	4695.908	0.000	0	4972.8	0	16576
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	769.354	2773.945	0.000	0	0	0	10001.6
OOSP	413.538	1491.034	0.000	0	0	0	5376
OCSP	72580.308	65755.949	0.000	101094	101094	0	202188
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	431.631	1556.267	0.000	0	0	0	5611.2
PEDU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PD	60471.815	49866.951	19600.000	58800	93100	4900	161700
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	224.431	809.197	0.000	0	0	0	2917.6
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	1106.215	3988.516	0.000	0	0	0	14380.8
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	1100.615	1412.527	0.000	0	3066	0	3066
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	157.877	569.233	0.000	0	0	0	2052.4
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	3925339.8	2840446.3	1852163.62	4027259.5	4471132.5	944568.81	11217920

5

July 29

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	488.4	815.169	0.000	0	621.6	0	2486.4
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANAR	33.6	125.72	0.000	0	0	0	470.4
ANFA	2693.4	1198.871	2234.400	2553.6	2872.8	840	5266.8
ANJU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APFL	3498951	2022251.1	2087904.00	2694199.3	5755789	361242	6613034.5
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	2052	5216.093	0.000	0	0	0	14364
APSP	156	583.699	0.000	0	0	0	2184
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	7987.2	12831.311	0.000	0	17203.199	0	34406.398
AUGRA	11964	12382.16	0.000	11088	22176	0	33264
CDSP	66444	49808.627	32928.000	55566	82320	4116	172872
CEHI	5624547.1	4637574.5	3093260.75	4505401.5	6321011	2017344	20913132
CHLSP	474867	375045.56	263340.000	464436	564984	19152	1606374
CHDI	230.4	862.078	0.000	0	0	0	3225.6
CLLO	13404	27958.73	0.000	0	0	0	75062.398
CLLT	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRQU	556.8	2083.355	0.000	0	0	0	7795.2
CRSP	974.4	3645.871	0.000	0	0	0	13641.6
CRRE	800	2993.326	0.000	0	0	0	11200
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	553480.2	790499.23	227068.800	340603.2	510904.8	56767.2	3207346.8
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	421.2	1078.355	0.000	0	0	0	3931.2
DECO	120	448.999	0.000	0	0	0	1680
DEIN	230.4	622.47	0.000	0	0	0	2150.4
DEOP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOCI	5200116.6	3077852.4	1568196.00	5554827.6	7654290	874776	9884968.8
DOPL	14112	30190.852	0.000	0	0	0	98784
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	1760	4473.842	0.000	0	0	0	12320
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSP	12644	12258.204	3052.000	9156	24416	0	36624
KILU	72	269.399	0.000	0	0	0	1008
KISP	76.8	287.359	0.000	0	0	0	1075.2
KOSP	18115.2	10771.247	9945.600	16576	26521.6	0	36467.199
MEVA	772	2888.56	0.000	0	0	0	10808
MEGL	111.6	221.765	0.000	0	0	0	520.8
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	44.8	167.626	0.000	0	0	0	627.2
MOSP	2.8	10.477	0.000	0	0	0	39.2
OOBO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOSP	4992	7444.513	0.000	0	10752	0	21504
OCSP	24070	40585.453	0.000	0	33698	0	134792
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	3880	14517.631	0.000	0	0	0	54320

PD	507150	427879.5	137200.000	438550	891800	9800	1460200
PESP	1880	7034.316	0.000	0	0	0	26320
PHSP	5210	3826.152	2917.600	5835.2	5835.2	0	11670.4
VAR63	17430	65217.088	0.000	0	0	0	244020
PSSP	187.2	400.491	0.000	0	0	0	1310.4
PTSP	2146	1390.788	1036.000	2072	3108	0	4662
QUCH	776	2903.526	0.000	0	0	0	10864
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	1027.2	3843.43	0.000	0	0	0	14380.8
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	949	1470.909	0.000	0	2044	0	5110
SNSP	1066	3988.607	0.000	0	0	0	14924
SPSC	3353.6	12548.022	0.000	0	0	0	46950.398
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	60	224.499	0.000	0	0	0	840
TRSP	586.4	1490.603	0.000	0	0	0	4104.8
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	13300	49764.043	0.000	0	0	0	186200
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	16096292	6980894.4	11128606.0	13057625	20467452	8948190	34375392

August 14

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	59335.2	76416.46	0.000	40521.602	81043.203	0	243129.59
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	1503.6	1273.851	319.200	1117.2	1915.2	0	3830.4
ANJU	9918	9497.486	0.000	9576	9576	0	31920
APFL	80353617	61885504	36004300.0	48495584	1.254e+08	13960850	2.006e+08
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	7920	11853.571	0.000	0	11088	0	33264
CDSP	14406	14507.412	0.000	10290	24696	0	49392
CEHI	29573303	23901984	8203865.50	22728743	52450944	672448	70338064
CHLSP	53010	52052.148	21546.000	38304	76608	0	193914
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	5361.6	20061.27	0.000	0	0	0	75062.398
CLLT	26807.999	47538.795	0.000	0	75062.398	0	150124.8
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRR1	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	79068.6	132747.96	0.000	0	85150.8	0	397370.4
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	374.4	800.982	0.000	0	0	0	2620.8
DECO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOCI	2433751.8	2432347.2	524865.600	1487119.2	4461357.6	174955.2	8266633.2
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	3800	9659.431	0.000	0	0	0	26600
ERGI	1206.4	4513.935	0.000	0	0	0	16889.6
EUSP	11000	20240.736	0.000	0	12320	0	55440
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSF	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	3788.8	6483.039	0.000	0	3315.2	0	19891.199
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	9287.2	13849.895	0.000	0	20003.199	0	40006.398
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	507877	809449.88	67396.000	202188	471772	0	2527350
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PD	74550	45812.272	49000.000	53900	78400	39200	176400
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	833.6	3119.046	0.000	0	0	0	11670.4
VAR63	913654	989657.8	40846.400	488040	1708140	0	3172260
PSSP	93.6	350.219	0.000	0	0	0	1310.4
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	1273.6	3237.435	0.000	0	0	0	8915.2
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	1.141e+08	79627825	46784664.0	83878304	1.693e+08	40630004	2.778e+08

August 19

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

ANSP	5788.8	21659.707	0.000	0	0	0	81043.203
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANJU	1824	2992.865	0.000	0	3192	0	9576
APFL	2641714.8	2615422	1224636.00	1775722.2	3061590	367390.81	10531870
			0				
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	9108	6740.059	5544.000	11088	11088	0	22176
CDSP	11172	8141.036	4116.000	8232	16464	0	28812
CEHI	8107801.7	4907539.3	4169177.50	6690857.5	10691923	3093260.8	20442420
CHLSP	10944	13336.314	0.000	7182	19152	0	47880
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	24127.2	37839.259	0.000	0	37531.199	0	112593.6
CLLT	2680.8	10030.635	0.000	0	0	0	37531.199
CRQU	185.6	694.452	0.000	0	0	0	2598.4
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRR1	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	10137	26362.198	0.000	0	0	0	85150.8
DESP	6360	23796.941	0.000	0	0	0	89040
DEBI	46.8	175.11	0.000	0	0	0	655.2
DECO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	120	448.999	0.000	0	0	0	1680
DOCI	184327.8	152656.05	87477.600	153085.8	349910.4	0	481126.8
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSF	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	1657.6	2252.235	0.000	0	3315.2	0	6630.4
MEVA	1544	3924.78	0.000	0	0	0	10808
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	1428.8	3631.946	0.000	0	0	0	10001.6
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	219037	166534.54	101094.000	168490	336980	0	505470
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	1940	7258.815	0.000	0	0	0	27160
PD	39900	36255.779	9800.000	31850	58800	0	127400
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

PHSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
VAR63	1298535	1420941.8	366030.000	549045	2806230	0	4392360
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	12580381	4604377.1	9290397.00	11790352	16378505	5551465	22575188

August 27

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	10130.4	32524.251	0.000	0	0	0	121564.8
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	22.8	85.31	0.000	0	0	0	319.2
ANJU	912	2559.294	0.000	0	0	0	9576
APFL	1968165	3181684.7	0.000	122463.6	2694199.3	0	9552161
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	13068	16928.889	0.000	5544	22176	0	55440
CDSP	17346	13033.802	8232.000	16464	32928	0	32928
CEHI	23521270	16107819	11229882.0	15701661	38733004	1277651.3	53795840
CHLSP	38133	60792.549	4788.000	11970	38304	0	215460
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRR1	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	2027.4	7585.836	0.000	0	0	0	28383.6
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	140.4	379.318	0.000	0	0	0	1310.4
DECO	120	448.999	0.000	0	0	0	1680
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	960	3591.991	0.000	0	0	0	13440
DOC1	215569.8	552315.66	0.000	0	174955.2	0	2099462.4

DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSP	1308	4894.088	0.000	0	0	0	18312
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	2857.6	10692.16	0.000	0	0	0	40006.398
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	21663	55461.536	0.000	0	0	0	202188
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	5820	15723.854	0.000	0	0	0	54320
PD	48300	46240.775	9800.000	39200	68600	4900	176400
PESP	15980	23186.992	0.000	0	39480	0	52640
PHSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
VAR63	732060	1826078.5	0.000	0	0	0	6100500
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	168	628.598	0.000	0	0	0	2352
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	6400	23946.607	0.000	0	0	0	89600
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	586.4	2194.108	0.000	0	0	0	8209.6
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	26623008	16142940	11303200.0	23255808	39929540	1306827.3	53994420

September 4

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	31838.401	36168.866	0.000	40521.602	40521.602	0	121564.8
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	136.8	299.287	0.000	0	0	0	957.6

ANJU	912	1951.11	0.000	0	0	0	6384
APFL	17932170	10424713	13470996.0	16532586	21798520	3918835.3	40657916
			00				
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	5544	5753.281	0.000	5544	11088	0	11088
CDSP	22932	15876.838	16464.000	16464	32928	0	57624
CEHI	4524390.4	2419419.1	3362240.00	3765708.9	4704000	2017344	10759168
CHLSP	224694	167779.44	138852.000	160398	292068	28728	574560
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	58977.599	52490.625	0.000	75062.398	75062.398	0	150124.8
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	166246.8	134454.29	0.000	198685.2	283836	0	340603.2
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DECO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOCI	1768297.2	781805.21	1224686.40	1749552	2536850.4	437388	2799283.2
			0				
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	36960	46601.029	0.000	12320	61600	0	135520
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	4286.4	8517.669	0.000	0	0	0	20003.199
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	57768	51917.086	0.000	67396	67396	0	134792
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	1200	3242.032	0.000	0	0	0	11200
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	3880	14517.631	0.000	0	0	0	54320
PD	40600	36437.259	9800.000	29400	68600	0	107800
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	74	276.883	0.000	0	0	0	1036
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	2054.4	7686.861	0.000	0	0	0	28761.6
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	2052.4	3117.819	0.000	0	4104.8	0	8209.6
TRIS	2380	6049.854	0.000	0	0	0	16660
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	24887394	11918441	17958652.0	24074428	28601860	8230611	49036708

September 10

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	7236	21918.494	0.000	0	0	0	81043.203
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANJU	228	853.098	0.000	0	0	0	3192
APFL	24825121	16831262	16165195.0	18614467	35759372	244927.2	61721656
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	5544	10428.707	0.000	0	11088	0	33264
CDSP	64386	158029.39	8232.000	16464	49392	0	609168
CEHI	2348764.7	3314568.3	134489.594	874182.38	4169177.5	0	11297126
CHLSP	324045	251315.81	114912.000	313614	474012	0	837900
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	16084.8	60183.812	0.000	0	0	0	225187.2
CLLT	8042.4	21728.096	0.000	0	0	0	75062.398
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	8109.6	20614.243	0.000	0	0	0	56767.2
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	468	1751.096	0.000	0	0	0	6552
DECO	1680	6285.984	0.000	0	0	0	23520
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	600	1817.454	0.000	0	0	0	6720
DOCI	4408246.2	3768657.3	2361895.20	3980230.8	5598566.4	0	14608759
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	3520	8947.684	0.000	0	0	0	24640
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSF	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	3572	7450.655	0.000	0	0	0	20003.199
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	327352	228332.46	202188.000	269584	336980	67396	808752
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	1600	5986.652	0.000	0	0	0	22400
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	3880	14517.631	0.000	0	0	0	54320
PD	946050	2927370.1	88200.000	137200	176400	39200	11103400
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
VAR63	26145	97825.632	0.000	0	0	0	366030
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	148	553.765	0.000	0	0	0	2072
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	1172.8	1924.36	0.000	0	4104.8	0	4104.8
TRIS	8330	31168.006	0.000	0	0	0	116620
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	33340326	20097451	20051310.0	25751933	43619236	10478068	77819888

September 17

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	11577.6	33447.351	0.000	0	0	0	121564.8
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	45.6	170.62	0.000	0	0	0	638.4
ANJU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APFL	46676127	28765969	24002866.0	46046314	49720220	13960850	1.242e+08

APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	21384	16540.363	11088.000	16632	33264	0	55440
CDSP	57036	23163.365	41160.000	61740	65856	24696	107016
CEHI	7502598.4	4212231.8	4438157.00	6052032	11431616	2151833.5	15197325
CHLSP	17100	22978.892	4788.000	9576	19152	0	90972
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	32169.6	63925.439	0.000	0	75062.398	0	225187.2
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	125698.8	116079.12	56767.200	85150.8	227068.8	0	340603.2
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DECO	240	897.998	0.000	0	0	0	3360
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	720	1945.219	0.000	0	0	0	6720
DOCI	7010704.8	3583849.1	4898745.60	5554827.6	7610551.2	3674059.2	16183356
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	37840	27954.055	12320.000	36960	61600	0	86240
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OBOO	4286.4	11580.537	0.000	0	0	0	40006.398
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	211816	247779.85	67396.000	101094	404376	0	741356
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	3880	14517.631	0.000	0	0	0	54320
PD	176400	94780.978	117600.000	176400	186200	49000	431200
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	833.6	3119.046	0.000	0	0	0	11670.4
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	74	276.883	0.000	0	0	0	1036
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	2054.4	7686.861	0.000	0	0	0	28761.6
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	61892585	30358285	38604412.0	58611974	63132108	28724074	1.456e+08

September 23

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	14472	34115.029	0.000	0	0	0	121564.8
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	136.8	206.269	0.000	0	319.2	0	638.4
ANJU	1140	2021.569	0.000	0	3192	0	6384
APFL	82260550	41593589	50944856.0	73723084	83275248	35514444	1.683e+08
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	6336	14885.192	0.000	0	11088	0	55440
CDSP	20580	18757.959	0.000	16464	32928	0	49392
CEHI	24726874	15398719	16407731.0	19500992	29318732	7800397	64958476
CHLSP	60192	69046.221	9576.000	40698	90972	0	253764
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	53615.999	68597.539	0.000	0	150124.8	0	150124.8
CLLT	10723.2	27257.898	0.000	0	0	0	75062.398
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	664987.2	719237.23	113534.400	340603.2	1078576.8	0	2327455.2
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	374.4	800.982	0.000	0	0	0	2620.8
DECO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	240	897.998	0.000	0	0	0	3360
DOCI	7754264.4	3665816	5248656.00	6910730.4	10759745	2624328	15920923
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	110880	83837.299	36960.000	110880	160160	12320	283360
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

GYSP	436	1631.363	0.000	0	0	0	6104
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	8288	16175.897	0.000	0	6630.4	0	56358.398
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	4286.4	8517.669	0.000	0	0	0	20003.199
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	803938	758116.53	269584.000	505470	1213128	0	2561048
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	3880	14517.631	0.000	0	0	0	54320
PD	174300	278254.66	19600.000	58800	274400	0	1058400
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	3751.2	6714.73	0.000	0	5835.2	0	17505.6
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	1.167e+08	53136020	74215112.0	1.027e+08	1.330e+08	58127752	2.130e+08

October 9

	mean	s.d.	p25	Median	p75	min	max
ACHA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ACSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANSP	23155.201	30631.452	0.000	0	40521.602	0	81043.203
ANAR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ANFA	68.4	184.796	0.000	0	0	0	638.4
ANJU	1173.6	2005.005	0.000	0	3192	0	6384
APFL	55458516	16409058	45556460.0	51067322	69069472	36249224	90133208
APIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
APSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ASFO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

AUDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
AUGRA	7128	8259.965	0.000	5544	11088	0	22176
CDSP	17640	12445.614	8232.000	16464	24696	0	41160
CEHI	6714873.6	3543552.9	4572646.50	5648563.3	7800397	2151833.5	14928346
CHLSP	51642	30582.056	23940.000	50274	62244	14364	129276
CHDI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CLLT	134040	141745.44	0.000	75062.398	225187.2	0	450374.41
CRQU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRRI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
CRPTSP	198685.2	163241.29	56767.200	198685.2	283836	0	567672
DESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEBI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DECO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEIN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DEOP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOCI	3505352.4	3465714	1312164.00	2055723.6	5248656	87477.6	13034162
DOPL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
DOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
ERGI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
EUSP	54560	66206.814	12320.000	30800	49280	0	221760
FRCR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GRLA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
GYSB	436	1631.363	0.000	0	0	0	6104
KILU	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KISP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
KOSP	2841.6	3405.059	0.000	1657.6	6630.4	0	9945.6
MEVA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MEGL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MIAE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOCOV	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
MOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OOBO	2857.6	7263.892	0.000	0	0	0	20003.199
OOSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
OCSP	1087964	715627.64	539168.000	943544	1684900	0	2358860
PAMO	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEPE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEAN	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PEDU	11640	31447.707	0.000	0	0	0	108640
PD	99400	58907.594	58800.000	102900	137200	0	215600
PESP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PHSP	1667.2	3566.765	0.000	0	0	0	11670.4
VAR63	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
PSSP	93.6	350.219	0.000	0	0	0	1310.4
PTSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUCH	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
QUSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCBI	336	1257.197	0.000	0	0	0	4704
SCEL	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCOB	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SCSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0

SCSE	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SNSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
SPSC	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
STNI	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TECA	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRSP	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
TRIS	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNCCY	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
UNSPCH2	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
WICR	0	0	0.000	0	0	0	0
Sum	67374070	18847710	55582872.0	60795120	83467328	43516564	1.129e+08

Appendix 10. Evenness(E), Shannon (H') and Simpson (D) diversity indices for each phytoplankton sample. The first two capitalized letters are month, followed by day, the sample location C = corral, O= lake.

Name	E	H'	D
JN18C1	0.481	1.602	0.664
JN18C2	0.36	1.04	0.3962
JN18C3	0.606	1.75	0.7813
JN18C4	0.429	1.161	0.5149
JN18C5	0.577	1.667	0.7442
JN18C6	0.467	1.375	0.6707
JN18C7	0.505	1.431	0.6159
JN18C8	0.511	1.555	0.7226
JN18C9	0.389	1.183	0.5182
JN18O1	0.259	0.664	0.2738
JN18O2	0.304	0.843	0.3307
JN18O3	0.426	1.059	0.4598
JN18O4	0.486	1.315	0.6503
JN18O5	0.309	0.858	0.356
JUL1C1	0.036	0.079	0.0238
JUL1C2	0.451	0.938	0.5434
JUL1C3	0.061	0.164	0.0515
JUL1C4	0.051	0.106	0.0356
JUL1C5	0.403	0.967	0.5532
JUL1C6	0.107	0.266	0.1016
JUL1C7	0.162	0.448	0.1902
JUL1C8	0.067	0.173	0.0571
JUL1C9	0.133	0.319	0.1195
JUL1O1	0.086	0.214	0.0775
JUL1O2	0.079	0.218	0.078
JUL1O3	0.106	0.287	0.1034
JUL1O4	0.05	0.133	0.0401
JUL17C1	0.344	0.755	0.3212

JUL17C2	0.755	1.353	0.6948
JUL17C3	0.576	1.326	0.6648
JUL17C4	0.382	0.979	0.4839
JUL17C5	0.664	1.382	0.6743
JUL17C6	0.593	1.365	0.6674
JUL17C7	0.484	1.277	0.6531
JUL17C8	0.409	0.9	0.4735
JUL17C9	0.472	1.211	0.6311
JUL17O1	0.29	0.603	0.3406
JUL17O2	0.348	0.836	0.507
JUL17O3	0.192	0.443	0.2136
JUL17O4	0.425	1.09	0.5467
JUL22C1	0.306	0.734	0.327
JUL22C2	0.266	0.554	0.2355
JUL22C3	0.433	1.11	0.5144
JUL22C5	0.534	1.326	0.5732
JUL22C6	0.516	1.43	0.6432
JUL22C7	0.689	1.514	0.6813
JUL22C8	0.307	0.675	0.2933
JUL22C9	0.631	1.386	0.7004
JUL22O1	0.171	0.375	0.1462
JUL22O2	0.223	0.399	0.1809
JUL22O3	0.056	0.109	0.0334
JUL22O4	0.27	0.593	0.2385
JUL22O5	0.486	0.871	0.4497
JUL29C1	0.49	1.579	0.7442
JUL29C2	0.37	1.069	0.5439
JUL29C3	0.397	1.147	0.5691
JUL29C4	0.492	1.332	0.6899
JUL29C5	0.508	1.438	0.6902
JUL29C6	0.571	1.507	0.7175
JUL29C7	0.539	1.493	0.7327
JUL29C8	0.5	1.242	0.6391
JUL29C9	0.491	1.391	0.7126
JUL29O1	0.426	1.353	0.6737
JUL29O2	0.505	1.369	0.6806
JUL29O3	0.474	1.343	0.618
JUL29O4	0.522	1.415	0.6763
JUL29O5	0.504	1.399	0.6825
AUG14C1	0.228	0.502	0.2653
AUG14C2	0.308	0.834	0.5249

AUG14C3	0.308	0.833	0.4861
AUG14C4	0.312	0.686	0.3761
AUG14C5	0.361	0.866	0.5179
AUG14C6	0.238	0.688	0.3967
AUG14C7	0.239	0.594	0.3053
AUG14C8	0.268	0.707	0.4181
AUG14C9	0.272	0.697	0.414
AUG14O1	0.239	0.614	0.3197
AUG14O2	0.315	0.783	0.3834
AUG14O3	0.451	0.937	0.5516
AUG14O4	0.07	0.173	0.0582
AUG14O5	0.382	0.98	0.5709
AUG19C1	0.44	1.093	0.5547
AUG19C2	0.388	0.853	0.5281
AUG19C3	0.462	1.107	0.5875
AUG19C4	0.182	0.399	0.1749
AUG19C5	0.484	1.064	0.5571
AUG19C6	0.424	1.054	0.5354
AUG19C7	0.501	1.286	0.6643
AUG19C8	0.354	0.908	0.4962
AUG19C9	0.551	1.268	0.664
AUG19O1	0.61	1.187	0.6074
AUG19O2	0.333	0.827	0.4272
AUG19O3	0.337	0.656	0.3624
AUG19O4	0.344	0.825	0.3964
AUG19O5	0.198	0.355	0.1491
AUG27C1	0.357	0.742	0.4892
AUG27C2	0.262	0.577	0.3384
AUG27C3	0.279	0.694	0.338
AUG27C4	0.025	0.048	0.013
AUG27C5	0.11	0.121	0.0439
AUG27C6	0.016	0.026	0.0064
AUG27C7	0.285	0.592	0.3078
AUG27C8	0.252	0.645	0.3367
AUG27C9	0.081	0.168	0.0556
AUG27O1	0.025	0.049	0.0129
AUG27O2	0.431	0.992	0.5613
AUG27O3	0.054	0.059	0.0197
AUG27O4	0.053	0.086	0.0299
AUG27O5	0.014	0.028	0.0073
SEPT4C1	0.334	0.802	0.395

SEPT4C2	0.482	1.157	0.6028
SEPT4C3	0.342	0.819	0.3779
SEPT4C4	0.553	1.272	0.6444
SEPT4C5	0.391	0.971	0.4682
SEPT4C6	0.24	0.65	0.3
SEPT4C7	0.346	0.888	0.4378
SEPT4C8	0.276	0.607	0.2739
SEPT4C9	0.382	0.948	0.4667
SEPT4O1	0.483	1.112	0.5872
SEPT4O2	0.362	0.795	0.421
SEPT4O3	0.343	0.853	0.4441
SEPT4O4	0.396	0.911	0.5185
SEPT4O5	0.353	0.814	0.4704
SEPT10C1	0.362	0.753	0.3627
SEPT10C2	0.292	0.642	0.311
SEPT10C3	0.262	0.575	0.3007
SEPT10C4	0.21	0.522	0.2031
SEPT10C5	0.263	0.548	0.2819
SEPT10C6	0.35	0.727	0.3344
SEPT10C7	0.486	0.871	0.4453
SEPT10C8	0.36	0.701	0.3517
SEPT10C9	0.307	0.597	0.3356
SEPT10O1	0.389	0.854	0.4366
SEPT10O2	0.467	1.119	0.5596
SEPT10O3	0.384	0.885	0.4595
SEPT10O4	0.386	0.889	0.4596
SEPT10O5	0.204	0.448	0.1663
SEPT17C1	0.306	0.706	0.3564
SEPT17C2	0.315	0.693	0.3576
SEPT17C3	0.279	0.642	0.3175
SEPT17C4	0.218	0.522	0.2589
SEPT17C5	0.457	1.137	0.6347
SEPT17C6	0.462	1.149	0.6348
SEPT17C7	0.327	0.811	0.4226
SEPT17C8	0.246	0.589	0.2991
SEPT17C9	0.507	1.215	0.6613
SEPT17O1	0.319	0.701	0.3572
SEPT17O2	0.376	0.782	0.414
SEPT17O3	0.292	0.727	0.3577
SEPT17O4	0.445	0.926	0.5304
SEPT17O5	0.273	0.568	0.2626

SEPT23C1	0.397	0.953	0.5267
SEPT23C2	0.348	0.801	0.4051
SEPT23C3	0.261	0.649	0.3357
SEPT23C4	0.327	0.814	0.4859
SEPT23C5	0.31	0.769	0.4083
SEPT23C6	0.297	0.761	0.3787
SEPT23C7	0.376	0.902	0.4265
SEPT23C8	0.354	0.907	0.4759
SEPT23C9	0.384	0.92	0.5375
SEPT23O1	0.297	0.737	0.397
SEPT23O2	0.322	0.801	0.4335
SEPT23O3	0.353	0.813	0.4463
SEPT23O4	0.439	0.965	0.5414
SEPT23O5	0.379	0.908	0.5273
OCT9C1	0.201	0.418	0.1952
OCT9C2	0.14	0.359	0.1432
OCT9C3	0.256	0.615	0.2811
OCT9C4	0.273	0.72	0.3451
OCT9C5	0.252	0.682	0.3046
OCT9C6	0.382	1.036	0.5247
OCT9C7	0.391	0.9	0.4703
OCT9C8	0.204	0.471	0.2185
OCT9C9	0.272	0.676	0.3201
OCT9O1	0.252	0.627	0.2927
OCT9O2	0.201	0.462	0.2115
OCT9O3	0.247	0.635	0.2941
OCT9O4	0.174	0.432	0.1738
OCT9O5	0.343	0.79	0.4129

Appendix 11. Linear regression results of ten most dominant phytoplankton taxa in relation to date sampled, in vs outside corals, and total phytoplankton biovolume

Appendix 11a. Best fit linear regression results of total phytoplankton biovolume (log transformed) as a function of date and inside vs. outside corals. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

logTotal	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-2.99	.239	-12.53	0	-3.462	-2.519	***
July 1	-.142	.243	-0.59	.559	-.623	.338	
July 17	-2.701	.243	-11.10	0	-3.181	-2.221	***
July 22	-3.542	.243	-14.56	0	-4.022	-3.062	***
July 29	-1.967	.239	-8.24	0	-2.438	-1.496	***
Aug 14	-.157	.239	-0.66	.512	-.628	.314	
Aug 19	-2.203	.239	-9.23	0	-2.675	-1.732	***
Aug 27	-1.682	.239	-7.05	0	-2.154	-1.211	***
Sept 4	-1.576	.239	-6.60	0	-2.047	-1.104	***

Sept 10	-1.336	.239	-5.60	0	-1.808	-.865	***
Sept 17	-.64	.239	-2.68	.008	-1.112	-.169	***
Sept 23base	0	
Oct 9	-.494	.239	-2.07	.04	-.965	-.023	**
InOutCode : base	0	
In							
Out	.014	.099	0.14	.887	-.181	.209	
Constant	18.483	.172	107.20	0	18.142	18.823	***
Mean dependent var		17.003	SD dependent var			1.267	
R-squared		0.770	Number of obs			179	
F-test		42.466	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11b. Best fit linear regression results of CEHI biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside corals, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtCEHI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-979.684	510.66	-1.92	.057	-1988	28.632	*
July 1	-2829.998	372.973	-7.59	0	-3566.447	-2093.549	***
July 17	239.939	492.497	0.49	.627	-732.514	1212.392	
July 22	419.917	563.153	0.75	.457	-692.048	1531.883	
July 29	-515.224	434.311	-1.19	.237	-1372.786	342.338	
Aug 14	319.421	366.026	0.87	.384	-403.31	1042.152	
Aug 19	206.564	450.171	0.46	.647	-682.313	1095.442	
Aug 27	1479.851	416.974	3.55	.001	656.52	2303.181	***
Sept 4	-1100.598	411.001	-2.68	.008	-1912.133	-289.063	***
Sept 10	-2238.635	398.769	-5.61	0	-3026.019	-1451.252	***
Sept 17	-1480.718	373.438	-3.97	0	-2218.085	-743.351	***
Sept 23b	0	
Oct 9	-1759.462	370.266	-4.75	0	-2490.565	-1028.36	***
InOut: base In	0	
Out	106.126	151.5	0.70	.485	-193.015	405.268	
logTotal	1018.176	119.239	8.54	0	782.735	1253.617	***
Constant	-14086.649	2219.614	-6.35	0	-18469.353	-9703.944	***
Mean dependent var		2630.972	SD dependent var			1713.771	
R-squared		0.707	Number of obs			179	
F-test		28.208	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11c. Best fit linear regression results of APFL biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside corals, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison dates.

sqrtAPFL	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-1400.726	699.441	-2.00	.047	-2781.797	-19.656	**
July 1	1323.192	510.854	2.59	.01	314.492	2331.892	**
July 17	-2654.687	674.564	-3.94	0	-3986.637	-1322.737	***
July 22	-1689.652	771.34	-2.19	.03	-3212.689	-166.615	**
July 29	-3361.625	594.867	-5.65	0	-4536.211	-2187.039	***
Aug 14	-156.156	501.339	-0.31	.756	-1146.066	833.755	
Aug 19	-3220.009	616.59	-5.22	0	-4437.487	-2002.531	***
Aug 27	-4764.572	571.122	-8.34	0	-5892.272	-3636.873	***
Sept 4	-1828.459	562.939	-3.25	.001	-2940.003	-716.916	***

Sept 10	-1710.614	546.186	-3.13	.002	-2789.078	-632.15	***
Sept 17	-1072.698	511.491	-2.10	.038	-2082.655	-62.741	**
Sept23b	0
Oct 9	-526.716	507.146	-1.04	.301	-1528.093	474.66	.
InOut: base In	0
Out	-246.392	207.506	-1.19	.237	-656.12	163.337	.
logTotal	1870.906	163.319	11.46	0	1548.427	2193.385	***
Constant	-25673.211	3040.161	-8.44	0	-31676.114	-19670.307	***
Mean dependent var		4421.452	SD dependent var			3681.934	
R-squared		0.881	Number of obs			179	
F-test		86.510	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11d. Best fit linear regression results of DOCI biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of sample date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtDOCI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-714.856	260.188	-2.75	.007	-1228.606	-201.107	***
July 1	-1851.869	190.035	-9.74	0	-2227.099	-1476.639	***
July 17	-1234.526	250.934	-4.92	0	-1730.003	-739.049	***
July 22	-726.751	286.934	-2.53	.012	-1293.312	-160.191	**
July 29	341.304	221.287	1.54	.125	-95.635	778.242	.
Aug 14	-1265.352	186.495	-6.78	0	-1633.592	-897.111	***
Aug 19	-1346.528	229.368	-5.87	0	-1799.423	-893.634	***
Aug 27	-1697.294	212.454	-7.99	0	-2116.791	-1277.796	***
Sept 4	-704.253	209.41	-3.36	.001	-1117.741	-290.766	***
Sept 10	-235.357	203.178	-1.16	.248	-636.539	165.825	.
Sept 17	160.85	190.272	0.85	.399	-214.848	536.548	.
Sept 23b	0
Oct 9	-808.003	188.655	-4.28	0	-1180.509	-435.497	***
InOut: base In	0
Out	-232.45	77.191	-3.01	.003	-384.866	-80.033	***
logTotal	454.137	60.754	7.48	0	334.177	574.097	***
Constant	-5599.083	1130.921	-4.95	0	-7832.126	-3366.04	***
Mean dependent var		1273.715	SD dependent var			1020.661	
R-squared		0.785	Number of obs			179	
F-test		42.831	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11e. Best fit linear regression results of CHLSP biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtCHLSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	342.81	143.455	2.39	.018	59.553	626.068	**
July 1	459.09	104.776	4.38	0	252.205	665.974	***
July 17	1140.85	138.353	8.25	0	867.666	1414.033	***
July 22	406.3	158.202	2.57	.011	93.925	718.676	**
July 29	687.712	122.007	5.64	0	446.804	928.62	***
Aug 14	12.784	102.825	0.12	.901	-190.247	215.814	.
Aug 19	156.5	126.463	1.24	.218	-93.205	406.205	.
Aug 27	158.063	117.137	1.35	.179	-73.228	389.354	.
Sept 4	438.881	115.459	3.80	0	210.904	666.859	***

Sept 10	474.907	112.023	4.24	0	253.714	696.1	***
Sept 17	-15.686	104.907	-0.15	.881	-222.828	191.456	
Sept 23b	0	
Oct 9	75.159	104.016	0.72	.471	-130.224	280.541	
InOutCode : base	0	
In							
Out	-190.272	42.56	-4.47	0	-274.307	-106.236	***
logTotal	127.274	33.497	3.80	0	61.134	193.415	***
Constant	-2079.026	623.537	-3.33	.001	-3310.222	-847.83	***
Mean dependent var		346.137	SD dependent var			392.453	
R-squared		0.558	Number of obs			179	
F-test		14.814	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11f. Best fit linear regression results of OCSP biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtOCSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-454.257	136.319	-3.33	.001	-723.424	-185.09	***
July 1	-601.276	99.564	-6.04	0	-797.868	-404.683	***
July 17	-432.023	131.471	-3.29	.001	-691.616	-172.43	***
July 22	-179.218	150.332	-1.19	.235	-476.054	117.617	
July 29	-474.231	115.938	-4.09	0	-703.154	-245.307	***
Aug 14	-211.103	97.71	-2.16	.032	-404.034	-18.172	**
Aug 19	-111.628	120.172	-0.93	.354	-348.911	125.655	
Aug 27	-530.423	111.31	-4.77	0	-750.209	-310.638	***
Sept 4	-415.687	109.715	-3.79	0	-632.324	-199.05	***
Sept 10	-88.188	106.45	-0.83	.409	-298.378	122.001	
Sept 17	-335.944	99.688	-3.37	.001	-532.781	-139.106	***
Sept23b	0	
Oct 9	245.619	98.841	2.48	.014	50.453	440.784	**
InOut: base In	0	
Out	38.345	40.442	0.95	.344	-41.51	118.2	
logTotal	106.981	31.83	3.36	.001	44.131	169.831	***
Constant	-1217.345	592.519	-2.05	.042	-2387.294	-47.396	**
Mean dependent var		341.318	SD dependent var			387.904	
R-squared		0.592	Number of obs			179	
F-test		16.987	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11g. Best fit linear regression results of PHRSP biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtPHRSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-70.993	177.991	-0.40	.691	-422.443	280.457	
July 1	-4.551	130.001	-0.04	.972	-261.241	252.14	
July 17	-65.293	171.661	-0.38	.704	-404.243	273.657	
July 22	-83.433	196.288	-0.43	.671	-471.011	304.144	
July 29	-11.408	151.38	-0.08	.94	-310.312	287.497	
Aug 14	755.264	127.579	5.92	0	503.355	1007.174	***
Aug 19	917.969	156.908	5.85	0	608.149	1227.788	***
Aug 27	323.04	145.337	2.22	.028	36.067	610.013	**
Sept 4	-37.404	143.255	-0.26	.794	-320.266	245.457	

Sept 10	11.489	138.992	0.08	.934	-262.955	285.933
Sept 17	-15.203	130.163	-0.12	.907	-272.214	241.807
Sept23b	0
Oct 9	-11.731	129.057	-0.09	.928	-266.558	243.096
InOut: base In	0
Out	-23.315	52.806	-0.44	.659	-127.581	80.951
logTotal	-23.74	41.561	-0.57	.569	-105.803	58.324
Constant	447.22	773.65	0.58	.564	-1080.379	1974.819
Mean dependent var		169.779	SD dependent var			453.884
R-squared		0.492	Number of obs			179
F-test		11.335	Prob > F			0.000

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11h. Best fit linear regression results of CRPTSP biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtCRPTSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	320.027	131.232	2.44	.016	60.906	579.149	**
July 1	-311.836	95.848	-3.25	.001	-501.092	-122.58	***
July 17	-116.344	126.564	-0.92	.359	-366.25	133.561	
July 22	-198.832	144.722	-1.37	.171	-484.59	86.926	
July 29	175.005	111.611	1.57	.119	-45.375	395.385	
Aug 14	-505.988	94.063	-5.38	0	-691.719	-320.257	***
Aug 19	-414.225	115.687	-3.58	0	-642.652	-185.797	***
Aug 27	-497.328	107.156	-4.64	0	-708.912	-285.745	***
Sept 4	-184.927	105.621	-1.75	.082	-393.479	23.625	*
Sept 10	-513.361	102.478	-5.01	0	-715.707	-311.016	***
Sept 17	-326.386	95.968	-3.40	.001	-515.877	-136.894	***
12b	0	
Oct 9	-258.863	95.153	-2.72	.007	-446.745	-70.981	***
InOutCode : base In	0	
Out	-143.439	38.933	-3.68	0	-220.313	-66.564	***
logTotal	109.928	30.643	3.59	0	49.423	170.433	***
Constant	-1286.779	570.406	-2.26	.025	-2413.066	-160.492	**
Mean dependent var		313.814	SD dependent var			349.588	
R-squared		0.534	Number of obs			179	
F-test		13.440	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11i. Best fit linear regression results of PD biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtPD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-26.629	134.314	-0.20	.843	-291.836	238.579	
July 1	-7.064	98.1	-0.07	.943	-200.765	186.637	
July 17	-9.402	129.537	-0.07	.942	-265.177	246.373	
July 22	-70.201	148.121	-0.47	.636	-362.67	222.268	
July 29	322.642	114.233	2.82	.005	97.086	548.198	***
Aug 14	-64.778	96.272	-0.67	.502	-254.871	125.315	
Aug 19	-133.192	118.404	-1.12	.262	-366.984	100.601	
Aug 27	-117.132	109.673	-1.07	.287	-333.684	99.421	

Sept 4	-143.676	108.101	-1.33	.186	-357.126	69.774	
Sept 10	270.804	104.884	2.58	.011	63.706	477.901	**
Sept 17	82.559	98.222	0.84	.402	-111.383	276.502	
Sept23b	0	
Oct 9	-31.952	97.387	-0.33	.743	-224.246	160.343	
InOut : base In	0	
Out	-217.594	39.848	-5.46	0	-296.274	-138.914	***
logTotal	8.146	31.362	0.26	.795	-53.78	70.071	
Constant	256.702	583.803	0.44	.661	-896.037	1409.442	
Mean dependent var		324.737	SD dependent var			300.309	
R-squared		0.339	Number of obs			179	
F-test		6.006	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11j. Best fit linear regression results of CLLT biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtCLLT	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	6.883	69.606	0.10	.921	-130.556	144.321	
July 1	176.145	50.838	3.46	.001	75.763	276.527	***
July 17	226.049	67.13	3.37	.001	93.498	358.599	***
July 22	101.848	76.761	1.33	.186	-49.719	253.414	
July 29	-30.843	59.199	-0.52	.603	-147.733	86.047	
Aug 14	47.907	49.891	0.96	.338	-50.605	146.419	
Aug 19	-16.007	61.361	-0.26	.795	-137.165	105.152	
Aug 27	-32.043	56.836	-0.56	.574	-144.267	80.182	
Sept 4	159.846	56.021	2.85	.005	49.23	270.462	***
Sept 10	-.095	54.354	-0.00	.999	-107.419	107.23	
Sept 17	56.167	50.902	1.10	.271	-44.34	156.674	
Sept23b	0	
Oct 9	256.061	50.469	5.07	0	156.408	355.714	***
InOut: base In	0	
Out	-23.924	20.65	-1.16	.248	-64.699	16.85	
logTotal	4.218	16.253	0.26	.796	-27.874	36.31	
Constant	-30.303	302.545	-0.10	.92	-627.688	567.082	
Mean dependent var		104.638	SD dependent var			160.241	
R-squared		0.376	Number of obs			179	
F-test		7.071	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 11k. Best fit linear regression results of CDSP biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtCDSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	136.282	43.856	3.11	.002	49.687	222.876	***
July 1	77.824	32.031	2.43	.016	14.577	141.07	**
July 17	-38.944	42.296	-0.92	.359	-122.458	44.571	
July 22	-52.833	48.364	-1.09	.276	-148.329	42.662	
July 29	135.681	37.299	3.64	0	62.034	209.329	***
Aug 14	-18.982	31.434	-0.60	.547	-81.051	43.086	
Aug 19	-5.275	38.661	-0.14	.892	-81.612	71.061	
Aug 27	7.447	35.81	0.21	.836	-63.26	78.155	
Sept 4	33.546	35.297	0.95	.343	-36.148	103.241	
Sept 10	70.729	34.246	2.07	.04	3.108	138.349	**

Sept 17	121.245	32.071	3.78	0	57.92	184.571	***
Sept23b	0
Oct 9	5.628	31.798	0.18	.86	-57.159	68.415	
InOut: base In	0
Out	-6.436	13.011	-0.49	.622	-32.126	19.255	
logTotal	6.586	10.24	0.64	.521	-13.634	26.805	
Constant	-2.444	190.621	-0.01	.99	-378.83	373.943	
Mean dependent var		144.291	SD dependent var			102.298	
R-squared		0.393	Number of obs			179	
F-test		7.572	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix III. Best fit linear regression results of AUGRA biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtAUGRA	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	112.969	36.764	3.07	.002	40.377	185.561	***
July 1	142.049	26.852	5.29	0	89.029	195.068	***
July 17	88.852	35.457	2.51	.013	18.842	158.863	**
July 22	59.553	40.543	1.47	.144	-20.501	139.607	
July 29	70.956	31.268	2.27	.025	9.217	132.695	**
Aug 14	18.664	26.352	0.71	.48	-33.368	70.696	
Aug 19	70.016	32.409	2.16	.032	6.023	134.01	**
Aug 27	65.57	30.019	2.18	.03	6.296	124.844	**
Sept 4	32.414	29.589	1.10	.275	-26.011	90.839	
Sept 10	15.564	28.709	0.54	.588	-41.122	72.251	
Sept 17	98.224	26.885	3.65	0	45.138	151.31	***
Sept23b	0
Oct 9	25.503	26.657	0.96	.34	-27.132	78.137	
InOut: base In	0
Out	-5.78	10.907	-0.53	.597	-27.316	15.756	
logTotal	12.152	8.584	1.42	.159	-4.798	29.102	
Constant	-183.216	159.798	-1.15	.253	-498.742	132.311	
Mean dependent var		82.350	SD dependent var			77.584	
R-squared		0.258	Number of obs			179	
F-test		4.071	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix III m. Best fit linear regression results of EUSP biovolume (sqrt transformed) as a function of date, inside vs. outside coralls, and total phytoplankton biovolume. Sept 23 was base comparison for dates.

sqrtEUSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
June 18	-212.482	43.195	-4.92	0	-297.772	-127.192	***
July 1	-247.82	31.548	-7.86	0	-310.114	-185.527	***
July 17	-211.429	41.659	-5.08	0	-293.685	-129.173	***
July 22	-214.567	47.635	-4.50	0	-308.624	-120.51	***
July 29	-250.383	36.737	-6.82	0	-322.921	-177.845	***
Aug 14	-250.138	30.961	-8.08	0	-311.271	-189.005	***
Aug 19	-261.242	38.078	-6.86	0	-336.429	-186.055	***
Aug 27	-272.248	35.27	-7.72	0	-341.891	-202.606	***
Sept 4	-127.776	34.765	-3.68	0	-196.421	-59.131	***
Sept 10	-257.133	33.73	-7.62	0	-323.735	-190.531	***
Sept 17	-126.357	31.588	-4.00	0	-188.728	-63.986	***

Sept23b	0
Oct 9	-96.988	31.319	-3.10	.002	-158.829	-35.146	***
InOut: base In	0
Out	-10.835	12.815	-0.85	.399	-36.138	14.469	.
logTotal	21.124	10.086	2.09	.038	1.209	41.039	**
Constant	-78.878	187.749	-0.42	.675	-449.595	291.839	.
Mean dependent var		82.490	SD dependent var			121.599	
R-squared		0.583	Number of obs			179	
F-test		16.377	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 12. Linear regression of total phytoplankton abundance vs. temperature.

logTOTAL	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TempC	-.262	.04	-6.52	0	-.342	-.183	***
Constant	23.021	.927	24.85	0	21.192	24.849	***
Mean dependent var		17.003	SD dependent var			1.267	
R-squared		0.194	Number of obs			179	
F-test		42.533	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Negative Solar days was a better predictor than temperature. As the days got shorter total biovolume tended to increase.

Linear regression

logTOTAL	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
negSolarDays	-.019	.003	-7.28	0	-.024	-.014	***
Constant	15.951	.167	95.64	0	15.622	16.281	***
Mean dependent var		17.003	SD dependent var			1.267	
R-squared		0.230	Number of obs			179	
F-test		53.014	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Temperature and negative solar days combined were better than separate.

Appendix 13. Linear regression of total phytoplankton abundance vs. daylight and temperature.

logTOTAL	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
negSolarDays	-.013	.004	-3.39	.001	-.021	-.006	***
TempC	-.104	.061	-1.72	.088	-.224	.016	*
Constant	18.64	1.575	11.83	0	15.531	21.748	***
Mean dependent var		17.003	SD dependent var			1.267	
R-squared		0.243	Number of obs			179	
F-test		28.271	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 14. SEM equation-level goodness of fit for each phytoplankton taxon.

depvars	Variance			R-squared	mc	mc2
	fitted	predicted	residual			
observed						
sqrtAPFL	1.62e+07	7389980	8808410	.4562169	.6754383	.4562169
sqrtOCSP	179699	101916.7	77782.22	.5671527	.7530954	.5671527
sqrtDOCI	1106143	494863.3	611279.8	.4473773	.6688627	.4473773
sqrtPHRSP	192263.3	60297.88	131965.4	.3136214	.5600191	.3136214
sqrtCEHI	3542457	2042054	1500403	.5764512	.7592439	.5764512
sqrtCHLSP	210022.5	32163.51	177858.9	.1531432	.3913352	.1531432
overall				.9077835		

mc = correlation between depvar and its prediction

mc2 = mc^2 is the Bentler-Raykov squared multiple correlation coefficient

Appendix 15. Best fit linear regression of taxa richness (s) as a function of total phytoplankton biovolume, sample date, and inside vs. outside corals.

s	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
logTotal	.795	.303	2.62	.01	.196	1.394	***
Date: base July18	0	
July 1	-7.653	1.283	-5.97	0	-10.186	-5.12	***
July 17	-7.618	.952	-8.00	0	-9.498	-5.738	***
July 22	-7.636	.963	-7.93	0	-9.537	-5.736	***
July 29	-1.385	.981	-1.41	.16	-3.322	.551	
Aug 14	-7.468	1.267	-5.90	0	-9.969	-4.966	***
Aug 19	-8.197	.96	-8.54	0	-10.094	-6.301	***
Aug 27	-11.183	1.011	-11.06	0	-13.18	-9.186	***
Sept 4	-7.697	1.024	-7.51	0	-9.719	-5.674	***
Sept 10	-10.172	1.057	-9.62	0	-12.259	-8.085	***
Sept 17	-9.297	1.172	-7.93	0	-11.612	-6.983	***
Sept 23	-8.664	1.299	-6.67	0	-11.23	-6.098	***
Oct 9	-7.842	1.2	-6.54	0	-10.211	-5.474	***
In vs Out: base In	0	
Out	-1.086	.386	-2.82	.005	-1.847	-.325	***
Constant	5.707	4.748	1.20	.231	-3.669	15.083	
Mean dependent var		11.559	SD dependent var			3.760	
R-squared		0.605	Number of obs			179	
F-test		17.959	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 16. Best fit linear regression of effective number of taxa, ENT as a function of total phytoplankton biovolume, sample date, and inside vs. outside corals.

ENT	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
logTotal	-.402	.073	-5.52	0	-.545	-.258	***
Date: base July18	0	
July 1	-1.09	.308	-3.54	.001	-1.697	-.482	***
July 17	-.622	.228	-2.72	.007	-1.073	-.171	***
July 22	-1.3	.231	-5.63	0	-1.756	-.844	***
July 29	.679	.235	2.89	.004	.215	1.143	***
Aug 14	-.47	.304	-1.55	.124	-1.07	.13	

Aug 19	-.751	.23	-3.26	.001	-1.206	-.296	***
Aug 27	-1.653	.243	-6.81	0	-2.132	-1.174	***
Sept 4	-.604	.246	-2.46	.015	-1.089	-.119	**
Sept 10	-.912	.254	-3.60	0	-1.412	-.411	***
Sept 17	-.452	.281	-1.61	.11	-1.007	.103	
Sept 23	-.155	.312	-0.50	.619	-.771	.46	
Oct 9	-.757	.288	-2.63	.009	-1.325	-.189	***
InOut: base In	0	
Out	-.385	.092	-4.17	0	-.568	-.203	***
Constant	10.034	1.139	8.81	0	7.785	12.283	***
Mean dependent var		2.453	SD dependent var			0.960	
R-squared		0.652	Number of obs			179	
F-test		21.909	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 17. Best fit linear regression of Evenness, e as a function of total phytoplankton biovolume, sample date, and inside vs. outside corals.

e	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
logTotal	-.084	.012	-7.15	0	-.107	-.061	***
Date: base July18	0	
July 1	-.062	.05	-1.24	.218	-.16	.037	
July 17	.042	.037	1.14	.258	-.031	.115	
July 22	-.105	.037	-2.82	.005	-.179	-.032	***
July 29	.135	.038	3.54	.001	.06	.21	***
Aug 14	.087	.049	1.77	.078	-.01	.184	*
Aug 19	.03	.037	0.82	.416	-.043	.104	
Aug 27	-.166	.039	-4.23	0	-.244	-.089	***
Sept 4	.06	.04	1.51	.133	-.018	.138	
Sept 10	.04	.041	0.98	.33	-.041	.121	
Sept 17	.106	.045	2.32	.021	.016	.195	**
Sept 23	.161	.05	3.20	.002	.062	.261	***
Oct 9	.03	.047	0.64	.522	-.062	.122	
InOut: base In	0	
Out	-.05	.015	-3.31	.001	-.079	-.02	***
Constant	1.757	.184	9.54	0	1.394	2.121	***
Mean dependent var		0.339	SD dependent var			0.148	
R-squared		0.615	Number of obs			179	
F-test		18.675	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 18. Best fit linear regression of Shannon diversity, h , as a function of total phytoplankton biovolume, sample date, and inside vs. outside corals.

h	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
logTotal	-.162	.029	-5.59	0	-.219	-.105	***
Date: base July18	0	
July 1	-.465	.123	-3.79	0	-.707	-.223	***
July 17	-.171	.091	-1.88	.062	-.351	.009	*
July 22	-.483	.092	-5.25	0	-.665	-.302	***
July 29	.278	.094	2.97	.003	.093	.463	***
Aug 14	-.085	.121	-0.70	.486	-.324	.154	
Aug 19	-.203	.092	-2.21	.029	-.384	-.021	**
Aug 27	-.694	.097	-7.18	0	-.884	-.503	***

Sept 4	-.121	.098	-1.24	.218	-.314	.072	
Sept 10	-.259	.101	-2.56	.011	-.458	-.059	**
Sept 17	-.072	.112	-0.64	.522	-.293	.149	
Sept 23	.07	.124	0.56	.575	-.175	.315	
Oct 9	-.216	.115	-1.88	.062	-.442	.011	*
InOut: base In	0	
Out	-.15	.037	-4.07	0	-.223	-.077	***
Constant	3.814	.454	8.40	0	2.918	4.71	***
Mean dependent var		0.824	SD dependent var			0.385	
R-squared		0.657	Number of obs			179	
F-test		22.394	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 19. Best fit linear regression of Simpson Diversity, d as a function of total phytoplankton biovolume, sample date, and inside vs. outside corals.

d	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
logTotal	-.082	.016	-5.00	0	-.114	-.05	***
Date: base July18	0	
July 1	-.168	.069	-2.43	.016	-.305	-.032	**
July 17	-.001	.051	-0.02	.981	-.103	.1	
July 22	-.207	.052	-3.98	0	-.31	-.104	***
July 29	.203	.053	3.84	0	.099	.308	***
Aug 14	.081	.068	1.19	.236	-.054	.216	
Aug 19	-.007	.052	-0.13	.9	-.109	.096	
Aug 27	-.26	.055	-4.76	0	-.368	-.152	***
Sept 4	.024	.055	0.43	.669	-.086	.133	
Sept 10	-.057	.057	-0.99	.322	-.169	.056	
Sept 17	.062	.063	0.97	.333	-.063	.186	
Sept 23	.147	.07	2.09	.038	.008	.285	**
Oct 9	-.046	.065	-0.71	.476	-.174	.082	
InOutCode : base	0	
In							
Out	-.072	.021	-3.47	.001	-.113	-.031	***
Constant	1.845	.256	7.19	0	1.339	2.351	***
Mean dependent var		0.411	SD dependent var			0.197	
R-squared		0.579	Number of obs			179	
F-test		16.133	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 20. Linear regression relationships between phytoplankton biovolume ($\log_{10} \text{TOTAL}$) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

$\log_{10} \text{TOTAL}$	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TSS	.011	.005	2.41	.018	.002	.02	**
ORP	.013	.004	3.04	.003	.004	.021	***
conductivity	-.014	.002	-6.67	0	-.019	-.01	***
Al	1.012	.304	3.33	.001	.41	1.615	***
Mg	.163	.019	8.50	0	.125	.201	***
NO ₂	-12.86	5.313	-2.42	.017	-23.399	-2.322	**
Constant	28.965	3.542	8.18	0	21.938	35.992	***
Mean dependent var		17.220	SD dependent var			1.267	

R-squared	0.685	Number of obs	108
F-test	36.621	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	245.876	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	264.651

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 21. Linear regression relationships between *Aphanizomenon flosaquae* (sqrtAPFL) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC. dP = dissolved phosphorus.

sqrtAPFL	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TSS	57.616	11.748	4.90	0	34.317	80.915	***
K	1063.634	142.808	7.45	0	780.409	1346.859	***
conductivity	-45.597	6.695	-6.81	0	-58.875	-32.319	***
dP	-36049.945	10259.941	-3.51	.001	-56398.117	-15701.772	***
Constant	59693.761	10132.369	5.89	0	39598.597	79788.925	***
Mean dependent var		4998.241	SD dependent var			4037.767	
R-squared		0.547	Number of obs			108	
F-test		31.044	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 22. Linear regression relationships between *Dolichospermum circinalis* (sqrtDOCI) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtDOCI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Ortho P	-16415.448	2097.938	-7.82	0	-20577.697	-12253.199	***
pH	3100.377	692.74	4.48	0	1726.001	4474.754	***
NO ₃	2129.711	508.595	4.19	0	1120.673	3138.748	***
conductivity	-4.866	1.569	-3.10	.003	-7.978	-1.753	***
Mg	153.559	18.796	8.17	0	116.267	190.85	***
DO	-218.191	64.591	-3.38	.001	-346.337	-90.045	***
Fe	733.693	218.162	3.36	.001	300.865	1166.52	***
Constant	-24527.78	5539.69	-4.43	0	-35518.367	-13537.193	***
Mean dependent var		1323.494	SD dependent var			1056.637	
R-squared		0.677	Number of obs			108	
F-test		29.943	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 23. Linear regression relationships between *Oscillatoria* sp. (sqrtOCSP) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtOCSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Mg	81.287	7.829	10.38	0	65.758	96.816	***
ORP	6.41	1.518	4.22	0	3.399	9.42	***
TP	-934.312	188.508	-4.96	0	-1308.218	-560.407	***
Al	222.722	85.639	2.60	.011	52.858	392.586	**
NO ₃	757.54	193.169	3.92	0	374.391	1140.689	***
Constant	-5539.429	538.341	-10.29	0	-6607.225	-4471.633	***
Mean dependent var		336.955	SD dependent var			428.771	
R-squared		0.568	Number of obs			108	
F-test		26.863	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 24. Linear regression relationships between *Phormidium sp.* (sqrtPHRSP) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtPHRSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Al	918.454	128.121	7.17	0	664.386	1172.522	***
Ca	-28.893	6.629	-4.36	0	-42.038	-15.748	***
Mg	-27.324	9.41	-2.90	.005	-45.985	-8.663	***
Constant	3041.449	817.16	3.72	0	1420.99	4661.909	***
Mean dependent var		151.453	SD dependent var			443.759	
R-squared		0.333	Number of obs			108	
F-test		17.310	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 25. Linear regression relationships between *Ceratium hirundinella* (sqrtCEHI) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtCEHI	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TSS	48.628	5.297	9.18	0	38.124	59.133	***
TP	2051.544	722.209	2.84	.005	619.212	3483.875	***
Ca	-71.67	18.292	-3.92	0	-107.947	-35.393	***
conductivity	9.898	2.516	3.93	0	4.909	14.887	***
Constant	-11660.623	4736.296	-2.46	.015	-21053.948	-2267.297	**
Mean dependent var		2776.833	SD dependent var			1886.711	
R-squared		0.641	Number of obs			108	
F-test		45.889	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 26. Linear regression relationships between *Chlamydomonas sp.* (sqrtCHLSP) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtCHLSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
NO ₂	11120.354	2394.666	4.64	0	6369.981	15870.727	***
VSS	2010.229	276.02	7.28	0	1462.68	2557.777	***
COD	-12.6	2.873	-4.39	0	-18.299	-6.901	***
Ca	13.422	4.711	2.85	.005	4.076	22.768	***
NH ₃	-1403.872	967.478	-1.45	.15	-3323.087	515.343	
dP	-2610.396	1604.385	-1.63	.107	-5793.065	572.273	
Constant	-924.2	348.198	-2.65	.009	-1614.931	-233.469	***
Mean dependent var		434.409	SD dependent var			460.419	
R-squared		0.560	Number of obs			108	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		1555.374	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			1574.149	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 27. Linear regression relationships between pennate diatoms (PD) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtPD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOutCode : base	0	
In							
Out	-205.923	32.039	-6.43	0	-269.186	-142.66	***
sqrtCDSP	1.822	.192	9.49	0	1.443	2.201	***
DateCode : base	0	

July 18							
July 1	115.096	79.111	1.45	.148	-41.111	271.304	
July 17	335.352	85.481	3.92	0	166.567	504.137	***
July 22	303.097	86.99	3.48	.001	131.333	474.861	***
July 29	346.421	77.265	4.48	0	193.859	498.983	***
Aug 14	233.807	81.583	2.87	.005	72.718	394.895	***
Aug 19	148.305	81.569	1.82	.071	-12.755	309.366	*
Aug 27	139.179	80.627	1.73	.086	-20.023	298.38	*
Sept 4	64.673	79.309	0.82	.416	-91.925	221.271	
Sept 10	410.489	77.965	5.27	0	256.545	564.433	***
Sept 17	127.528	77.256	1.65	.101	-25.016	280.072	
Sept 23	263.397	80.431	3.27	.001	104.584	422.21	***
Oct 9	223.095	80.305	2.78	.006	64.53	381.661	***
Constant	-73.449	71.862	-1.02	.308	-215.343	68.445	
Mean dependent var		324.737	SD dependent var			300.309	
R-squared		0.573	Number of obs			179	
F-test		15.731	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 28. Linear regression relationships between centric diatoms (CDSP) and predictors suggested by LASSO and reevaluated using AIC and BIC.

sqrtCDSP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
sqrtPD	.178	.022	8.23	0	.135	.221	***
ORP	1.08	.458	2.36	.02	.171	1.989	**
VSS	-153.206	56.219	-2.73	.008	-264.801	-41.611	***
sqrtAUGRA	.208	.098	2.12	.037	.013	.403	**
NO ₃	176.838	45.997	3.84	0	85.535	268.141	***
OrthoP	-1255.346	283.271	-4.43	0	-1817.635	-693.057	***
sqrtOCSP	-.068	.023	-3.00	.003	-.113	-.023	***
TDS	-.054	.032	-1.66	.1	-.118	.01	*
Ca	-1.005	1.286	-0.78	.437	-3.556	1.547	
TSS	.632	.346	1.83	.071	-.055	1.32	*
Temperature	-8.983	5.663	-1.59	.116	-20.225	2.258	
Constant	314.513	163.244	1.93	.057	-9.524	638.55	*
Mean dependent var		152.575	SD dependent var			111.498	
R-squared		0.625	Number of obs			108	
F-test		14.521	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 29. Full SEM model.

Structural equation model
 Estimation method = ml
 Log likelihood = -5560.3625
 Number of obs = 108

Standardized	OIM Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	[95% Conf. Interval]	
Structural						
sqrtAPFL						
sqrtDOCI	.5291925	.0699532	7.56	0.000	.3920869	.6662982
sqrtCEHI	.2552475	.0824185	3.10	0.002	.0937103	.4167848
orthopmgl	.235548	.0794362	2.97	0.003	.079856	.39124
camgl	.3895805	.0745941	5.22	0.000	.2433787	.5357823
_cons	-3.777176	.6643805	-5.69	0.000	-5.079337	-2.475014
sqrtOCSP						
sqrtAPFL	.4180902	.0646563	6.47	0.000	.2913662	.5448141
tpmgl	-.2708561	.0712372	-3.80	0.000	-.4104785	-.1312336
mgmgl	.6123018	.0653771	9.37	0.000	.484165	.7404385
_cons	-7.229289	.7311406	-9.89	0.000	-8.662298	-5.79628
sqrtDOCI						
orthopmgl	-.3375375	.0774082	-4.36	0.000	-.4892549	-.1858202
tpmgl	.2000922	.08772	2.28	0.023	.0281643	.3720202
mgmgl	.5645737	.0750838	7.52	0.000	.4174123	.7117352
camgl	.1588313	.0781891	2.03	0.042	.0055834	.3120791
_cons	-7.037224	1.300732	-5.41	0.000	-9.586611	-4.487836
sqrtPHRSP						
sqrtDOCI	-.294436	.0806797	-3.65	0.000	-.4525652	-.1363068
femgl	.7389118	.096801	7.63	0.000	.5491852	.9286383
camgl	-.5548118	.1034792	-5.36	0.000	-.7576274	-.3519962
_cons	4.48544	.8219846	5.46	0.000	2.874379	6.0965
sqrtCEHI						
sqrtPHRSP	.1381928	.0728654	1.90	0.058	-.0046207	.2810063
femgl	.5217277	.1000361	5.22	0.000	.3256605	.717795
orthopmgl	.1501487	.0689919	2.18	0.030	.014927	.2853704
tpmgl	.3393135	.0724461	4.68	0.000	.1973217	.4813054
camgl	-.5763001	.0978592	-5.89	0.000	-.7681006	-.3844997
_cons	5.114565	.7958451	6.43	0.000	3.554737	6.674392
sqrtCHLSP						
femgl	-.4534339	.1113455	-4.07	0.000	-.6716671	-.2352006
camgl	.4868005	.1102353	4.42	0.000	.2707433	.7028578
_cons	-2.702142	.8874839	-3.04	0.002	-4.441578	-.9627054
mean(femgl)	1.757918	.1535125	11.45	0.000	1.457039	2.058797
mean(orthopmgl)	1.772664	.1542956	11.49	0.000	1.470251	2.075078
mean(tpmgl)	1.16268	.1245701	9.33	0.000	.9185273	1.406833
mean(mgmgl)	12.77126	.8742855	14.61	0.000	11.05769	14.48483
mean(camgl)	9.135466	.6289937	14.52	0.000	7.902661	10.36827
var(e.sqrtAPFL)	.5437831	.0702614			.4221271	.7005
var(e.sqrtOCSP)	.4328473	.0612343			.3280321	.5711539
var(e.sqrtDOCI)	.5526227	.0711351			.4293977	.7112097
var(e.sqrtPHRSP)	.6863786	.0714769			.5596581	.8417919
var(e.sqrtCEHI)	.4235488	.0618796			.318086	.5639781
var(e.sqrtCHLSP)	.8468568	.0637789			.7306407	.9815583
var(femgl)	1	.			.	.
var(orthopmgl)	1	.			.	.
var(tpmgl)	1	.			.	.
var(mgmgl)	1	.			.	.
var(camgl)	1	.			.	.
cov(femgl,orthopmgl)	.0328968	.0961209	0.34	0.732	-.1554968	.2212903
cov(femgl,tpmgl)	-.0693518	.0957622	-0.72	0.469	-.2570423	.1183388
cov(femgl,mgmgl)	.0917647	.0954148	0.96	0.336	-.0952447	.2787742
cov(femgl,camgl)	.6556232	.0548635	11.95	0.000	.5480927	.7631537
cov(orthopmgl,tpmgl)	.3848978	.0819697	4.70	0.000	.2242402	.5455554
cov(orthopmgl,mgmgl)	.0347864	.0961086	0.36	0.717	-.153583	.2231558
cov(orthopmgl,camgl)	-.0414018	.0960601	-0.43	0.666	-.2296762	.1468725
cov(tpmgl,mgmgl)	.4274929	.0786399	5.44	0.000	.2733615	.5816242
cov(tpmgl,camgl)	-.303779	.0873452	-3.48	0.001	-.4749725	-.1325855
cov(mgmgl,camgl)	-.3737428	.082784	-4.51	0.000	-.5359964	-.2114892

Appendix 30. SEM direct effects.

Direct effects

	OIM				Std. Coef.
	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	
Structural					
sqrtAPFL					
sqrtDOCI	2.025	0.290	6.984	0.000	0.529
sqrtPHRSP	0.000	(no path)			0.000
sqrtCEHI	0.546	0.178	3.069	0.002	0.255
femgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
orthopmgl	27545.217	9332.640	2.951	0.003	0.236
tpmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
mgmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
camgl	222.694	43.478	5.122	0.000	0.390
<hr/>					
sqrtOCSP					
sqrtAPFL	0.044	0.007	6.316	0.000	0.418
sqrtDOCI	0.000	(no path)			0.000
sqrtPHRSP	0.000	(no path)			0.000
sqrtCEHI	0.000	(no path)			0.000
femgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
orthopmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
tpmgl	-632.576	164.049	-3.856	0.000	-0.271
mgmgl	56.533	6.633	8.523	0.000	0.612
camgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
<hr/>					
sqrtDOCI					
orthopmgl	-1.03e+04	2399.919	-4.298	0.000	-0.338
tpmgl	1159.411	510.416	2.272	0.023	0.200
mgmgl	129.327	19.080	6.778	0.000	0.565
camgl	23.726	11.705	2.027	0.043	0.159
<hr/>					
sqrtPHRSP					
sqrtDOCI	-0.123	0.034	-3.589	0.000	-0.294
femgl	1035.215	151.475	6.834	0.000	0.739
orthopmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
tpmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
mgmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
camgl	-34.552	6.735	-5.130	0.000	-0.555
<hr/>					
sqrtCEHI					
sqrtDOCI	0.000	(no path)			0.000
sqrtPHRSP	0.593	0.314	1.892	0.058	0.138
femgl	3137.515	589.552	5.322	0.000	0.522
orthopmgl	8211.163	3766.954	2.180	0.029	0.150
tpmgl	3518.480	764.829	4.600	0.000	0.339
mgmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
camgl	-154.055	25.910	-5.946	0.000	-0.576
<hr/>					
sqrtCHLSP					
femgl	-663.952	171.719	-3.867	0.000	-0.453
camgl	31.685	7.633	4.151	0.000	0.487

Appendix 31. SEM indirect effects

Indirect effects

	OIM		z	P> z	Std. Coef.
	Coef.	Std. Err.			
Structural					
sqrtAPFL					
sqrtDOCI	-0.040	0.027	-1.469	0.142	-0.010
sqrtPHRSP	0.324	0.201	1.611	0.107	0.035
sqrtCEHI	0.000	(no path)			0.000
femgl	2047.672	724.109	2.828	0.005	0.159
orthopmgl	-1.60e+04	6367.974	-2.512	0.012	-0.137
tpmgl	4222.269	1260.485	3.350	0.001	0.190
mgmgl	256.758	53.688	4.782	0.000	0.293
camgl	-48.169	42.920	-1.122	0.262	-0.084
<hr/>					
sqrtOCSP					
sqrtAPFL	0.000	(no path)			0.000
sqrtDOCI	0.087	0.019	4.611	0.000	0.217
sqrtPHRSP	0.014	0.009	1.561	0.119	0.015
sqrtCEHI	0.024	0.009	2.760	0.006	0.107
femgl	90.171	34.937	2.581	0.010	0.067
orthopmgl	508.556	443.881	1.146	0.252	0.041
tpmgl	185.931	62.831	2.959	0.003	0.080
mgmgl	11.307	2.966	3.813	0.000	0.122
camgl	7.685	2.634	2.918	0.004	0.128
<hr/>					
sqrtDOCI					
orthopmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
tpmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
mgmgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
camgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
<hr/>					
sqrtPHRSP					
sqrtDOCI	0.000	(no path)			0.000
femgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
orthopmgl	1266.170	459.634	2.755	0.006	0.099
tpmgl	-142.322	74.151	-1.919	0.055	-0.059
mgmgl	-15.875	5.005	-3.172	0.002	-0.166
camgl	-2.912	1.650	-1.765	0.078	-0.047
<hr/>					
sqrtCEHI					
sqrtDOCI	-0.073	0.044	-1.674	0.094	-0.041
sqrtPHRSP	0.000	(no path)			0.000
femgl	614.073	336.779	1.823	0.068	0.102
orthopmgl	751.072	481.593	1.560	0.119	0.014
tpmgl	-84.423	62.657	-1.347	0.178	-0.008
mgmgl	-9.417	5.796	-1.625	0.104	-0.023
camgl	-22.223	12.479	-1.781	0.075	-0.083
<hr/>					
sqrtCHLSP					
femgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000
camgl	0.000	(no path)			0.000

Appendix 32. SEM total effects

Total effects

	OIM				Std. Coef.
	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z	
Structural					
sqrtAPFL					
sqrtDOCI	1.985	0.294	6.749	0.000	0.519
sqrtPHRSP	0.324	0.201	1.611	0.107	0.035
sqrtCEHI	0.546	0.178	3.069	0.002	0.255
femgl	2047.672	724.109	2.828	0.005	0.159
orthopmgl	11548.666	9912.734	1.165	0.244	0.099
tpmgl	4222.269	1260.485	3.350	0.001	0.190
mgmgl	256.758	53.688	4.782	0.000	0.293
camgl	174.525	53.052	3.290	0.001	0.305
sqrtOCSP					
sqrtAPFL	0.044	0.007	6.316	0.000	0.418
sqrtDOCI	0.087	0.019	4.611	0.000	0.217
sqrtPHRSP	0.014	0.009	1.561	0.119	0.015
sqrtCEHI	0.024	0.009	2.760	0.006	0.107
femgl	90.171	34.937	2.581	0.010	0.067
orthopmgl	508.556	443.881	1.146	0.252	0.041
tpmgl	-446.645	173.515	-2.574	0.010	-0.191
mgmgl	67.839	6.891	9.844	0.000	0.735
camgl	7.685	2.634	2.918	0.004	0.128
sqrtDOCI					
orthopmgl	-1.03e+04	2399.919	-4.298	0.000	-0.338
tpmgl	1159.411	510.416	2.272	0.023	0.200
mgmgl	129.327	19.080	6.778	0.000	0.565
camgl	23.726	11.705	2.027	0.043	0.159
sqrtPHRSP					
sqrtDOCI	-0.123	0.034	-3.589	0.000	-0.294
femgl	1035.215	151.475	6.834	0.000	0.739
orthopmgl	1266.170	459.634	2.755	0.006	0.099
tpmgl	-142.322	74.151	-1.919	0.055	-0.059
mgmgl	-15.875	5.005	-3.172	0.002	-0.166
camgl	-37.464	7.102	-5.275	0.000	-0.602
sqrtCEHI					
sqrtDOCI	-0.073	0.044	-1.674	0.094	-0.041
sqrtPHRSP	0.593	0.314	1.892	0.058	0.138
femgl	3751.588	515.552	7.277	0.000	0.624
orthopmgl	8962.235	3738.206	2.397	0.017	0.164
tpmgl	3434.057	758.800	4.526	0.000	0.331
mgmgl	-9.417	5.796	-1.625	0.104	-0.023
camgl	-176.279	24.040	-7.333	0.000	-0.659
sqrtCHLSP					
femgl	-663.952	171.719	-3.867	0.000	-0.453
camgl	31.685	7.633	4.151	0.000	0.487

Appendix 33. Linear regression of periphyton biomass by sample date. July 17 was base comparison.

Biomass	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
MonthDay base July17	0
Aug15	.118	.115	1.03	.312	-.116	.353	
Sept4	.356	.115	3.09	.004	.121	.591	***
Oct9	.399	.115	3.46	.002	.164	.634	***
Constant	.067	.082	0.82	.419	-.099	.233	
Mean dependent var		0.285	SD dependent var			0.288	
R-squared		0.339	Number of obs			36	
F-test		5.480	Prob > F			0.004	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		4.550	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			10.884	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 34. Linear regression of pennate diatom to centric diatom ratio (PD/CD) inside vs. outside of corals, and by date.

PDCD	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
InOutCode : base In	0
Out	-1.406	.203	-6.94	0	-1.807	-1.005	***
DateCode : base June 18	0
July 1	.559	.453	1.23	.22	-.337	1.455	
July 17	2.415	.522	4.63	0	1.383	3.446	***
July 22	1.762	.575	3.06	.003	.625	2.9	***
July 29	2.093	.445	4.71	0	1.214	2.972	***
Aug 14	1.299	.488	2.66	.009	.334	2.263	***
Aug 19	.613	.453	1.35	.178	-.283	1.509	
Aug 27	.192	.474	0.40	.687	-.746	1.129	
Sept 4	.075	.453	0.17	.868	-.821	.971	
Sept 10	2.008	.453	4.43	0	1.112	2.904	***
Sept 17	.552	.445	1.24	.217	-.327	1.431	
Sept 23	.845	.487	1.73	.085	-.118	1.808	*
Oct 9	1.007	.463	2.18	.031	.092	1.922	**
Constant	1.703	.323	5.28	0	1.065	2.341	***
Mean dependent var		2.169	SD dependent var			1.526	
R-squared		0.457	Number of obs			151	
F-test		8.885	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Most Utah Lake management emphasis has been on cyanobacteria and HABs, particularly on the potential toxin producers, *Aphanizomenon flosaquae*, *Dolichospermum* spp., primarily *D. circinalis*, and *Microcystis* sp. However, we have documented that the dinoflagellate, *Ceratium hirundinella* can be as abundant or more abundant than many of the cyanobacteria taxa as well as other phytoplankton taxa in Utah Lake (Richards et al 2024). The Richards and Miller (2024) ecosystem function model for Utah Lake had *C. hirundinella* as the most annually abundant phytoplankton taxon and it was the least grazed by zooplankton, although some zooplankton taxa are potential grazers (see below). *Ceratium hirundinella*, is the most widespread freshwater dinoflagellate, and is present in almost all water bodies of the world (Zarei-Darki and Krakhmalnyi 2019). *Ceratium hirundinella*'s size and shape limits most zooplankton grazing. Subsequently, *C. hirundinella* can have mostly unhindered impacts on Utah Lake's ecosystem function via competitive release from predators.

We have shown that *C. hirundinella* can have major effects on light attenuation (Chapter 3). This ecosystem effect alone dictates a better ecological understanding of this atypical phytoplankton species. Here we describe more of its biology and ecology.

Whittington et al. (2000) reported that:

“*Ceratium* dinoflagellates may reproduce sexually (two parent cells) or asexually (one parent cell) . In asexual reproduction, the pellicle (shell) pulls apart and exposes the naked cell. The cell then increases in size and divides, creating 4–8 daughter cells, each with two flagella. The nuclear membrane is present throughout the process and the centrioles are not present, unlike many other eukaryotic organisms. The nuclear membrane only divides when the waist of the organism constricts.

In sexual reproduction, the cells of two organisms couple close to their sulci (longitudinal groove). Meiosis occurs, which allows the chromosomes given by the haploid parents to pair. Then diploid offspring, known as "swarmers", are released.”

The formation of cysts is a characteristic of this group of algae which allows their survival in sediments and promotes the presence of the dinoflagellate in subsequent years. Thus, the cysts are over-wintering forms in temperate zones and over summering forms in subtropical areas (Pollinger et al. 1993). Because of their independent mobility they suffer low sedimentation losses, accumulate in the water column where light conditions are best, and they can obtain nutrients throughout the water column.

Dinoflagellates can also have two or three generations under low phosphorus concentration due to their capacity for luxury phosphorus consumption, allowing for better competition with other algae if phosphorus becomes limiting. *Ceratium* sp. also have relatively long generation times and their losses due to grazing are low by comparison with those of other planktonic algae (Pollinger 1988).

Ceratium species are often mixotrophic. They can be photosynthetic and heterotrophic, consuming other plankton. *Ceratium* spp. have a unique adaptation that allows them to store compounds in a vacuole that they can use for growth when nutrients become unavailable. *Ceratium* sp. are also known to actively move in the water column in order to receive maximum sunlight and nutrients for growth. They also can extend appendages during the day which contain chloroplasts to absorb light for photosynthesis. At night, they retract these appendages and move to deeper layers of the water column. *Ceratium hirundinella* as cyst can immobilize large amounts of nutrients and promotes a decrease in the overall activity of the ecosystem, associated with its long generation time and perennation during several months in the sediments (Pollinger 1988). Nitrate limitation and anoxia can negatively affect *Ceratium* development (Rengefors 1997, Pérez-Martínez & Sánchez-Castillo 2001; Pollinger 1988). The vertical distribution of *Ceratium* in the water column is a function of the interplay between vertical migration, water movement and turbulent mixing (George and Heaney, 1978; Harris et al., 1979; Heaney and Talling, 1980; Harris, 1983). These researchers found that overnight deepening of the surface mixed layer by convective cooling produced homogeneous distributions of *Ceratium* sp. with a significant proportion of the population below the depth where light saturation of photosynthesis occurred. *Ceratium* migrated towards the surface from suboptimal light intensities, at a velocity of $1.6\text{--}2.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Subsurface accumulations of *Ceratium* occurred under a variety of turbulence intensities; however, accumulation was significantly reduced when the turbulent velocity scale in the mixed layer was $>5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, beyond which turbulent diffusion dominated advection by swimming.

Ceratium hirundinella in Utah Lake are not known to produce toxic chemicals. However, under conditions that promote rapid population growth in oceans, *Ceratium* sp. blooms known as Red Tides can deplete resources and nutrients of the surrounding environment. These blooms deplete dissolved oxygen in the water, which is known to cause fish kills. We did not find any relationship between *C. hirundinella* and DO in this study.

Ceratium hirundinella can play an important role at the base of Utah Lake's food web. They are sources of nutrients for larger organisms and also prey on smaller organisms, including diatoms. Mac Donagh, Casco, and Claps (2005) found that the native *Peridinium* sp. (a dinophyte that also occurs in Utah Lake) decreased after a *C. hirundinella* invasion in a sub-tropical lake and that *Asplanchna* sp. became that dominant zooplankton after first bloom of *C. hirundinella*. *Asplanchna* sp. also occur in Utah Lake. Casco et al. (2002) showed that zooplankton showed a decrease in species richness and abundance, probably associated with the increase of *C. hirundinella* and to the detriment of palatable algae.

“Duarte et al. 2020 also concluded that phytoplankton communities with lower diversity were dominated by dinoflagellates and exhibit higher cell numbers and production than communities with higher diversity”

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Appendix 36. Summary statistics of zooplankton taxa by date sampled.

		DAPU	DARE	DAME	DIHE	CEDU	MOMI	PLAD	BOLO	ACAM	LESI	LESC	LEKI	KECO	HARP
29-Jul															
In	Mean	3.62	22.90	3.98	28.87	9.32	0.11	0.00	0.06	15.85	24.35	0.11	1.54	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.94	10.02	0.79	7.28	2.24	0.06	0.00	0.04	3.64	12.79	0.09	0.53	0.00	0.00
	Median	2.11	8.48	3.29	21.45	6.44	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.73	9.62	0.00	1.29	0.00	0.00
	25th	1.83	5.22	1.85	17.76	4.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.69	7.58	0.00	0.28	0.00	0.00
	75th	4.04	20.16	5.52	24.27	15.72	0.23	0.00	0.00	14.37	19.78	0.00	1.85	0.00	0.00
Out	Mean	2.75	37.91	7.20	43.69	14.61	0.05	0.00	0.05	22.17	39.13	0.74	0.30	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.49	9.26	2.52	9.92	9.05	0.05	0.00	0.05	5.67	11.07	0.74	0.18	0.00	0.00
	Median	2.22	41.53	5.92	44.43	9.66	0.00	0.00	0.00	20.36	33.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	2.21	25.16	5.55	35.53	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	17.02	16.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	2.74	56.28	6.76	45.34	14.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	28.01	62.79	0.00	0.74	0.00	0.00
Total	Mean	3.31	28.26	5.13	34.16	11.21	0.09	0.00	0.06	18.10	29.63	0.34	1.09	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.62	7.29	1.06	5.97	3.39	0.04	0.00	0.03	3.08	9.06	0.26	0.38	0.00	0.00
	Median	2.22	14.90	4.76	23.20	6.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	14.22	16.55	0.00	0.75	0.00	0.00
	25th	1.93	7.18	1.85	17.76	3.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	9.69	8.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	4.04	55.38	6.44	45.34	15.72	0.23	0.00	0.00	20.61	33.31	0.00	1.57	0.00	0.00

		DAPU	DARE	DAME	DIHE	CEDU	MOMI	PLAD	BOLO	ACAM	LESI	LESC	LEKI	KECO	HARP
14-Aug															
In	Mean	0.30	64.55	10.42	12.18	2.12	0.00	0.12	0.00	55.48	6.29	0.00	0.24	0.12	0.00
	S.E.	0.23	13.91	3.59	1.82	1.95	0.00	0.12	0.00	9.65	1.87	0.00	0.13	0.12	0.00
	Median	0.00	52.03	8.14	10.39	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	51.43	4.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	43.83	4.25	7.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	40.71	2.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	74.81	14.39	15.20	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	55.51	8.14	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00
Out	Mean	0.00	94.88	0.98	51.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	22.26	19.10	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	19.25	0.30	10.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.95	3.06	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	109.99	1.01	58.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	23.23	17.86	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	61.92	0.90	47.94	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	16.92	13.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

	75th	0.00	117.29	1.13	59.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	24.81	25.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	Mean	0.19	75.38	7.05	26.31	1.36	0.00	0.07	0.00	43.62	10.87	0.07	0.15	0.07	0.00
	S.E.	0.15	11.55	2.58	6.44	1.26	0.00	0.07	0.00	7.57	2.30	0.07	0.09	0.07	0.00
	Median	0.00	57.22	3.08	14.67	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	39.39	9.79	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	43.83	1.01	9.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	23.23	2.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	109.99	8.31	47.94	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	53.24	17.77	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

27-Aug

		DAPU	DARE	DAME	DIHE	CEDU	MOMI	PLAD	BOLO	ACAM	LESI	LESC	LEKI	KECO	HARP
In	Mean	0.00	83.90	8.80	24.45	7.39	0.28	0.24	0.00	287.60	37.26	2.82	0.30	0.79	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	39.82	3.32	5.51	2.28	0.28	0.19	0.00	68.16	19.49	2.82	0.21	0.79	0.00
	Median	0.00	29.82	5.92	27.92	6.91	0.00	0.00	0.00	229.69	2.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	7.90	2.54	6.91	0.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	166.82	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	137.37	10.86	35.53	12.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	331.57	56.84	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Out	Mean	0.00	46.61	2.01	11.75	3.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	466.18	23.99	4.22	3.89	1.42	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	20.93	0.85	3.41	1.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	64.37	3.82	3.07	2.47	1.42	0.00
	Median	0.00	26.64	2.54	11.84	2.54	0.00	0.00	0.00	466.68	22.83	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	24.56	0.00	7.02	1.78	0.00	0.00	0.00	338.59	17.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	27.90	3.55	12.68	3.95	0.00	0.00	0.00	571.37	31.58	5.33	7.61	0.00	0.00
Total	Mean	0.00	70.58	6.38	19.92	6.10	0.18	0.16	0.00	351.38	32.52	3.32	1.59	1.02	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	26.46	2.29	4.01	1.58	0.18	0.13	0.00	53.45	12.45	2.05	0.96	0.69	0.00
	Median	0.00	27.27	3.75	18.18	3.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	321.71	15.90	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	13.96	1.75	6.91	1.75	0.00	0.00	0.00	225.00	1.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	130.26	7.11	30.79	11.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	558.26	33.75	0.00	0.99	0.00	0.00

4-Sep

		DAPU	DARE	DAME	DIHE	CEDU	MOMI	PLAD	BOLO	ACAM	LESI	LESC	LEKI	KECO	HARP
In	Mean	0.00	18.61	3.42	11.49	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	18.15	79.13	1.22	4.31	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	5.95	0.75	3.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.32	16.64	0.73	1.25	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	13.60	2.88	9.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.73	77.73	0.41	2.67	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	4.00	1.70	6.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.99	46.43	0.00	1.41	0.00	0.00

	75th	0.00	35.97	3.95	13.88	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	19.74	97.12	0.70	7.90	0.00	0.00
Out	Mean	0.00	17.26	0.10	7.30	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.07	50.44	0.00	0.55	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	1.69	0.10	1.64	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.56	4.86	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	17.57	0.00	9.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.90	51.46	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	14.10	0.00	4.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.17	46.82	0.00	0.35	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	18.63	0.00	9.97	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.65	57.04	0.00	0.62	0.00	0.00
Total	Mean	0.00	18.13	2.23	9.99	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	13.84	68.88	0.78	2.97	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	3.79	0.65	2.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3.20	11.25	0.48	0.93	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	15.84	1.46	9.26	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.80	56.90	0.00	1.31	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	6.86	0.00	4.93	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.90	46.43	0.00	0.47	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	22.71	3.33	10.60	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	14.39	96.92	0.44	3.89	0.00	0.00

23-Sep

		DAPU	DARE	DAME	DIHE	CEDU	MOMI	PLAD	BOLO	ACAM	LESI	LESC	LEKI	KECO	HARP
In	Mean	0.02	48.44	8.05	23.22	1.63	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.16	31.44	5.29	0.63	0.00	0.14
	S.E.	0.02	12.30	1.76	6.39	0.46	0.00	0.00	0.00	16.76	6.96	2.88	0.25	0.00	0.14
	Median	0.00	32.26	6.51	15.04	1.08	0.00	0.00	0.00	58.88	23.32	1.82	0.47	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	17.46	5.47	9.87	0.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	47.72	17.61	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	87.48	9.87	29.61	2.47	0.00	0.00	0.00	64.16	45.97	2.42	1.21	0.00	0.00
Out	Mean	0.00	70.51	4.89	27.80	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	67.16	43.34	1.52	1.53	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	24.05	1.60	10.91	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.42	3.69	0.93	0.69	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	44.63	5.26	16.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	64.49	47.94	0.00	0.70	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	38.81	2.73	15.51	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	44.41	34.61	0.00	0.66	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	68.44	7.90	22.21	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	79.25	48.70	3.64	2.63	0.00	0.00
Total	Mean	0.01	56.32	6.92	24.86	1.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	69.09	35.69	3.94	0.95	0.00	0.09
	S.E.	0.01	11.49	1.30	5.44	0.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.21	4.81	1.91	0.30	0.00	0.09
	Median	0.00	39.14	6.08	15.96	0.79	0.00	0.00	0.00	60.94	38.90	1.53	0.60	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	31.45	3.80	13.81	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	44.41	20.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	87.48	9.32	29.61	1.71	0.00	0.00	0.00	79.25	48.70	3.64	1.66	0.00	0.00

9-Oct

		DAPU	DARE	DAME	DIHE	CEDU	MOMI	PLAD	BOLO	ACAM	LESI	LESC	LEKI	KECO	HARP
In	Mean	0.00	10.25	1.17	32.42	1.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	72.61	23.79	4.97	0.40	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.00	2.31	0.34	6.16	0.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.56	7.02	1.56	0.21	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	10.91	0.78	35.10	0.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	72.61	17.18	4.57	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	3.70	0.39	20.36	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	68.15	11.90	0.85	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	14.45	1.85	42.07	1.66	0.00	0.00	0.00	85.75	33.16	6.17	0.62	0.00	0.00
Out	Mean	0.07	17.28	1.10	14.28	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	44.79	21.22	2.36	0.17	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.07	2.44	0.33	2.20	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	10.66	3.39	0.39	0.11	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	17.19	1.07	12.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.51	20.23	2.47	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	13.05	0.98	10.85	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	32.30	19.24	2.15	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	22.21	1.48	19.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	51.02	28.12	2.96	0.33	0.00	0.00
Total	Mean	0.03	12.76	1.15	25.94	0.74	0.00	0.00	0.00	62.67	22.87	4.04	0.32	0.00	0.00
	S.E.	0.03	1.91	0.24	4.62	0.26	0.00	0.00	0.00	6.57	4.57	1.05	0.14	0.00	0.00
	Median	0.00	12.56	1.03	20.18	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.00	70.33	19.74	2.89	0.00	0.00	0.00
	25th	0.00	9.97	0.39	12.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	36.51	11.90	0.98	0.00	0.00	0.00
	75th	0.00	17.19	1.85	35.71	1.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	82.90	30.39	4.67	0.54	0.00	0.00

Appendix 37. More summary statistics including diversity metrics.

18-Jun										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
JN1824I1	11.21	24.43	212.97	0.00	90.48	7	0.76	1.47	0.71	4.35
JN1824I2	2.99	6.46	56.80	0.00	24.27	8	0.72	1.50	0.71	4.47
JN1824I3	4.52	8.17	85.81	0.00	23.60	8	0.81	1.68	0.78	5.34
JN1824I4	2.72	4.85	51.72	0.00	17.76	9	0.82	1.80	0.79	6.03
JN1824I5	4.14	6.49	78.72	0.00	19.78	9	0.85	1.87	0.82	6.47
JN1824I6	3.88	6.54	73.63	0.00	19.61	9	0.82	1.81	0.81	6.09
JN1824I7	2.71	3.85	51.42	0.00	9.87	11	0.83	1.98	0.85	7.26
JN1824I8	3.20	5.47	60.70	0.00	22.13	9	0.85	1.86	0.80	6.42
JN1824I9	2.72	5.19	51.75	0.00	15.92	9	0.74	1.63	0.77	5.12
JN1824O1	11.35	19.55	215.59	0.00	57.36	7	0.88	1.71	0.80	5.50
JN1824O2	11.73	22.18	222.90	0.00	77.24	7	0.84	1.63	0.77	5.11
JN1824O3	10.27	19.10	195.11	0.00	62.79	7	0.83	1.62	0.77	5.06
JN1824O4	15.66	33.04	297.51	0.00	124.93	8	0.74	1.53	0.73	4.60
JN1824O5	8.18	17.37	155.42	0.00	67.35	8	0.73	1.52	0.72	4.56
16-Jul										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
JL1624I1	5.24	11.17	99.62	0.00	36.18	6	0.79	1.41	0.72	4.11
JL1624I2	7.48	19.85	142.11	0.00	79.94	5	0.71	1.14	0.60	3.13
JL1624I3	3.82	10.00	72.54	0.00	34.79	5	0.66	1.07	0.61	2.90
JL1624I4	6.61	14.37	125.63	0.00	52.03	6	0.77	1.38	0.71	3.96
JL1624I5	11.81	37.93	224.43	0.00	166.24	6	0.53	0.94	0.43	2.56
JL1624I6	7.46	15.63	141.72	0.00	52.52	6	0.81	1.45	0.73	4.28
JL1624I7	6.24	15.06	118.64	0.00	51.43	7	0.64	1.25	0.66	3.49
JL1624I8	10.50	20.93	199.50	0.00	74.81	11	0.67	1.62	0.75	5.03
JL1624I9	9.08	26.93	172.58	0.00	109.67	5	0.56	0.90	0.51	2.47
JL1624O1	10.63	33.39	201.98	0.00	145.42	6	0.52	0.93	0.46	2.53
JL1624O2	9.90	26.88	188.01	0.00	109.99	4	0.77	1.06	0.58	2.90
JL1624O3	12.05	29.62	228.95	0.00	117.29	5	0.75	1.21	0.65	3.36
JL1624O4	6.61	15.90	125.49	0.00	59.02	5	0.77	1.24	0.66	3.45
JL1624O5	9.02	22.34	171.41	0.00	78.97	5	0.73	1.17	0.64	3.23
29-Jul										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
J12924I1	12.02	25.25	228.42	0.00	90.48	7	0.77	1.50	0.73	4.46

J12924I2	3.11	6.57	59.01	0.00	24.27	8	0.73	1.51	0.72	4.53
J12924I3	4.61	8.27	87.53	0.00	23.60	8	0.81	1.68	0.79	5.37
J12924I4	2.85	5.12	54.07	0.00	17.76	9	0.81	1.78	0.79	5.92
J12924I5	4.31	6.60	81.95	0.00	19.78	9	0.86	1.88	0.83	6.58
J12924I6	3.97	6.69	75.48	0.00	19.61	9	0.82	1.81	0.81	6.08
J12924I7	2.71	3.85	51.42	0.00	9.87	11	0.83	1.98	0.85	7.26
J12924I8	3.23	5.49	61.30	0.00	22.13	9	0.85	1.86	0.80	6.43
J12924I9	2.72	5.19	51.75	0.00	15.92	9	0.74	1.63	0.77	5.12
J12924O1	11.35	19.55	215.59	0.00	57.36	7	0.88	1.71	0.80	5.50
J12924O2	11.73	22.18	222.90	0.00	77.24	7	0.84	1.63	0.77	5.11
J12924O3	10.27	19.10	195.11	0.00	62.79	7	0.83	1.62	0.77	5.06
J12924O4	15.66	33.04	297.51	0.00	124.93	8	0.74	1.53	0.73	4.60
J12924O5	8.30	17.43	157.64	0.00	67.35	8	0.74	1.53	0.73	4.61
14-Aug										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
AU1424I1	5.59	12.23	106.20	0.00	42.76	6	0.77	1.39	0.71	3.99
AU1424I2	8.30	21.51	157.65	0.00	79.94	5	0.71	1.14	0.61	3.13
AU1424I3	4.13	11.05	78.46	0.00	40.71	5	0.65	1.04	0.59	2.82
AU1424I4	6.85	14.86	130.07	0.00	52.03	6	0.77	1.37	0.71	3.94
AU1424I5	11.81	37.93	224.43	0.00	166.24	6	0.53	0.94	0.43	2.56
AU1424I6	7.91	16.85	150.36	0.00	53.24	6	0.80	1.43	0.72	4.19
AU1424I7	6.24	15.06	118.64	0.00	51.43	7	0.64	1.25	0.66	3.49
AU1424I8	11.32	23.37	215.08	0.00	74.81	10	0.66	1.53	0.73	4.61
AU1424I9	9.84	29.96	187.03	0.00	124.12	5	0.54	0.87	0.49	2.38
AU1424O1	11.06	33.50	210.06	0.00	145.42	6	0.55	0.99	0.49	2.68
AU1424O2	10.14	26.92	192.71	0.00	109.99	4	0.79	1.10	0.60	3.00
AU1424O3	12.05	29.62	228.95	0.00	117.29	5	0.75	1.21	0.65	3.36
AU1424O4	6.80	15.98	129.22	0.00	59.02	5	0.79	1.27	0.67	3.55
AU1424O5	9.73	22.85	184.87	0.00	78.97	5	0.77	1.23	0.67	3.42
27-Aug										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
AU2724I1	57.96	147.53	1101.31	0.00	558.26	6	0.66	1.18	0.62	3.25
AU2724I2	10.65	37.97	202.36	0.00	166.82	7	0.38	0.75	0.31	2.11
AU2724I3	2.77	8.51	52.54	0.00	36.03	6	0.51	0.91	0.48	2.48
AU2724I4	23.45	75.24	445.59	0.00	331.57	9	0.47	1.03	0.43	2.81
AU2724I5	4.73	18.32	89.92	0.00	80.27	7	0.26	0.51	0.20	1.67
AU2724I6	15.03	52.43	285.54	0.00	229.69	9	0.36	0.78	0.34	2.19

AU2724I7	21.71	71.34	412.50	0.00	311.84	5	0.53	0.85	0.41	2.34
AU2724I8	29.79	66.19	566.06	0.00	225.00	6	0.75	1.34	0.70	3.80
AU2724I9	50.36	150.04	956.83	0.00	648.94	6	0.59	1.05	0.50	2.85
AU2724O1	20.66	70.90	392.56	0.00	310.85	8	0.39	0.82	0.36	2.27
AU2724O2	28.57	106.41	542.78	0.00	466.68	7	0.32	0.61	0.26	1.85
AU2724O3	45.50	147.87	864.46	0.00	643.41	8	0.44	0.91	0.42	2.47
AU2724O4	20.31	77.34	385.95	0.00	338.59	5	0.32	0.51	0.22	1.66
AU2724O5	33.34	130.48	633.53	0.00	571.37	5	0.28	0.45	0.18	1.57
4-Sep										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
SE424I1	5.90	17.87	112.15	0.00	77.73	6	0.57	1.02	0.49	2.78
SE424I2	4.31	10.85	81.96	0.00	46.43	7	0.69	1.35	0.63	3.84
SE424I3	10.65	27.55	202.36	0.00	118.45	7	0.67	1.31	0.61	3.70
SE424I4	2.63	5.96	49.96	0.00	23.76	7	0.74	1.43	0.69	4.18
SE424I5	9.44	23.90	179.38	0.00	96.92	6	0.70	1.25	0.63	3.49
SE424I6	4.39	12.96	83.48	0.00	56.75	7	0.58	1.12	0.51	3.06
SE424I7	14.55	40.85	276.49	0.00	176.32	6	0.64	1.14	0.55	3.13
SE424I8	8.41	23.20	159.71	0.00	97.12	5	0.68	1.09	0.57	2.99
SE424I9	4.29	11.27	81.41	0.00	46.87	7	0.63	1.23	0.60	3.40
SE424O1	5.45	13.85	103.47	0.00	57.04	6	0.68	1.21	0.62	3.36
SE424O2	3.35	8.68	63.66	0.00	34.16	5	0.71	1.14	0.61	3.14
SE424O3	5.12	14.69	97.36	0.00	62.70	5	0.64	1.04	0.54	2.82
SE424O4	4.12	12.06	78.24	0.00	51.46	5	0.62	0.99	0.52	2.69
SE424O5	3.47	10.94	65.85	0.00	46.82	5	0.53	0.85	0.45	2.35
23-Sep										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
SE2324I1	2.00	3.95	37.91	0.00	13.97	7	0.80	1.56	0.75	4.74
SE2324I2	20.14	44.69	382.72	0.00	180.43	8	0.72	1.50	0.70	4.46
SE2324I3	13.77	29.53	261.57	0.00	111.05	7	0.74	1.45	0.72	4.24
SE2324I4	8.07	19.10	153.34	0.00	63.00	6	0.71	1.28	0.67	3.58
SE2324I5	18.57	35.34	352.82	0.00	117.61	7	0.81	1.58	0.77	4.87
SE2324I6	6.58	13.45	125.09	0.00	44.33	8	0.73	1.53	0.74	4.60
SE2324I7	5.10	11.64	96.81	0.00	47.93	8	0.69	1.44	0.69	4.21
SE2324I8	6.17	13.28	117.13	0.00	47.72	7	0.74	1.43	0.72	4.17
SE2324I9	9.09	17.95	172.61	0.00	58.88	7	0.78	1.52	0.75	4.56
SE2324O1	9.73	21.05	184.90	0.00	79.25	7	0.75	1.45	0.71	4.27
SE2324O2	14.06	26.45	267.18	0.00	71.07	7	0.81	1.57	0.77	4.79

SE2324O3	18.52	43.74	351.96	0.00	164.02	6	0.72	1.29	0.67	3.62
SE2324O4	7.17	14.54	136.17	0.00	43.42	6	0.81	1.45	0.74	4.28
SE2324O5	7.64	16.24	145.22	0.00	47.94	5	0.83	1.34	0.72	3.82
9-Oct										
Sample Code	Mean	Stand.Dev.	Sum	Minimum	Maximum	S	E	H'	D	ENT
OC924I1	2.18	6.50	41.41	0.00	28.20	8	0.52	1.08	0.50	2.94
OC924I2	6.39	16.26	121.33	0.00	68.15	7	0.65	1.26	0.62	3.52
OC924I3	9.26	22.27	175.99	0.00	89.27	6	0.71	1.28	0.66	3.58
OC924I4	8.82	20.48	167.51	0.00	78.69	6	0.73	1.31	0.68	3.72
OC924I5	7.12	19.44	135.19	0.00	72.50	7	0.55	1.07	0.58	2.92
OC924I6	6.92	19.81	131.41	0.00	85.75	8	0.55	1.14	0.54	3.14
OC924I7	7.83	18.30	148.74	0.00	72.61	7	0.69	1.34	0.67	3.83
OC924I8	9.26	20.09	175.97	0.00	65.46	7	0.75	1.46	0.71	4.28
OC924I9	11.72	26.61	222.65	0.00	95.42	6	0.75	1.34	0.69	3.82
OC924O1	7.91	19.66	150.26	0.00	82.90	8	0.63	1.32	0.64	3.73
OC924O2	5.43	11.13	103.11	0.00	36.51	6	0.82	1.46	0.74	4.30
OC924O3	5.82	13.25	110.64	0.00	51.02	7	0.71	1.38	0.69	3.96
OC924O4	3.64	7.20	69.18	0.00	21.21	7	0.77	1.49	0.75	4.44
OC924O5	3.93	8.61	74.65	0.00	32.30	6	0.78	1.39	0.71	4.01

Appendix 38. Some functional traits of zooplankton encountered in this study. Mostly derived from Hébert, Beatrix, and Maranger 2016.

	Trophic group	Mean Body length (mm)	Min. Body length (mm)	Max. Body length (mm)	Mean body Dry mass (mg)	Min. Body Dry mass (mg)	Max. Body Dry mass (mg)	Protein content (%)	Lipid content (%)
<i>Acanthocyclops americanus</i> ¹	Omnivore/carnivore	0.72-1.14	NA	NA	0.0086	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>Daphnia retrocurva</i>	Herbivore	0.87			0.0034				
<i>Leptodiaptomus sicilis</i>	Omnivore	1.07	1.24		0.009				
<i>Diaphanosoma cf. heberti</i>	Herbivore	0.69 ^c	0.54	1.12	0.003 ^c			39.3	23.6
<i>Daphnia mendotae</i>	Herbivore	1.3-3.0			0.0057	0.0025	0.0089		
<i>Ceriodaphnia dubia</i>	Herbivore	0.8	NA	NA	0.003 ^a	0.002 ^a	0.0035 ^a	54.41 ^b	5.29 ^b
<i>Leptodiaptomus siciloides</i>	Herbivore	0.95			0.0049				
<i>Leptodora kindti</i>	Carnivore (predator)	3.8			0.0085-0.011	0.0029	0.046	70	37.1
<i>Daphnia pulex</i> gr.	Herbivore	1.2-2.45	1.2	3.5	0.028-0.039				

<i>Keratella cochlearis</i>	Primarily herbivore ²	0.04 – 0.11 ^d							
<i>Moina micrura</i>	Herbivore	0.72	0.6	0.84	0.004				
<i>Pleuroxus aduncus</i>	Herbivore	0.66				0.007			
<i>Chydorus brevilabrus</i>	Herbivore	0.29							
Harpacticoida	Omnivore	0.47-0.9			0.0027-0.0087				
<i>Bosmina longirostris</i> complex	Herbivore	0.33-0.4	0.24	0.52	0.00177	0.00054	0.0018	62.2	14.5

¹Based on *Acanthocyclops robusta* and *A. vernalis* values

^a Predicted from regression of other *Ceriodaphnia* sp.

^b based on *C. quadrangula*.

^c mean values from other *Diaphanosoma* sp.

² Known to feed on *Cryptomonas* sp. and *Chlamydomonas* sp. (Bogdan and Gilbert 1982)

^d *Keratella cochlearis* has several subspecies of varying body lengths (see **Error! Reference source not found.**). The subspecies in Utah Lake is unknown.

Appendix 39. Best fit regression of total zooplankton abundance (density L⁻¹). Total abundance was log transformed for model.

Log total zoo	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
July 29	-.91	.27	-3.37	.001	-1.447	-.372	***
Aug 14	-1.101	.276	-3.98	0	-1.651	-.55	***
base Aug 27	0	
Sept 4	-1.338	.219	-6.10	0	-1.774	-.901	***
Sept 23	-1.007	.288	-3.50	.001	-1.581	-.434	***
Oct 9	-1.293	.256	-5.05	0	-1.802	-.783	***
Sqrt Pennate Diatoms	-.001	0	-2.01	.048	-.001	0	**
LogTotal Phyto	.175	.112	1.56	.123	-.048	.398	
Constant	3.145	1.879	1.67	.098	-.598	6.888	*
Mean dependent var		5.043	SD dependent var			0.727	
R-squared		0.419	Number of obs			84	
F-test		7.836	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 40. ANOVAs for richness and diversity indices. Only significant ANOVAs are reported.

Taxa Richness ANOVAs inside corrals vs outside

June 18

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	6.1015873	1	6.1015873	6.81	0.0228
Within groups	10.7555556	12	.896296296		
Total	16.8571429	13	1.2967033		

July 29

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	6.1015873	1	6.1015873	6.81	0.0228
Within groups	10.7555556	12	.896296296		
Total	16.8571429	13	1.2967033		

September 4

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	4.97777778	1	4.97777778	11.89	0.0048
Within groups	5.02222222	12	.418518519		
Total	10	13	.769230769		

September 23

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	3.35873016	1	3.35873016	6.34	0.0270
Within groups	6.35555556	12	.52962963		
Total	9.71428571	13	.747252747		

Evenness ANOVA

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1.27	7	0.18	24.05	0
Within groups	0.79	104	0.01		
Total	2.06	111	0.02		

Post hoc Bonferroni multiple comparison test statistics and p-values.

	18-Jun	16-Jul	29-Jul	14-Aug	27-Aug	4-Sep	23-Sep
16-Jul		-0.11 0.03					
29-Jul		0.00	0.11 1.00				
14-Aug		-0.11	0.00	-0.11 1.00			
27-Aug		-0.35	-0.24	-0.36	-0.25 1.00		
4-Sep		-0.15	-0.04	-0.16	-0.05	0.20 1.00	
23-Sep		-0.04	0.07	-0.04	0.07	0.31	0.11 1.00
9-Oct		-0.12	-0.01	-0.12	-0.01	0.24	0.04 1.00
		0.02	1.00	0.02	1.00	1.00	0.77

Shannon Diversity ANOVA

August 27

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	.240142837	1	.240142837	4.43	0.0570
Within groups	.650200014	12	.054183334		
Total	.89034285	13	.068487912		

September 4

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	.092407766	1	.092407766	5.03	0.0446
Within groups	.220542196	12	.018378516		
Total	.312949962	13	.024073074		

October 9

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	.076891435	1	.076891435	5.90	0.0318
Within groups	.156479985	12	.013039999		
Total	.23337142	13	.017951648		

Simpson Diversity ANOVA

August 27

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	.077555714	1	.077555714	4.04	0.0674
Within groups	.23027999	12	.019189999		
Total	.307835704	13	.02367967		

October 9

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	.019667297	1	.019667297	4.69	0.0511
Within groups	.050275556	12	.00418963		
Total	.069942852	13	.005380219		

Effective Number of Taxa (ENT) ANOVA

Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	117.92	7	16.85	37.93	0.001
Within groups	46.19	104	0.44		
Total	164.11	111	1.48		

Post hoc Bonferroni multiple comparison test statistics and p-values.

	18-Jun	16-Jul	29-Jul	14-Aug	27-Aug	4-Sep	23-Sep
16-Jul	-2.070	0.000					
29-Jul	0.018	2.088	1.000	0.000			
14-Aug	2.090	-0.020	-2.108	0.000	1.000	0.000	
27-Aug	-3.076	-1.006	-3.094	-0.986	0.000	0.003	0.000
4-Sep	-2.246	-0.176	-2.264	-0.156	0.829	0.000	1.000
23-Sep	-1.155	0.915	-1.173	0.935	1.921	1.091	0.000
9-Oct	-1.728	0.342	-1.746	0.362	1.348	0.519	0.580
	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.000	1.000	0.700

Appendix 41. Summary statistics of total zooplankton abundances (L-1) by treatments on September 4, September 23, and October 9. Phosphorus treatment was conducted on September 11 in corrals P2.

treatment	Mean	se(mean)	Median	p25	p75
September 4					
Control	162.06	65.41	159.71	49.96	276.51
Lake	81.72	8.08	78.25	65.85	97.37
P1	125.00	28.42	112.15	83.48	179.38
P2	121.90	40.22	81.96	81.41	202.35
September 23					
Control	122.42	16.53	117.12	96.81	153.33
Lake	217.08	40.89	184.92	145.21	267.17
P1	171.94	93.87	125.10	37.9	352.82
P2	272.71	60.85	262.81	172.6	382.72

October 9

Control	164.08	8.04	167.52	148.75	175.98
Lake	101.56	14.54	103.12	74.64	110.64
P1	102.67	30.65	131.40	41.41	135.21
P2	173.32	29.27	175.98	121.35	222.64

Appendix 42. Zooplankton vs phytoplankton vs treatments starting Sept 4. Best fit Linear regression model.

Log Total Zooplankton	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Log total phytoplankton	.298	.101	2.96	.005	.094	.502	***
Treatment							
P1	-.504	.237	-2.13	.04	-.983	-.025	**
P2 base	0	
Control	-.241	.236	-1.02	.313	-.719	.237	
Lake	-.369	.211	-1.75	.089	-.796	.058	*
Constant	-.155	1.793	-0.09	.932	-3.787	3.477	
Mean dependent var		4.857	SD dependent var		0.553		
R-squared		0.263	Number of obs		42		
F-test		3.298	Prob > F		0.021		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 43. Best fit linear regression of *Acanthocyclops americanus* ACAM (log transformed) with several factors . Note: BOLO only occurred in two samples but significantly improved model.

logACAM	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
sqrtPD	-.001	0	-2.85	.007	-.001	0	***
Cond	.008	.005	1.60	.117	-.002	.019	
lesc	.039	.013	3.14	.003	.014	.064	***
DO	.139	.041	3.43	.001	.058	.221	***
bolo	-5.334	1.342	-3.97	0	-8.037	-2.631	***
sqrtCEHI	0	0	2.69	.01	0	0	**
dame	.026	.01	2.66	.011	.006	.045	**
phcsp	0	0	-1.65	.106	0	0	
leki	.052	.035	1.47	.15	-.019	.123	
chlsp	0	0	-2.95	.005	0	0	***
Mg	-.126	.024	-5.33	0	-.174	-.079	***
NH ₃	-7.89	2.182	-3.62	.001	-12.284	-3.496	***
oobo	0	0	-2.94	.005	0	0	***
trsp	0	0	-2.71	.009	0	0	***
Constant	-2.833	9.294	-0.30	.762	-21.553	15.887	
Mean dependent var		4.037	SD dependent var		1.133		
R-squared		0.877	Number of obs		60		
F-test		22.923	Prob > F		0.000		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 44. Quantile regression of zooplankton densities vs. phytoplankton biovolumes inside vs. outside of corrals.

Inside Corrals

	Coef.	Bootstrap Std. Err.	t	P > t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
q10						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.043	0.12	0.36	0.719	-0.195	0.282
cons	1.414	0.84	1.68	0.097	-0.261	3.089
q20						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.202	0.057	3.53	0.001	0.088	0.317
cons	0.383	0.409	0.94	0.352	-0.432	1.199
q30						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.251	0.058	4.29	0.00	0.134	0.367
cons	0.09	0.437	0.2	0.838	-0.782	0.962
q40						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.191	0.068	2.79	0.007	0.055	0.327
cons	0.606	0.531	1.14	0.258	-0.454	1.666
q50						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.199	0.073	2.72	0.008	0.053	0.344
cons	0.594	0.576	1.03	0.306	-0.554	1.741
q60						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.137	0.081	1.69	0.095	-0.024	0.298
cons	1.119	0.645	1.74	0.087	-0.166	2.405
q70						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.074	0.075	0.98	0.329	-0.076	0.223
cons	1.698	0.58	2.93	0.005	0.541	2.855
q80						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.077	0.076	1.01	0.315	-0.075	0.229
cons	1.746	0.558	3.13	0.003	0.633	2.858
q90						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.126	0.157	0.81	0.423	-0.186	0.439
cons	1.539	1.152	1.34	0.186	-0.759	3.836

Outside Corrals

	Coef.	Bootstrap Std. Err.	t	P > t	[95% Conf.	Interval]
q10						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.2	0.133	-1.51	0.141	-0.469	0.069
cons	3.396	0.992	3.42	0.002	1.387	5.406
q20						

log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.058	0.14	-0.41	0.681	-0.343	0.226
cons	2.476	1.022	2.42	0.02	0.406	4.546
q30						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.095	0.124	-0.77	0.448	-0.346	0.156
cons	2.871	0.897	3.2	0.003	1.053	4.689
q40						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.13	0.101	-1.28	0.208	-0.335	0.076
cons	3.183	0.728	4.37	0.00	1.708	4.657
q50						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.112	0.08	-1.41	0.166	-0.274	0.049
cons	3.112	0.566	5.5	0.00	1.965	4.259
q60						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.069	0.079	-0.88	0.387	-0.228	0.09
cons	2.817	0.563	5	0.00	1.676	3.958
q70						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.033	0.102	-0.33	0.745	-0.239	0.173
cons	2.579	0.743	3.47	0.001	1.075	4.084
q80						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	-0.038	0.151	-0.25	0.804	-0.343	0.268
cons	2.729	1.073	2.54	0.015	0.556	4.903
q90						
log ₁₀ Phytoplankton	0.301	0.244	1.23	0.225	-0.193	0.795
cons	0.476	1.71	0.28	0.782	-2.99	3.941

Log ₁₀ Phytoplankton Biovolume (N = 179)			
Percentile	Centile	95% CIs	
10	6.623	6.428	6.799
20	6.954	6.799	7.002
30	7.079	6.996	7.176
40	7.230	7.114	7.362
50	7.398	7.301	7.591
60	7.613	7.462	7.730
70	7.756	7.643	7.797
80	7.875	7.784	7.986
90	8.079	7.984	8.178

Appendix 45. Linear regression results of zooplankton densities vs. individual phytoplankton taxa biovolumes outside of corals. All phytoplankton biovolumes were square root transformed. APFL = *Aphanizomenon flosaquae*, CEHI = *Ceratium hirundinella*, CHLSP = *Chlamydomonas sp.*, PD = pennate diatoms, CLLO = *Closteriopsis longissima*, EUSP = *Euglena sp.*

log ₁₀ Zooplankton	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
sqrtAPFL	< -0.001	0	-4.45	0	0	0	***
sqrtCEHI	< 0.001	0	4.15	0	0	0	***
sqrtCHLSP	< -0.001	0	-3.30	.002	-.001	0	***
sqrtPD	.001	0	2.46	.02	0	.001	**
sqrtCLLO	.001	0	3.27	.003	0	.001	***
sqrtEUSP	-.001	0	-2.59	.014	-.001	0	**
Constant	2.324	.072	32.24	0	2.178	2.471	***
Mean dependent var		2.265	SD dependent var			0.264	
R-squared		0.717	Number of obs			39	
F-test		13.527	Prob > F			0.000	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 46. Best fit SEM structural model for dominant phytoplankton and zooplankton interactions.

OIM						
Standardized	Coef.	Std.Err.	z	P>z	[95%Conf.	Interval]
Structural						
DARE						
DAME	0.587	0.095	6.160	0.000	0.400	0.774
ACAM	0.202	0.096	2.100	0.035	0.014	0.389
LESI	0.507	0.083	6.080	0.000	0.343	0.670
CEDU	0.041	0.101	0.410	0.685	-0.158	0.240
_cons	-0.235	0.362	-0.650	0.517	-0.945	0.475
APFL						
CEHI	0.051	0.222	0.230	0.820	-0.385	0.486
DAME	0.824	0.278	2.970	0.003	0.279	1.369
ACAM	-0.426	0.170	-2.510	0.012	-0.759	-0.094
CEDU	-0.937	0.186	-5.050	0.000	-1.301	-0.574
_cons	2.212	0.542	4.080	0.000	1.150	3.274
DOCI						
APFL	0.491	0.094	5.220	0.000	0.307	0.675
DIHE	0.226	0.104	2.180	0.029	0.023	0.429
ACAM	-0.578	0.081	-7.160	0.000	-0.736	-0.420
_cons	2.128	0.541	3.940	0.000	1.069	3.188
CEHI						
DARE	0.276	0.227	1.220	0.224	-0.168	0.720
APFL	0.325	0.142	2.290	0.022	0.047	0.603
DIHE	-0.199	0.133	-1.490	0.135	-0.460	0.062
DAME	0.177	0.196	0.900	0.366	-0.207	0.562
ACAM	0.420	0.124	3.390	0.001	0.177	0.663
LESI	-0.268	0.167	-1.610	0.108	-0.596	0.059
_cons	0.827	0.649	1.270	0.202	-0.445	2.100
DIHE						
DARE	0.362	0.136	2.660	0.008	0.095	0.628
APFL	-0.186	0.152	-1.220	0.223	-0.484	0.113
PHRSP	-0.145	0.152	-0.950	0.341	-0.443	0.153

_cons	3.014	0.618	4.880	0.000	1.803	4.226
DAME						
APFL	-0.831	0.352	-2.360	0.018	-1.520	-0.142
_cons	2.522	0.471	5.360	0.000	1.599	3.444
var(e.DARE)	0.281	0.067			0.176	0.448
var(e.APFL)	0.659	0.261			0.304	1.431
var(e.DOCl)	0.372	0.089			0.233	0.593
var(e.CEHI)	0.516	0.105			0.346	0.768
var(e.DIHE)	0.833	0.108			0.647	1.074
var(e.DAME)	1.826	0.597			0.962	3.467

Appendix 47. SEM of dominant phytoplankton and zooplankton taxa indirect and total effects

Indirect effects

		OIM				
		Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
Structural						
DARE						
DARE		0.00	0.01	-0.22	0.83	-0.03 0.02
APFL		0.00	0.00	-3.32	0.00	0.00 0.00
CEHI		0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.82	0.00 0.00
DIHE		0.00	0.02	0.22	0.82	-0.03 0.04
DAME		0.30	0.14	-2.23	0.03	-0.57 -0.04
ACAM		0.12	0.06	1.96	0.05	0.00 0.23
LESI		0.00	0.01	0.22	0.83	-0.02 0.03
PHRSP		0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.83	0.00 0.00
CEDU		0.29	0.11	2.75	0.01	0.08 0.50
APFL						
DARE		20.45	94.46	0.22	0.83	-164.69 205.60
APFL		0.40	0.18	-2.25	0.02	-0.76 -0.05
CEHI		0.05	0.21	-0.23	0.82	-0.46 0.36
DIHE		30.25	135.63	-0.22	0.82	-296.08 235.58
DAME		-1332.88	1090.78	-1.22	0.22	-3470.76 805.00
ACAM		616.23	434.62	1.42	0.16	-235.60 1468.06
LESI		17.28	78.90	-0.22	0.83	-171.92 137.35
PHRSP		0.01	0.04	0.22	0.83	-0.06 0.08
CEDU		1339.45	771.29	1.74	0.08	-172.25 2851.15
DOCI						
DARE		76.02	45.33	1.68	0.09	-12.82 164.86
APFL		0.07	0.03	-2.43	0.02	-0.12 -0.01
CEHI		0.01	0.04	0.22	0.82	-0.06 0.08
DIHE		-3.36	15.14	-0.22	0.82	-33.03 26.31

DAME	281.51	75.82	3.71	0.00	132.91	430.12
ACAM	73.32	45.62	-1.61	0.11	-162.74	16.10
LESI	37.10	26.84	1.38	0.17	-15.50	89.71
PHRSP	0.08	0.09	-0.86	0.39	-0.26	0.10
CEDU	215.48	88.38	-2.44	0.02	-388.70	-42.26
<hr/>						
CEHI						
DARE	100.37	79.13	-1.27	0.21	-255.47	54.73
APFL	0.11	0.05	-2.04	0.04	-0.21	0.00
CEHI	0.00	0.01	0.26	0.79	-0.02	0.03
DIHE	-1.47	5.63	-0.26	0.79	-12.51	9.57
DAME	308.11	318.20	0.97	0.33	-315.55	931.77
ACAM	19.02	113.38	0.17	0.87	-203.20	241.23
LESI	151.05	171.90	0.88	0.38	-185.87	487.97
PHRSP	0.11	0.14	0.80	0.43	-0.16	0.39
CEDU	83.15	221.52	-0.38	0.71	-517.33	351.02
<hr/>						
DIHE						
DARE	0.00	0.01	-0.22	0.83	-0.01	0.01
APFL	0.00	0.00	-0.37	0.71	0.00	0.00
CEHI	0.00	0.00	-0.23	0.82	0.00	0.00
DIHE	0.00	0.01	0.23	0.82	-0.02	0.02
DAME	0.03	0.08	0.32	0.75	-0.13	0.18
ACAM	0.10	0.05	2.07	0.04	0.01	0.20
LESI	0.13	0.06	2.26	0.02	0.02	0.24
PHRSP	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.83	0.00	0.00
CEDU	0.15	0.08	1.96	0.05	0.00	0.30
<hr/>						
DAME						
DARE	0.00	0.02	-0.22	0.83	-0.04	0.03
APFL	0.00	0.00	1.09	0.28	0.00	0.00
CEHI	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.82	0.00	0.00
DIHE	0.01	0.03	0.22	0.82	-0.05	0.06
DAME	0.42	0.17	-2.43	0.02	-0.75	-0.08
ACAM	0.16	0.08	2.08	0.04	0.01	0.31
LESI	0.00	0.02	0.22	0.83	-0.03	0.03
PHRSP	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.83	0.00	0.00
CEDU	0.40	0.13	3.13	0.00	0.15	0.65
<hr/>						

Total effects

OIM

Structural	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
DARE						
DARE	0.00	0.01	-0.22	0.83	-0.03	0.02
APFL	0.00	0.00	-3.32	0.00	0.00	0.00
CEHI	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.82	0.00	0.00
DIHE	0.00	0.02	0.22	0.82	-0.03	0.04
DAME	0.42	0.14	2.95	0.00	0.14	0.71
ACAM	0.32	0.11	2.94	0.00	0.11	0.53
LESI	0.53	0.10	5.54	0.00	0.34	0.72
PHRSP	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.83	0.00	0.00
CEDU	0.33	0.13	2.50	0.01	0.07	0.59
APFL						
DARE	20.45	94.46	0.22	0.83	-164.69	205.60
APFL	-0.40	0.18	-2.25	0.02	-0.76	-0.05
CEHI	0.07	0.32	0.22	0.82	-0.55	0.69
DIHE	-30.25	135.63	-0.22	0.82	-296.08	235.58
DAME	2053.99	317.80	6.46	0.00	1431.12	2676.87
ACAM	-793.80	304.50	-2.61	0.01	-1390.61	-196.99
LESI	-17.28	78.90	-0.22	0.83	-171.92	137.35
PHRSP	0.01	0.04	0.22	0.83	-0.06	0.08
CEDU	-1970.34	503.49	-3.91	0.00	-2957.15	-983.52
DOCI						
DARE	76.02	45.33	1.68	0.09	-12.82	164.86
APFL	0.07	0.03	2.26	0.02	0.01	0.12
CEHI	0.01	0.04	0.22	0.82	-0.06	0.08
DIHE	305.56	141.66	2.16	0.03	27.92	583.20
DAME	281.51	75.82	3.71	0.00	132.91	430.12
ACAM	-592.12	101.05	-5.86	0.00	-790.17	-394.06
LESI	37.10	26.84	1.38	0.17	-15.50	89.71
PHRSP	-0.08	0.09	-0.86	0.39	-0.26	0.10
CEDU	-215.48	88.38	-2.44	0.02	-388.70	-42.26
CEHI						
DARE	288.06	321.97	0.89	0.37	-342.98	919.11
APFL	0.03	0.07	0.44	0.66	-0.10	0.16
CEHI	0.00	0.01	0.26	0.79	-0.02	0.03
DIHE	-426.08	283.88	-1.50	0.13	-982.48	130.32
DAME	616.93	195.10	3.16	0.00	234.54	999.33
ACAM	606.87	188.68	3.22	0.00	237.06	976.68
LESI	-243.44	188.37	-1.29	0.20	-612.65	125.77
PHRSP	0.11	0.14	0.80	0.43	-0.16	0.39

CEDU	-83.15	221.52	-0.38	0.71	-517.33	351.02
DIHE						
DARE	0.24	0.10	2.43	0.02	0.05	0.43
APFL	0.00	0.00	-2.03	0.04	0.00	0.00
CEHI	0.00	0.00	-0.23	0.82	0.00	0.00
DIHE	0.00	0.01	0.23	0.82	-0.02	0.02
DAME	0.03	0.08	0.32	0.75	-0.13	0.18
ACAM	0.10	0.05	2.07	0.04	0.01	0.20
LESI	0.13	0.06	2.26	0.02	0.02	0.24
PHRSP	0.00	0.00	-0.94	0.35	0.00	0.00
CEDU	0.15	0.08	1.96	0.05	0.00	0.30
DAME						
DARE	0.00	0.02	-0.22	0.83	-0.04	0.03
APFL	0.00	0.00	-4.15	0.00	0.00	0.00
CEHI	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.82	0.00	0.00
DIHE	0.01	0.03	0.22	0.82	-0.05	0.06
DAME	-0.42	0.17	-2.43	0.02	-0.75	-0.08
ACAM	0.16	0.08	2.08	0.04	0.01	0.31
LESI	0.00	0.02	0.22	0.83	-0.03	0.03
PHRSP	0.00	0.00	-0.22	0.83	0.00	0.00
CEDU	0.40	0.13	3.13	0.00	0.15	0.65

Equation-level goodness of fit

	fitted	predicted	residual	R-squared	mc	mc2
DARE	1.493	1.076	0.419	0.719	0.848	0.719
APFL	1.65e+07	1.44e+07	1.09e+07	0.341	0.650	0.422
DOCI	1214427	7.63e+05	451537	0.628	0.793	0.628
CEHI	2958187	1421738	1525890	0.484	0.696	0.484
DIHE	0.650	0.106	0.542	0.167	0.408	0.167
DAME	0.977	0.675	1.783	-0.826	-0.081	0.007
Overall				0.752		

mc = correlation between depvar and its prediction

mc2 = mc^2 is the Bentler-Raykov squared multiple correlation coefficient

Appendix 48, Summary statistics of benthic invertebrate densities (m^{-2}) by date from limnocorral study 2024.

16-Jul						
Location	mean	se(mean)	p25	p50	p75	N
In	2,306	496	1,335	1,765	2,928	9
Out	2,936	1,316	1,206	2,024	2,153	5
Mean	2,531	543	1,206	1,895	2,928	
13-Aug						
Location	mean	se(mean)	p25	p50	p75	N
In	4,763	1,761	1,033	2,368	6,631	9
Out	3,178	1,016	1,722	3,402	5,253	5
Mean	4,197	1,176	1,033	2,777	5,382	
3-Sep						
Location	mean	se(mean)	p25	p50	p75	N
In	4,843	1,266	2,712	3,401	5,856	9
Out	6,123	1,022	4,865	6,200	8,267	5
Peri	376,832		376,832	376,832	376,832	1
Mean	30,069	24,782	2,842	5,081	8,267	
8-Oct						
Location	mean	se(mean)	p25	p50	p75	N
In	5,837	1,731	2,670	3,875	8,310	9
Out	4,323	1,115	2,239	3,961	6,803	5
Peri	80,281		80,281	80,281	80,281	1
Mean	10,295	5,116	2,239	3,961	8,310	
All dates						
Location	mean	se(mean)	p25	p50	p75	N
In	4,437	709	1,378	2,885	5,468	36
Out	4,140	591	1,873	3,681	6,501	20
Peri	228,557	148,275	80,281	228,557	376,832	2
Mean	12,063	6,550	1,636	3,294	6,200	

Appendix 49. Summary statistics of benthic invertebrate densities (m^{-2}) by taxon from each location during limnocorral study 2024.

Inside	PRSP	CRSY	CHCR	CHDE	CRCSP	POHA	GLSP	PASP	CRSP	CLSP	NEMA	OLIGO	EISP	COFL	NAID	OSTR
Mean	25	16	789	90	4.8	8.9	20	3.6	1.2	968	28	2,453	15	14	.	.
Std. Error	8.4	11	164	28	2.3	3.1	8.1	2.6	1.2	259	9.3	505	5.5	6.4	.	.
25th	0	0	151	0	0	0	0	0	0	172	0	538	0	0	.	.
50th	0	0	431	43	0	0	0	0	0	431	0	1,356	0	0	.	.
75th	43	0	1,052	108	0	0	0	0	0	1,184	43	3,035	0	0	.	.
Outside	PRSP	CRSY	CHCR	CHDE	CRCSP	POHA	GLSP	PASP	CRSP	CLSP	NEMA	OLIGO	EISP	COFL	NAID	OSTR
Mean	17	2.2	1,070	103	8.6	2.2	0	0	0	86	41	2,732	71	6.5	.	.
Std. Error	6.6	2.2	275	24	6.7	2.2	0	0	0	51	13	479	22	3.5	.	.
25th	0	0	323	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	990	0	0	.	.
50th	0	0	581	43	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,981	22	0	.	.
75th	43	0	1,076	215	0	0	0	0	0	65	86	4,456	108	0	.	.
Periphyton	PRSP	CRSY	CHCR	CHDE	CRCSP	POHA	GLSP	PASP	CRSP	CLSP	NEMA	OLIGO	EISP	COFL	NAID	OSTR
Mean	0	10,965	23,448	2,790	.	2,350	.	30,399	.	.	143,723	14,881
Std. Error	.	783	49	1,322	.	2,350	.	14,245	.	.	139,807	8,616
25th	0	10,182	23,399	1,469	.	0	.	16,154	.	.	3,916	6,266
50th	0	10,965	23,448	2,790	.	2,350	.	30,399	.	.	143,723	14,881
75th	0	11,749	23,497	4,112	.	4,699	.	44,644	.	.	283,530	23,497
Total	PRSP	CRSY	CHCR	CHDE	CRCSP	POHA	GLSP	PASP	CRSP	CLSP	NEMA	OLIGO	EISP	COFL	NAID	OSTR
Mean	22	389	890	95	6.2	6.5	821	98	0.77	712	33	3,513	35	11	143,723	14,881
Std. Error	5.8	266	144	20	2.8	2.2	566	75	0.77	184	7.5	836	9.1	4.3	139,807	8,616
25th	0	0	215	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	603	0	0	3,916	6,266
50th	0	0	517	43	0	0	0	0	0	172	0	1,550	0	0	143,723	14,881
75th	43	0	1,052	129	0	0	0	0	0	861	43	4,004	60	0	283,530	23,497

Appendix 50. Mean and standard error (S.E.) for the five-diversity metrics by sample date and inside vs. outside of corral. S = number of taxa, E = Evenness, H' = Shannon Diversity, D = Simpson Diversity.

16-July

		S	E	H'	D	ENT
In	mean	8.8	0.79	1.7	0.76	5.6
	S.E.	0.64	0.03	0.074	0.02	0.45
Out	mean	6.4	0.68	1.2	0.61	3.5
	S.E.	0.68	0.084	0.12	0.06	0.39
Total	mean	7.9	0.75	1.5	0.71	4.8
	S.E.	0.56	0.037	0.089	0.031	0.42

13-Aug

		S	E	H'	D	ENT
In	mean	5.8	0.63	1.1	0.58	2.9
	S.E.	0.43	0.05	0.067	0.027	0.19
Out	mean	6.2	0.58	0.89	0.43	2.5
	S.E.	1.2	0.091	0.082	0.025	0.2
Total	mean	5.9	0.61	1	0.53	2.8
	S.E.	0.47	0.044	0.055	0.028	0.15

3-Sep

		S	E	H'	D	ENT
In	mean	4.8	0.68	1	0.58	2.8
	S.E.	0.55	0.029	0.048	0.025	0.13
Out	mean	5.6	0.56	0.95	0.52	2.6
	S.E.	0.51	0.023	0.064	0.029	0.17
Total	mean	5.1	0.64	0.99	0.56	2.7
	S.E.	0.4	0.026	0.038	0.02	0.1

8-Oct

		S	E	H'	D	ENT
In	mean	7.7	0.53	1	0.49	3
	S.E.	0.75	0.069	0.13	0.065	0.43
Out	mean	3.6	0.45	0.57	0.31	1.9
	S.E.	0.51	0.12	0.15	0.099	0.27
Total	mean	6.2	0.5	0.87	0.43	2.6
	S.E.	0.74	0.059	0.11	0.058	0.33

Appendix 51. Linear regression of taxa richness by date and location inside corral (In), outside corral (Out), and in periphyton community on insides of corral (Peri),

S	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date: base July 16	0
August 13	-2	.755	-2.65	.011	-3.515	-.485	**
September 3	-2.857	.755	-3.79	< 0.01	-4.373	-1.342	***
October 8	-1.714	.755	-2.27	.027	-3.23	-.199	**

InOut: base In	0
Out	-1.3	.557	-2.33	.024	-2.418	-.182	**
Constant	8.393	.57	14.73	< 0.01	7.249	9.536	***

Mean dependent var	6.286	SD dependent var	2.278
R-squared	0.287	Number of obs	56
F-test	5.141	Prob > F	0.001

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 52. Linear regression of Evenness by date and location inside corrals (In) vs. outside of corrals (Out).

E	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date: base July 16	0
August 13	-.144	.059	-2.43	.019	-.262	-.025	**
September 3	-.116	.059	-1.97	.054	-.235	.002	*
October 8	-.251	.059	-4.24	< 0.01	-.369	-.132	***
InOut: base In	0
Out	-.09	.044	-2.06	.044	-.177	-.002	**
Constant	.784	.045	17.58	< 0.01	.694	.873	***

Mean dependent var	0.624	SD dependent var	0.181
R-squared	0.306	Number of obs	56
F-test	5.623	Prob > F	0.001

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 53. Linear regression Shannon Diversity by date and location inside corrals (In) vs. outside of corrals (Out).

H	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date: base July 16	0
August 13	-.523	.099	-5.26	< 0.01	-.722	-.323	***
September 3	-.534	.099	-5.37	< 0.01	-.734	-.335	***
October 8	-.652	.099	-6.56	< 0.01	-.852	-.453	***
InOut: base In	0
Out	-.296	.073	-4.03	< 0.01	-.443	-.149	***
Constant	1.631	.075	21.74	< 0.01	1.48	1.781	***

Mean dependent var	1.098	SD dependent var	0.386
R-squared	0.570	Number of obs	56
F-test	16.901	Prob > F	0.000

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 54. Linear regression of Simpson Diversity by date and location inside corrals (In) vs. outside of corrals (Out).

D	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
DateCode : base	0
July 16							
August 13	-.179	.046	-3.90	< 0.01	-.272	-.087	***
September 3	-.15	.046	-3.26	.002	-.242	-.058	***
October 8	-.282	.046	-6.13	< 0.01	-.375	-.19	***
InOutCode : base	0
In							
Out	-.135	.034	-3.97	< 0.01	-.203	-.067	***
Constant	.757	.035	21.79	< 0.01	.687	.826	***

Mean dependent var	0.556	SD dependent var	0.168
R-squared	0.516	Number of obs	56
F-test	13.575	Prob > F	0.000

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 55. Linear regression of Effective Number of Taxa by date and location inside corrals (In) vs. outside of corrals (Out).

ENT	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Date: base July 16	0
August 13	-2.054	.356	-5.77	< 0.01	-2.769	-1.34	***
September 3	-2.113	.356	-5.94	< 0.01	-2.828	-1.398	***
October 8	-2.216	.356	-6.23	< 0.01	-2.931	-1.502	***
InOut: base In	0
Out	-.987	.263	-3.76	< 0.01	-1.515	-.46	***
Constant	5.184	.269	19.30	< 0.01	4.645	5.723	***

Mean dependent var	3.235	SD dependent var	1.385
R-squared	0.571	Number of obs	56
F-test	16.988	Prob > F	0.000

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Appendix 56. Brief description of important invertebrate taxa found in our study 2024.

Chironomids

Two important chironomid taxa collected in our study that were indicators of conditions within the limnocorrals were *Cladotanytarsus* sp. and *Glyptotendipes* sp. The latter being a very good indicator of the periphyton community growing on the inside of corrals.

Cladotanytarsus sp.

There are 28 known (described) species of the genus *Cladotanytarsus* known from the northern hemisphere, but the larvae of most species remain undescribed. The larvae are found in many kinds of aquatic habitats: streams, rivers, lakes, ponds, brackish estuaries, and hot springs. They build silty sessile cases of silk and fine detritus. Hilsenhoff gave the genus a tolerance value of 7.0, indicating that he found them tolerant of adverse organically enriched habitats, but that they were more facultative. In Western Rivers, they can be found in a wide range of habitats, often among deposits of sand mixed silt, at locations that do not support large populations of *Chironomus* or *Glyptotendipes*. The specimens found in Utah Lake have smaller Lauterborne organs than most specimens we have collected in western rivers. Most of the 11 *Cladotanytarsus* species observed by Epler (2001) from the southeastern USA have not been formally named and have temporary letter designations.

Glyptotendipes sp.

Glyptotendipes larvae live among silt and other fine organic sediments of still or slow-moving eutrophic waters. Larvae often incorrectly field identified as “*Chironomus* sp.” because of their size and red color. Hilsenhoff (1987) gave this genus an HBI tolerance value of 10.0, the maximum (the same as *Chironomus*), because of their occurrence in very eutrophic environments. However, many species are most often associated with benthic algae in these

environments, although some may burrow between the bark and cambium of submerged wood. There are about 25 species known as adults, but the larval taxonomy remains “confused since its establishment” (Anderson et al. 2013).

In addition, *Parachironomus* sp. was a strong indicator of the periphyton community, but it occurred in relatively low densities (Figure 49). This taxon has been shown to prefer macrophytes substrates, including *Juncus* sp. (a type of rush) (Bazzanti et al. 2010, Čerba et al. 2023).

Segmented worms

Segmented worms are quintessential decomposers. Three segmented worm taxa were strong indicators of the periphyton assemblages, the lumbricid *Eiseniella* sp., Oligochaeta, and Naididae. Naidids were only found in the periphyton communities.

Ostracods

Ostracods are microphagous, which means they feed on tiny organisms and organic particles in the water. Their diet can vary depending on the species and the environment they live in but typically includes bacteria, algae, diatoms, detritus, and other tiny invertebrates. Some are herbivorous and feed primarily on algae or diatoms, while others are omnivorous and consume a mix of algae, bacteria, and other dead organic material. Ostracods were only found in the periphyton community.